

eDNAAqua-Plan
NEXT GENERATION OF AQUATIC BIODIVERSITY MONITORING

D3.3

Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility

Deliverable 3.3

Work Package 3

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document information

Grant agreement	101112800
Project acronym	eDNAqua-Plan
Project title	A Plan towards an eDNA reference library and data repository for Aquatic Organisms, navigating Europe towards the next generation biodiversity monitoring
Deliverable title	Infrastructure/services, linking and compatibility
Deliverable number	3.3
Work package title	Data Standards, Data Linking & Compatibility
Work package number	3
Lead beneficiary	VLIZ
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Due date	28-February-2026
Submission date	02- March-2026
Dissemination level	Public
Type of deliverable	Report

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Executive summary

This deliverable maps the **European aquatic eDNA “digital ecosystem”** – the connected (and often disconnected) set of repositories, standards, taxonomies, and web services that underpin **routine, comparable, and reusable** eDNA-based biodiversity monitoring. It complements **D3.1** (curated reference libraries) and **D3.2** (metadata standards for eDNA repositories) by focusing specifically on **connectivity (linking)** and **interoperability (compatibility)** across infrastructures, and by highlighting the gaps that impede end-to-end traceability from biodiversity observations back to sequences and physical samples.

Purpose and scope

- Provide a **landscape and gap analysis** of infrastructures that publish biodiversity observations and related environmental data, and how they connect to genomics repositories, reference libraries, taxonomic backbones, and biobanks/culture collections.
- Emphasis is on **open, non-commercial infrastructures**, and on *how data are exposed and linked*, not on building proof-of-concept systems (which is deferred to the WP5 blueprint/roadmap).

Key findings (what works well)

- **Strong adoption of biodiversity standards** among major biodiversity infrastructures:
 - Metadata commonly use **EML** (often XML), and biodiversity data commonly use **Darwin Core / DwC-A**.
 - Major aggregators (notably **GBIF and OBIS**) enable a “**publish once, share many times**” model via nodes/partners and the **IPT**, supporting broad dissemination and a degree of standardisation and QA.
- **Genomics infrastructures** rely heavily on established formats (e.g., **FASTA/FASTQ**) and metadata vocabularies (GSC **MlxS**), with BioSample/BioProject acting as critical metadata layers for sequence archives.
- Across domains, there is meaningful (though uneven) use of **persistent identifiers (PIDs)** to reference related objects (sequences, projects, samples), and much dataset discovery and description metadata is provided in XML; both providing a foundation for stronger linking.

Main gaps and barriers (why linking/compatibility still breaks)

1. **Links often exist, but are not robust or machine-actionable**
 - Cross-system references are frequently **PIDs or strings**, not resolvable **URIs**, which slows navigation and limits automated integration.
2. **Taxonomic interoperability remains a major friction point**
 - Multiple taxonomic backbones are in active use (e.g., WoRMS/CoL/GBIF backbone vs. NCBI taxonomy), with **insufficient consistent use of taxon IDs in metadata**, and incomplete/opaque mapping processes.
3. **Metadata completeness and consistency are uneven**
 - Many repositories and stakeholders allow “**as provided**” free text and optional fields; critical eDNA provenance elements (workflow steps, parameters, reference library versions, confidence/quality indicators) are often missing or inconsistently and incompletely represented.

4. **Web services are generally developer-friendly, not ecosystem-interoperable**
 - Many APIs are “**documented & discoverable**”, but not semantically aligned across stakeholders; the ecosystem needs movement toward **semantic interoperability** (machine-understandable outputs) to enable scalable federation.
5. **Provenance chains are fragile in practice**
 - Use-case tracing from GBIF/OBIS to underlying sequence repositories is *possible*, but **manual** and **time-consuming**, with breaks such as missing reciprocal links, missing licences in some views, and loss of related-publication links through intermediate systems.
6. **Biobanks and culture collections (physical anchors) are digitally heterogeneous**
 - There is a “**digital divide**” between institutions with mature LIMS and publishing pipelines versus smaller collections relying on spreadsheets/local databases, producing “**dark data**” (high-value assets that are not findable through global catalogues).
 - A recurring “**broken feedback loop**”: sequences are submitted to archives, but accession numbers are not reliably pushed back to the originating collection records.

Compatibility recommendations (high-level direction)

- Increase use of **resolvable identifiers (URIs/CURIEs)** for taxa, samples, sequences, and vocabularies; reduce reliance on unqualified strings.
- Strengthen cross-domain alignment between **DwC** (biodiversity) and **MixS/BioSamples** (genomics) through clearer mappings and shared practices.
- Promote metadata exports that support **machine-understandability** (e.g., JSON-LD / RDF approaches, versioned feeds such as LDES where suitable), enabling automated knowledge-graph style integration.
- For physical collections: adopt stronger identifier practices and biobanking extensions (e.g., **GGBN extensions alongside DwC**) and implement processes to close the **biobank ↔ sequence archive feedback loop**.
- Support inclusion of less digitally mature nodes via a “**publishing proxy**” approach and **template-based submission**, so valuable holdings are not excluded.

What this enables for WP5

The landscaping and gap analysis in D3.3 is positioned as direct input to the WP5 blueprint/roadmap: it identifies **where links are missing or weak**, where standards alignment is most impactful (notably around GBIF/OBIS and INSDC ecosystems), and what technical patterns (persistent IDs, semantic exposure, interoperable services) are most likely to deliver a **coordinated, federated European eDNA monitoring infrastructure**.

The iceberg of “dark data” in aquatic biodiversity monitoring. Only a small fraction of high-quality biological data is visible through public infrastructures. The majority remains digitally inaccessible due to missing identifiers, standards, or publishing capacity, rather than scientific limitations.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASV	Amplicon Sequence Variant
API	Application Programming Interface
BBGM	Botanical Garden and Botanical Museum
BeBOP	Better Biomolecular Ocean Practices
BODC	British Oceanographic Data Centre
BOLD	Barcode Of Life Data systems
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CEFAS	Centre for Environment, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Science
CCAP	Culture Collection of Algae & Protozoa
CIIMAR	Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research
CoL	Catalogue of Life
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CSV/TSV	Comma/Tab-separated variable (spreadsheet)
dbGaP	The Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DSMZ	Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen
DwC-A and DwC	Darwin Core (data format and a vocabulary)
EC	European Commission
EDMED	European Directory of Marine Environmental Data
eDNA	Environmental DNA
EEA	European Environment Agency
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
EMBRC-ERIC	European Marine Biological Resource Centre - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
EML	Ecological Metadata Language
EoL	Encyclopedia of Life
ERDDAP	Environmental Research Division Data Access Program.
EU	European Union
EASIN	European Alien Species Information Network
EurOBIS	European Ocean Biodiversity Information System
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FAIRe	FAIR eDNA project
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GEO	Gene Expression Omnibus
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GeoJSON	Standard for geographical data interchange using JSON
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFBio	German Federation for Biological data
GIS	Geographical Information System
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GSC	Genomics Standards Consortium
GUID	Globally Unique Identifier
ILVO	Instituut voor Landbouw-, Visserij- & Voedingsonderzoek

INSDC	International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (NBCI, ENA, DDNJ (DNA Databank of Japan))
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
IPT	Integrated Publishing Toolkit
ITIS	Integrated Taxonomic Information System
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data
LIB	Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change
LDES	Linked Data Event Stream
LifeWatch-ERIC/ LW ERIC	E-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research - European Research Infrastructure Consortium
LIMS	Laboratory Information Management System
LLM	Large Language Model
LOD	Linked Open Data
LSID	Life Science Identifier
m2m / m2d	Machine 2 Machine / Machine 2 Developer web services
MBA	Marine Biological Association
MBLWHOI	Marine Biological Laboratory Woods Hole Library
MfN	Museum für Naturkunde Berlin
MIEM	Minimum Information for Environmental Metabarcoding
MixS	Minimum Information about any (x) Sequence
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information, short for NCBI GenBank
NCEI	National Centers for Environmental Information
NOAA	National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Administration
NORCCA	Norwegian Culture Collection of Algae
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocols for Metadata Harvesting
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
OGS Services	Services following the Open Geospatial Consortium standards
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
PID	Persistent Unique Identifier
RBINS	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences
REST API	API following the representational state transfer architectural style
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise(s)
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SRA	Sequence Read Archive
SSBE	Seascope Belgium
TXT	Text
UI	User Interface
UNEP	UN Environment Programme
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization

URI/URL	Uniform Resource Identifier / Locator
UVEG	Universitat de Valencia
VLIZ	Vlaams Instituut Voor de Zee
WoRMS	World Register of Marine Species
WP	Work Package(s)
WSDL	Web Services Description Language
XLSX	Data export format for Excel spreadsheets
XML	Extensible Markup Language

1. Scope of this report

Harmonising monitoring practices and methodologies across Europe has become an increasingly pressing priority (Kissling et al. 2026)⁹. Beyond standardising protocols, making monitoring data openly available and aligning the tools and pathways used to share it are essential steps toward ensuring that data generated through monitoring efforts is comparable across monitoring programs and countries, as well as reusable across the wider scientific community. In aquatic biomonitoring, environmental DNA (eDNA) methodologies, and metabarcoding in particular, have matured to the point where integration into routine monitoring programmes is now a realistic prospect. Realising this potential requires the availability of quality-controlled, curated reference systems for taxonomic assignment, and a digital infrastructure built on connected, interoperable data and metadata systems that allow eDNA data to be effectively reused in support of broader aquatic biodiversity monitoring goals.

The eDNAqua-Plan project addresses these challenges systematically. The project evaluates the current landscape of aquatic eDNA data (WP2, WP4), develops recommendations to improve its accessibility, interoperability, and overall effectiveness (WP3, WP4), and will ultimately translate these findings into a concrete blueprint and roadmap for the infrastructure needed to bring the envisioned future landscape into being (WP5). The landscaping work covers the different types of data that are produced throughout an eDNA monitoring workflow, the metadata that should be recorded alongside the data, the repositories where these data and metadata can or should be submitted, as well as the way in which repositories format, expose and exchange data. This report, D3.3, focuses on the overall connectivity of the eDNA data landscape. It complements D3.1, which develops recommendations for curated reference libraries, and D3.2, which evaluates metadata standards for eDNA repositories.

More specifically, the D3.3 report is structured around the following tasks:

1. Landscape the biodiversity data infrastructures: their (meta)data and web services.
2. Look at the commonality and connectivity between the biodiversity and various types of genomics data infrastructures in the eDNA digital ecosystem: how and what (meta)data they publish, how and what they share with each other, the standards and formats used.
3. Look at the role of biobanks and culture collections in the scientific and the digital landscape, at how they handle their (meta)data and link to the other components of the digital ecosystem.
4. Taxonomic interoperability and mapping.
5. To highlight the results of the work of T3.1, T3.2, WP2's gap analysis, and WP4's use cases, related to the gaps that present barriers to a smoothly connected and coordinated digital ecosystem.

This landscaping and gap analysis will provide input to the development of a blueprint for the digital ecosystem. In the original proposal, Task 3.3 was also charged with proposing how to fill these gaps, but as this will be provided in the blueprint (Task 5.1), it will not be covered here.

⁹ Kissling, W. D., Lumbierres, M., Lyche Solheim, A., Liqueste, C., Breeze, T. D., Bonn, A., ... Pereira, H. M. (2026). Building the backbone for Europe's biodiversity monitoring. *Nature Reviews Biodiversity*. doi: 10.1038/s44358-026-00140-6

A list of stakeholders was put together in the first year of the project by all the WPs, based on their personal knowledge, online searches, and online catalogues. Those stakeholders we considered for this deliverable are:

- Data infrastructures that publish biodiversity data: observations of biological organisms with associated taxonomic, geographic, temporal, quantitative, and/or environmental information
- Data infrastructures that publish omics data: focussing on DNA and RNA sequences and bioinformatics analysis results, primarily ASVs and OTUs
- Data brokers, that direct data to different data infrastructures for publications
- Reference libraries, that provide reference data to use for taxonomic identification via sequence analysis
- Organisations and institutes that perform bioinformatics including computational biological analysis.
- Taxonomic backbones and catalogues, which provide taxonomic classification, names and identifiers
- Biobanks and culture collections, which store samples that are or could be used in omics analysis

N.B. Our focus is primarily on those stakeholders that provide their data for open consumption, as opposed to commercial enterprises.

2. Biodiversity data infrastructures

To complement the work of Task 3.1 (reference libraries) and Task 3.2 (eDNA repositories), in this first part of Task 3.3 we carried out a landscaping and gap analysis of stakeholders that publish biodiversity, environmental, and marine data (excluding those focussed on physical or chemical data). For this we looked primarily at those that were based in Europe, but for completeness we also included stakeholders outside of Europe. Most of the data infrastructures investigated publish observations of organisms at a time and place with associated information and data, but a subset were focussed solely on publishing species identifications from DNA. A list of all 51 stakeholders investigated can be found in Appendix [A1](#); this table also includes the wider set of stakeholders that are the subjects of Sec. [3](#).

2.1 (Meta)data, standards, and linking

For this first analysis, we focussed on the stakeholders that cover the following scientific domains: earth, environment, biodiversity, biology, marine, selecting out 27 from the list of 50 that were investigated in total (the rest are covered in Sec. [3](#)). All of these stakeholders do or are ready to include data based on DNA results, this is often in the form of links from the organism identification to the sequences from where these were derived.

We collected information on the stakeholder via manual searches of their websites, searches from links identified in AI overview from Google search using, publications found via internet keyword searches, Wikipedia, etc. For some stakeholders we also browsed their (meta)data catalogues and inspected the metadata records and datasets. A questionnaire was sent out to a subset of the stakeholders near the start of the work, but after receiving only seven replies, we realised that questionnaire-fatigue rendered this approach worthless.

While our landscape analysis focused on obtaining the wider, rather than the deeper picture, the information collected as described above and detailed in Secs 2 and 3 cannot be

considered as exhaustive. For most stakeholders investigated, not all the information could be found on their websites (e.g. what happens within their own databases, their data models, and what they are currently working on), and it was only possible to carry-out our manual investigation of their actual (meta)data on very small subsets of their total holdings. Nevertheless, we are confident that the results are representative of the reality of these aspects of the eDNA data ecosystem

The data-collection template – “questions” investigated and the standardised “answers” – is in Appendix [A2](#), together with a link to the collected data spreadsheet.

We collected data on their

- Metadata and data standards used
- Taxonomic backbones used
- Other vocabularies used

We also looked at the connections between stakeholders regarding the

- Source of their data
- Harvesters of their data
- Organisations linked to in their data and metadata

Finally, we investigated

- DNA-relevant (meta)data collected

We used ChatGPT to analyse some of the collected data. To ensure reliable and useful results, we tested our analysis on a small subset of the stakeholders first, after which we created a standardised approach to our “answers” in the spreadsheet. We also carried out random manual checks when analysing the full set of stakeholders. (*A-posteriori*, we realised that ChatGPT was less useful than expected for analysing the data in the form that we provided it in: we believe this is because LLMs, being *language*-based, require more wordy inputs than our terse spreadsheet provided.)

Collecting the information was a lengthy process. Not all stakeholders provide the same clarity of information about their (meta)data standards, models, formats, vocabularies, and about what they do/do not do with the data they publish. *This part of the digital ecosystem could definitely be improved, e.g. by using a standardised way to describe the “what” and “how” of each data system.* We feel that this is important information to convey not just for those wanting to landscape the digital ecosystem, but also for those submitters and users of the data (both human and machine) so they can fully understand the data they are working with: what happens with those data, what you can and cannot expect from the data, and how those data can link to other data within the wider digital ecosystem.

When considering the landscape of data and metadata in the digital ecosystem, it is necessary to bear in mind that different data infrastructures have different data models and structure their data and metadata in varying ways. Many infrastructures hold more traditional catalogue metadata records which include the links to their downloadable data (GBIF, PANAGEA); for others the metadata *are* the data, i.e. there is no separate downloadable dataset (BioSamples, Catalogue of Life); another group have several layers of metadata that sit on top of one or more data objects (INSDC, with its different types of accession numbers, including BioSample IDs). It is also the case that some infrastructures have data formats in which much of the information we are interested in are contained *within* the data, rather than / as well as within the metadata (DwC used by GBIF, and the spreadsheet templates provided

by PANGAEA), while for others all the information we are interested in are contained in their metadata only.

For our investigations, we separated metadata from data. “Data” generally means data files that can be accessed or downloaded: DwC files from GBIF, FASTA files from ENA, images, spreadsheets, etc. “Metadata” usually means that which is used by repositories to make the data they hold discoverable: author, title, licence, abstract, keywords, etc. However, where a stakeholder provides their users with data that is only information with no related downloadable data files, we consider this a “metadata-only” stakeholder: BioSamples metadata, a listing of collected facts on a species, etc. The reason we define these two types of metadata provisions is a technical one: dataset-discovery metadata is often stored (in the backend) separately to the data, follow metadata schemas and are exported in metadata formats; while metadata-as-data are also stored in their own (backend) database but usually do not follow metadata schemas and standards. Additionally, these two types of metadata are often exposed to the web in different ways, via different interfaces, APIs, and protocols. This is hence something to be taken into account by Task 5.1 when drawing up their Roadmap.

The 27 stakeholders we investigated are in the scientific domain of: biodiversity, earth, environment, marine, biology, but excluding those classified as “biodiversity genomics” which are included in the analysis of Sec. 3. Of these 27, 23 provide both data and metadata, 2 provide only data, and 2 provide only metadata (as we define it). This is tabulated in the data spreadsheet provided via Appendix A2.

These 27 organisations are: OBIS, GBIF, EurOBIS/EMODnet, PANGAEA, GFBio, WISE Marine, WISE Freshwater, PlutoF, FINBIF, SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal, PNDB Data Repository, EnviDat, DASSH - MEDIN, NBN Atlas, BCO-DMO, VertNet, Dandjoo, Atlas of Living Australia (ALA), Observation, HELCOM Biodiversity database, iNaturalist, Freshwater Biodiversity Data Portal, ODIS / Ocean Info Hub, NIOZ Dataverse, SDBI, Freshwater Ecology, MarineInfo.

2.1.1 Schemas, standards, and taxonomy in (meta)data

(Meta)data formats, schemas, standards

Here we look at the (meta)data formats, schemas, standards, and export methods used by the 27 stakeholders. When inspecting the tables, bear in mind that any stakeholder can have more than one type of standard, schema, or method in use.

The most common metadata schemas and standards, and export formats used are presented in Figs 1 and 2.

Other than the unknowns, we found no stakeholders that did not use some kind of standard or schema for formatting or for exporting their metadata. The most common schema is EML, which is exported in the XML format. This is used by OBIS, EurOBIS/EMODnet and GBIF and a number of other stakeholders. EML – Ecological Metadata Language – was designed for these types of data, and so it is no surprise it is well used. While EML does have a few downsides (for example, it only recently started to accommodate some semantic annotation), it is a community-agreed, maintained, and machine-readable schema. Work is ongoing to map and convert EML to JSON-LD ([emld](https://docs.ropensci.org/emld/)¹⁰), and this will greatly enhance its machine-understandability, and hence its cross-domain interoperability.

¹⁰ <https://docs.ropensci.org/emld/>

DwC and DublinCore are also popular as controlled vocabularies used in metadata. These are also well-maintained (TDWG for DwC) and community-agreed. ISO 19115 and 19139 are for geographical/spatial metadata, as is INSPIRE. DataCite is also one of the more common formats: while being very interoperable and widely-used, it does not accommodate taxonomic names or measurement types.

The category “in-house” was used when it appeared that the infrastructure was using its own model of metadata fields. Both of the organisations that fall under this category do use standard for metadata export: EnviDat export metadata as XML using the schemas from DataCite, ISO 19139 and GCMD DIF; BCO-DMO used ISO 19115 and DataCite.

Overall, the use of metadata schemas and standards is strong among these stakeholders, and there are many of them in use. The interoperability of the metadata export is also quite good, with many using XML and JSON/JSON-LD. XML is machine-readable, but it is not guaranteed to also be machine-understandable¹¹, as semantic annotation is not a requirement. (The same comment applies to JSON). JSON-LD, the next most popular format, is both machine-readable and -understandable and is therefore highly interoperable. We note that mapping XML to JSON-LD, especially where the data infrastructure already uses controlled vocabularies, is not a particularly onerous task and would greatly improve the interoperability of the metadata, in particular cross-domain.

PANGAEA has its own formatted XML. Their metadata incorporate controlled vocabularies and schemas (ISO 19X, DublinCore, DwC, etc). This approach allows them to incorporate the wide range of vocabularies and standards that their broad scope of data require; they could improve mainly by having a schema in JSON-LD rather than XML.

We note that one stakeholder (MarineInfo) provided metadata via an LDES feed. LDES is a technical standard for publishing immutable, versioned data as an append-only stream, and so allowing systems to synchronise and consume data efficiently using Linked Data principles and RDF.

In summary, there is good use of standards and schemas: the main standards/schemas are EML and DwC, and the main export format is XML with JSON-LD a distant second, but stronger use of export formats that accommodate machine-understandability as well as readability is recommended, in particular to allow cross-domain interoperability (this include across the eDNA digital ecosystem).

¹¹ Machine-readable: a machine can open, process, and read (parse) the digital object. Machine-understandable: the data includes semantic context so that a machine can additionally interpret and act on the information

Figure 1 Metadata standards/schemas occurrences among the stakeholders

Figure 2 Metadata export format occurrences among the stakeholders

Next, the most common data standards and export formats are presented in Figs 3 and 4, and export methods in Table 1.

Figure 3 Data standards/schemas occurrences among the stakeholders

Figure 4 Data export format occurrences among the stakeholders

Table 1: Statistics on standards among the biodiversity data stakeholders

Data export method	No.
web page	24
API	19
web tools	5
IPT	4
OAI-PMH	3
GIS, ERDDAP	1 each
None, Unknown	1 each

The [DwC-A data format](#)¹² is the most popular data standard. DwC-A is for biodiversity data, and it is not one that is easily adopted by biodiversity infrastructures that cover a wider scientific scope (e.g. physical and chemical data), [PANGAEA](#)¹³ being one example (although PANGAEA does work with GBIF to export data as DwC-A). However, the DwC vocabulary *can be used by anyone*. (We note that PANGAEA is currently working on its templates for DNA-based data submission.)

It is encouraging that more use of CSV/TSV is made than XLSX as a data standard (format). While Excel is a useful tool for collecting and analysing data, is it not a good tool for producing openly accessible, interoperable data. CSV/TSV is also the most popular format for exporting data to data users, encouragingly more so than XLSX.

For the export methods, very many of the stakeholders (24 out of the 27) provide APIs for accessing their databases. The majority provide downloads via (meta)data webpages or a web tool or portal; the few that do not are data brokers (who do not themselves provide access to the data but link to wherever they are published). The Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT) is used by GBIF and OBIS and a few others to publish DwC-A files and make them publicly accessible on their platforms.

Additionally, 15 of the stakeholders provided data templates. This is very encouraging: templates allow for a better degree of data standardisation, and improve the quality (and reduce the curation requirements) of the submitted data.

See Sec. [2.2](#) for an analysis of the web services of some of these stakeholders.

In summary, a wide range of data formats are found for ingesting and exporting data, which is not surprising given the range of data types that are accommodated by these stakeholders (even biodiversity data contains more than just occurrences). Much biodiversity data is recorded in spreadsheets, and the popularity of CSV (an open format) is encouraging. To ensure that the data in these spreadsheets are interoperable and reusable (the I and R of FAIR), data templates should be offered and required by all data infrastructures.

¹² https://manual.obis.org/data_format.html

¹³ <https://www.pangaea.de/>

DwC-A and the DwC vocabulary

Darwin Core Archive (DwC-A)¹⁴ is an extension of DublinCore, and is a package (zip) for sharing data, made up of CSV and TXT files following a star schema. It uses the DwC vocabulary¹⁵ which is maintained by the Biodiversity Information Standard (TDWG, formerly the Taxonomic Databases Working Group), and EML-XML as the dataset discovery and description metadata schema. The DwC-A format contains extensions for occurrences (observations of organisms) and events, among others, and although DwC-A cannot contain multimedia, sequence or ASV/OTU files, it can contain links to those where they are made available.

A DNA-derived data extension¹⁶ to DwC-A has been proposed. The terms for the extension come largely from the MIxS standard (Minimum Information of any (x) Sequence) maintained by the Genomics Standard Consortium (GSC), with additional terms agreed on by the consortium that created this extension. While these terms have not yet been officially accepted by TDWG – they are still undergoing updates – this extension is now used by GBIF and OBIS, with a handful of datasets of this type having already been published.

The DwC vocabulary reaches a good level of interoperability.

Strengths:

- Global, dereferenceable URIs
- Multiple machine-readable serialisations
- Clear human definitions
- Applied in global biodiversity infrastructures

Limitations as a semantic ontology:

- The current RDF exposure of DwC mainly treats terms as flat properties and classes; it does not provide deep OWL¹⁷ axioms, class hierarchies, or logical constraints (e.g., domain/range, equivalences, restrictions)
- Many DwC terms are effectively literal attributes rather than relationships between entities
- The conceptual model is not machine-processable; model isn't published as OWL/SHACL¹⁸, limiting automated reasoning and strict validation

Potential improvements:

- Publish a formal ontology version of the conceptual model (this would enable reasoners to infer class membership and validate instance data more robustly).
- Define classes as `rdfs:Class` or `owl:Class`, and properties with domain/range constraints.
- Include axioms like `subClassOf`, `equivalentClass`, `inverseProperty`, etc.
- Link to external vocabularies with explicit semantics: having formal mappings or alignment files (e.g., SSSOM¹⁹) between DwC and other vocabularies (MIxS, Schema.org, ENVO²⁰ etc.) increases cross-domain interoperability.

¹⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Darwin_Core_Archive

¹⁵ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/>

¹⁶ <https://rs.gbif.org/extensions.html>

¹⁷ Web Ontology Language

¹⁸ Shapes Constraint Language

¹⁹ <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

²⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/envo>

- Expose richer term annotations: Including metadata such as creation date, contributors, provenance, usage examples, and licensing in machine-readable form (using Dublin Core, SKOS²¹, Void²², etc.) would make it more self-describing.

At the time of writing this report, a new Darwin Core publishing model, the Darwin Core Data Package (DwC-DP), has completed public review and is awaiting formal adoption. This exchange format extends the Frictionless Data Package specification and replaces the star schema of Darwin Core Archives (where an event or occurrence table stands at its core), with a fully relational model in which multiple tables can reference each other directly. This new model eliminates the need to duplicate information across rows or tables, significantly reducing file sizes which is especially relevant for DNA-based biodiversity data. Both GBIF and OBIS are actively preparing to support DwC-DP, with pipeline development and updated tooling planned for 2026–2027, while DwC-A remains a valid and supported format in the interim.

Taxonomic naming systems

We looked at the range of taxonomic naming systems/backbones that were used over the 27 stakeholders, at where they were used (data and/or metadata), whether IDs were used, and at the condition (mandatory, recommended, options) on this information in the (meta)data. In Figs. 5 and 6 are the statistics for the used taxonomic systems in data and metadata, and the types of IDs used for taxon names in data and metadata.

Most of the stakeholders do use widely-used taxonomic naming systems and their taxon IDs in their data, although noticeably fewer use taxon IDs in their metadata. We believe that EML is the only schema among those in use by these stakeholders that specifically provides fields for taxon names and IDs in the dataset discovery metadata (DwC also provides for taxon fields, but these are in the data).

Of those stakeholders falling under the “none” for the metadata, three (GFBio, ODIS, and PlutoF) do not provide their own metadata (the first is a broker, the second only harvests metadata, the third is a data management platform).

One possible issue including taxonomic information in metadata is where the number of names is in the dozens or more (which will often be the case for eDNA data), although there are strategies that can be employed to group the names along the taxonomic tree and so reduce the list to make it still useful for search purposes. It is important for dataset discovery (in particular for *machine* discovery) that some level of taxonomic information is given in the metadata.

Two of the stakeholders using “in-house” are the citizen science platforms iNaturalist and Observation, which provide similar user interfaces and information. Both use an in-house system which draws from a number of taxonomic sources (including WoRMS) for the different types of organisms they cover. Taxon names are linked to URIs on their own web sites, which provide various information about the organisms and provide them with unique PIDs. For these stakeholders, the taxonomic information is found in the metadata, while the data are maps, images etc for which this is not necessary. PANGAEA also has an in-house taxonomic vocabulary that incorporates taxonomic systems such as WoRMS.

²¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simple_Knowledge_Organization_System

²² <https://www.w3.org/TR/void/>

Concerning the format in which the taxonomic information are provided, we investigated whether strings, PIDs, URIs, or something else were used. Where taxonomic names are only given as a string – *Solea solea* (Linnaeus, 1758) – it is not possible to be sure from which taxonomic authority that name derives, and hence its provenance is unknown; and if something related to that name changes at that authority, this information is lost. If instead a formatted PID or a URI from the authority is used, it is possible to locate the webpage with the information about that name and hence complete the provenance trail and be informed of any changes to that name. Where a PID is used – BOLD:AAB5850 or ncbitaxon:90069 – the identifier is guaranteed to be unique, although only within that system, and locatable on the web, but only by humans (who will understand to which website those PIDs belong). A URI – <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/taxonomy/90069/> – is guaranteed to be globally unique and web-locatable and hence machine-readable, being thus the most interoperable approach to take. LSIDs as used by WoRMS – urn:lsid:marinespecies.org:taxname:127160 – fall between PIDs and URIs in their machine interoperability as they are globally unique but not directly locatable on the web.

A greater use of at least formatted PIDs, if not full URIs, should be encouraged for taxonomic names given in data and metadata, so that the provenance trail is complete, and so that they are machine-interoperable.

Table 2 lists the statistics for the conditions set on the use of taxonomic names and IDs in the (meta)data. Almost half (data) and just over a third (metadata) make this field mandatory. Note that stakeholders that accommodate other types of data cannot make this field mandatory, one example being GFBio (a data broker). For quite a few stakeholders this field was not relevant or we could not find the information. We therefore conclude that the majority of stakeholders that hold data related to organisms make it mandatory to include a name. Very few stakeholders, however, make the IDs mandatory or recommended. This is unfortunate for the interoperability of the (meta)data.

Table 2 Statistics on conditions set for taxonomic information

Condition on taxonomic ID	No. used in data	No. used in metadata	Condition on taxonomic name	No. used in data	No. used in metadata
Mandatory	4	2	Mandatory	14	11
Recommended	5	3	Recommended	1	2
Optional	3	2	Optional	0	1
As provided	2	1	As provided	1	2
None	2	8	None	1	5
Unknown	4	8	Unknown	4	3
N/A	6	3	N/A	6	3

Figure 5 Taxonomic systems used in metadata (upper) and data (lower)

Figure 6 The types of IDs used for taxonomic names in metadata (upper) and data (lower)

A brief introduction to the taxonomic systems as listed here:

- The GBIF taxonomic backbone is a combination of numerous taxonomic sources: CoL, WoRMS, iBOL, UNITE, ITIS, to name a few, including traditional and molecular taxonomic naming systems.
- CoL also compiles data from other authoritative taxonomic sources, primarily from the traditional naming approaches based on morphology, but it is also incorporating those derived from molecular approaches²³. CoL and GBIF are in fact working together and “...have united their capabilities to make ChecklistBank (the CoL infrastructure) a consistent foundation and repository for all CoL datasets and any other openly licensed species lists, including those mobilised and registered through GBIF.”²⁴

²³ <https://www.catalogueoflife.org/building/classification>

²⁴ <https://www.checklistbank.org/>

- WoRMS maintains its own curated catalogue and identification system (LSIDs), it is ocean focussed and has its own taxonomic curators, but also incorporates other systems that cover fish, non-fish marine life, algae, viruses, and more. WoRMS is the taxonomic backbone preferred by OBIS and EurOBIS/EMODnet, being an authoritative and curated taxonomic system.
- BOLD does not provide names for organisms, rather so-called BINs²⁵ – Barcode Index Numbers – which is based on their one taxonomic backbone and “...which cluster DNA barcode sequences into OTUs that often correspond to species. Each BIN is automatically generated, uniquely identified, and linked to metadata, including taxonomy, specimen images, and collection details.” Users can use these BINs in their own data.
- NCBI Taxonomy²⁶ is the standard nomenclature used by the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC). It is not a formal nomenclatural authority but a curated classification that serves as a central organising hub for sequences deposited in GenBank, ENA, and DDBJ. It is heavily biased towards organisms with sequenced genetic material and often includes informal names (e.g., "uncultured bacterium") essential for molecular studies but not present in traditional Linnaean authorities.
- ITIS (Integrated Taxonomic Information System) is a partnership of US, Canadian, and Mexican agencies that provides authoritative taxonomic information. While it has a strong focus on North American biota, it offers global coverage for many groups and serves as a critical standard for widely used identifiers (TSNs - Taxonomic Serial Numbers).
- UNITE is a specialist reference library and taxonomic system focused on fungi. It is unique in that it uses Species Hypotheses (SHs) based on the ITS gene region to classify organisms. This allows for stable communication about fungal species (using DOIs) even when formal Linnaean names are missing or ambiguous, bridging the gap between molecular clustering and traditional taxonomy.

More information on taxonomic systems, in particular mapping between NCBI and WoRMS, can be found in Sec. [4.5](#).

In summary, many taxonomic systems are in use, which is not surprising given the range of types of organisms on our planet and recorded by our stakeholders. Several backbones which incorporate many different systems exist, which is encouraging although needs to be well maintained to avoid inconsistencies. We did not investigate how the incorporation is done, but this is an area where LOD, URIs, LDES feeds can help automate the process for the provider and receiver. This will be explored further in D5.1. Insufficient use is made of URIs to refer to the names given in the data and the metadata, which leads to a loss of interoperability of this information.

Other vocabularies

We surveyed the range of other vocabularies used in the (meta)data of our stakeholders. The intention was not to get a full list – that would be too long – but to get an idea of how many stakeholders use vocabularies.

Greater use of vocabularies is found in data than in the metadata.

²⁵ <https://portal.boldsystems.org/bin>

²⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/docs/v2/data-processing/taxonomy-processing/taxonomy/>

- Data: DwC (including the DNA extension) (12), BODC (7), ENVO (5), ISO xxx (4), ABCD (3), MlxS (2), and more than a dozen geographical and keyword vocabularies were used. Two organisations accepted whatever was provided by the data submitter, and two had none.
- Metadata: as provided (13), none (4), INSPIRE (3), schema.org (3) (not strictly-speaking vocabularies, but they are standardised names with fixed definitions), in-house (2), DCAT (2), GEMET (2), WFD (2), and ten more with 1 each.

Vocabularies are important to use for interoperability, and this is equally true for data as for metadata. A wide range of vocabularies is used, which is not surprising given the scientific scope of these data. We find that the use of vocabularies is less common in the metadata than it is for data.

For the formats these vocabularies were provided in, strings were disappointingly very common for data (11) and metadata (6); with URIs are barely used in data (6) and metadata (2), and similarly for PIDs (4 and 1 respectively). “As provided by the data submitted” was fairly common for data (7) and metadata (9).

In summary, while many vocabularies are used, greater use of URIs (or at least PIDs) for those terms should be made. Greater use of vocabularies in the metadata is also recommended, especially as metadata are used to make data discoverable in the first place. Providing recommendations regarding which vocabularies are most suitable to use for eDNA data would make it easier for data submitters to include these terms and may encourage update by the data infrastructures who publish those data.

2.1.2 Connections between biodiversity stakeholders

To look at the connections that are made between the stakeholders we investigated

1. the sharing of (meta)data
2. (meta)data providing and receiving between stakeholders
3. what kind of external data are linked to from within (meta)data

Sharing of (meta)data

The organisations with which biodiversity data infrastructures connect include those in the wider eDNA digital ecosystem: we look at all of these in Sec. 3.2 while here we focus on the sharing of biodiversity (meta)data between biodiversity organisations.

GBIF and OBIS are the two largest biodiversity data infrastructures in our digital ecosystem. Both have a global reach, and include DNA-based results via the DNA extension²⁷. Both harvest data from their partners/nodes/providers and each other (via their nodes), providing a “publish once, share many times” approach for (meta)data. This approach allows their partners to have a degree of ownership (control, influence) in the process, so better embedding the concept of sharing and publishing interoperable data within the minds of the scientists, projects, and organisations that they publish data for. It also allows the effort of creating standards and curating data to be spread over many, reducing the resources required by any one.

²⁷ see <https://docs.gbif.org/publishing-dna-derived-data/en/> and https://manual.obis.org/dna_data

This (meta)data sharing also allows for a high level of standardisation – GBIF and OBIS both use the [DwC²⁸](#) standard (data formatting and vocabulary) and EML as the metadata schema (XML format) – leading to a high level of interoperability. Both use instances of the [IPT²⁹](#) to share data (from data submitters to nodes, and nodes to core), which performs quality checks as well as provides an interface for data access.

In addition, both provide tools (see Table 3), training, and documentation, which help scientists in submitting, finding, and using their data. OBIS is working on a [bioinformatics pipeline³⁰](#) and both GBIF and OBIS are looking at including the [FAIRe checklist³¹](#) in their standards³² (for more information on this, see the [Task 5.1 Blueprint workshop³³](#) report)

Table 3 Some OBIS and GBIF tools

URL	description
https://iobis.github.io/obistools/	OBIS Tools for data enhancement and quality control
https://seamap.env.duke.edu/	OBIS-SEAMAP
https://github.com/iobis/robis	OBIS R client for the OBIS API, including for finding DNA-based data
https://mapper.obis.org	OBIS mapper
https://sequence.obis.org/	OBIS Sequence search tool
https://manual.obis.org/ipt	OBIS IPT documentation
https://mdt.gbif.org/	GBIF Metabarcoding Toolkit
https://www.gbif.org/ipt	GBIF IPT
https://www.gbif.org/tools/data-validator/about	data validator
https://www.gbif.org/tools/species-lookup https://www.gbif.org/tools/name-parser	and species lookup tool and name parser
https://www.gbif.org/tools/sequence-id/about	documentation on the GBIF Sequence ID tool

²⁸ <https://dwc.tdwg.org/> fw

²⁹ <https://www.gbif.org/ipt>

³⁰ https://manual.obis.org/dna_data.html#how-to-find-genetic-data-in-obis

³¹ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

³² see https://manual.obis.org/dna_data.html#faire-checklist-development

³³ <https://zenodo.org/records/18833437>

URL	description
https://www.gbif.org/resource/search?content_Type=tool	dozens of other tools

There are some differences in how OBIS and GBIF accommodate DNA-based occurrences in their databases: for example OBIS prefers WoRMS as the taxonomic backbone, with the information to be included in the field scientificName/ID, with others (ITIS, BOLD, NCBI GenBank) to be added to taxonConceptID; while GBIF allows DNA-based taxonomy to be added to scientificName field, with taxonConceptID recommended for MOTUs (Molecular Operational Taxonomic Units). There are also some differences in the required / recommended metadata fields (see the next section).

Globally, GBIF have over 100 partners/nodes and 2700 publishers³⁴ who provide data. In Europe there are almost 40 partners. Partners each designate a “node” responsible for coordinating their activities. GBIF has a wide global reach, covering a good fraction of the world (exclusions include parts of north and central-southern Africa, Russia, and Central and East Asia). GBIF’s key DNA-related partners³⁵ include EMBL-EBI, ELIXIR, International Barcode of Life (iBOL), Catalogue of Life (CoL), TDWG, and OBIS, most of which are included among our investigated stakeholders.

OBIS has 36 nodes³⁶ spread over the globe (their gaps include Russia and north Africa): 29 regional and 7 thematic. EurOBIS is the Europe node (this also being one of our investigated stakeholders).

In summary, the main driver of data sharing in the academic biodiversity world, at least, is GBIF and OBIS and their partner/node model. This approach to “publish once, share many times” is recommended by eDNAqua-Plan (see [eDNAqua-Plan Milestone 7](#)³⁷) wherever that is possible. There are some considerations that need to be taken into account (ensuring that harvested (meta)data are properly linked to the source record, dealing with duplications, dealing with corrections, etc) which are highlighted in the report on the [Task 5.1 Blueprint workshop](#)³⁸. *This approach is a significant enabler in the biodiversity data world, by making a great deal of data more findable, accessible, and interoperable than would otherwise be the case.* However, it also means that GBIF, especially, and OBIS become *de facto* leaders, while others will follow their requirements. Currently, the limited mandatory metadata and lack of strong requirements on the accessibility of the information included in the metadata (i.e. use of URIs to ensure references are findable online), *allows for the publication of biodiversity data that is less accessible and reusable than FAIR principles recommend.* This permissive vs rigor metadata tradeoff is common, and understandable, in large biological data repositories. Ultimately as discussed earlier it needs the community to better reward data generators and fund data repositories. This topic was discussed at some length in the T5.1 workshop. The recommendation of eDNAqua-Plan would be to adopt a more rigorous approach.

³⁴ see <https://www.gbif.org/the-gbif-network>

³⁵ see https://www.gbif.org/dna#_key-dna-related-partners

³⁶ see <https://obis.org/about/nodes/>

³⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/16367374>

³⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/18833437>

(Meta)data providing and receiving between stakeholders

We created graphs showing the connections between the biodiversity stakeholders and their (meta)data providers and receivers, based on information available on the stakeholders websites. We have excluded individuals, research organisations, research programs, and universities in these diagrams. as almost all of the stakeholders work with these agents. “Partners” and “nodes” means official partners of the respective organisations. Note that we have slightly modified the input from the spreadsheet for these diagrams in order to make them easier to read and to complete some connections (e.g. adding specifically GBIF France and Sweden rather than including them as “nodes”, as they are specifically connected to by other stakeholders). The graphs can be found in Appendix [A3](#).

These figures show that GBIF and OBIS have many (meta)data providers, being their various nodes, official partners/publishers; and that they also provide to many others. A small number of other stakeholders figure notably (e.g. GFBio, DASSH as (meta)data receivers). Many of the other stakeholders also have designated partners. There are several stakeholders that seem less well connected, however this may be due to how this information was collected; it is also the case that there is less connectivity in the freshwater domain.

Only a few stakeholders are linked to industry, national/government/EU agents. This is possibly partly due to a lack of sufficient information arising from the investigation (for example, we became aware via news articles of some new GBIF activities in this domain). WISE (Water Information System for Europe) Marine and Freshwater do not appear to be connected to OBIS or GBIF. WISE appears to be mainly for reports: it would be interesting to know whether those are based on, or feed into, data in OBIS.

We can see some genomics stakeholders as providers (MGnify, ENA): these will be addressed more fully in Sec.[3](#).

In summary, these graphs of connections could be extremely useful for understanding the ecosystem, however a more focussed and deeper analysis (requiring interviews with all stakeholders) would be necessary to complete the graphs and interpret them fully. For example, a specific investigation of the connection between academic and monitoring/mandated stakeholders would be interesting.

What kind of data can be linked to from within (meta)data

The types of external data that can be linked to from within data or metadata by our 27 stakeholders discussed here. This is where there is accommodation for including links to external (meta)data held elsewhere, rather than what types of data is covered by the stakeholder. Excluded are links to taxonomic names, as this was assessed previously. The figures (and a link to online versions) are provided in Appendix [A3](#).

Statistics on the types and formats of external data that can be linked are shown in Figs 7 and 8. Around a third of the stakeholders recommend/require links made to external sequence data (i.e. to actual sequences) and sequence metadata (i.e. information about the sequencing provenance, for example the fields in the [MIXS checklists](#)³⁹) in the data they receive: the DwC-DNA extension used by GBIF, its nodes such as FINBIF, and (Eur)OBIS includes many MIXS fields, which account for the metadata, and recommends that links to the accession number of sequences archived in ENA (and similar) are given; other

³⁹ <https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/>

stakeholders also follow this approach (PANGAEA, PlutoF, SDBI, SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal, BCO-DMO, and GFBio). Fewer do this for metadata, however given how many such unique links (e.g. unique accession numbers) could be found in a dataset, this is understandable.

About a third of the stakeholders also accept whatever the data submitter provides in their data and metadata, and do not make any recommendations regarding this information.

Sample metadata, usually in the form of BioSample accession numbers, are not frequently, and often not adequately provided in data and metadata. Samples (and their metadata) are the provenance of sequence data (as sequences are derived from samples), while the eDNA sequences (and their metadata) are the provenance of biodiversity data (as occurrences are derived from sequences). Samples and their metadata are the foundation of everything that follows, and so should always be accessible and complete. Therefore, if the link to the sequence exists, then the access to the sample metadata can be achieved through the sequence, though a direct reference to sample metadata among the biodiversity stakeholders would improve linking.

Figure 7 Upper: the types of external data that can be linked to from within the data. Lower: the types of external data that can be linked to from the metadata

Figure 8 The formats of the links to external data in metadata (red) and data (blue). The zero for the red bars is where they rise from the blue bars.

The form that these links take in the metadata and data are largely PIDs, a smaller number being URIs, and the rest being whatever the data provider used or just a string. As stated

previously, URIs should be enforced to allow the highest degree of interoperability, but the fact that PIDs are largely used is a good starting point for improvements.

In summary, a reasonably wide use of PIDs to link to other data within the (meta)data of the 27 stakeholders is found, but wider use of URIs is to be encouraged. About a third of the stakeholders allow/expect references to sequence (meta)data within their own datasets; where omics data are the source of bioinformatics results, this information should always be mandatory and the source data should (as much as possible) be open access. We note, however, that as DNA-based data in biodiversity archives is still a relatively new area, it is possible that some of our investigated stakeholders are still working on incorporating DNA data in their (meta)data models.

2.1.3 eDNA-relevant fields in the data held by biodiversity data infrastructures

Where (e)DNA-based occurrences (some kind of taxonomic identification) are published in biodiversity repositories, information about the (e)DNA workflow and data should be included. First and foremost, the immediate evidence of the occurrence is necessary, i.e. the DNA sequence of that occurrence together with all necessary provenance of that sequence and the taxonomic identification made therefrom.

For example, for the case of species names derived from metabarcoding data extracted from field samples, the following should ideally happen:

→ The biodiversity data (usually a spreadsheet), and specifically each reported occurrence therein, contains the links to the open, online-accessible ASV/OTU from which each occurrence was derived. In this scenario, these ASV/OTU data are published in a repository specific to that type of data.

→ The taxonomic information derived from each ASV/OTU should also be included in the biodiversity data file, i.e. the taxon name and rank, taxon ID (as a URI), and qualifying information (e.g. quality flags, number of reads, reliability information, confidence levels, etc.). This should be accompanied by provenance metadata describing how (what software) and with what inputs (software settings, reference libraries, etc) that information was obtained.

→ In the repository where the ASV/OTUs are published, these data should also be accompanied by provenance metadata describing the workflow and its inputs (software and its settings) used to obtain those ASV/OTUs, and including links to the open, online-accessible raw sequence data that are the source data of that work. In this scenario, the raw sequences are published in a repository specific to that type of data (which may or may not be the same repository holding the ASV/OTUs).

→ *However*, if the ASV/OTUs are *not* published elsewhere, then it will be necessary to include them within the biodiversity dataset instead, together with the provenance information. For example, OBIS highly recommends that the DNA sequence supporting each ASV/OTU is included within the DwC-A data package. This can be given in the field DNA_sequence within the DNA-derived extension, and linked to the Occurrence core with the occurrenceID⁴⁰.

→ In the repository where the raw sequences are published, these should be accompanied by provenance metadata describing how they were obtained (links to the sample metadata,

⁴⁰ https://manual.obis.org/dna_data.html#edna-and-dna-derived-data-example

processing protocols, molecular work, etc). The model used by ENA, for example, is that these data are linked to a sample/BioSample accession number, which in its turn accommodates the specialist information needed for sample data.

So each dataset points to its immediately preceding data and its provenance metadata, and each type of specialist data is published in a specialist repository: ideally ASVs/OTUs are published in their own specialist repositories with their own specialist metadata, rather than having to add that very specific metadata to the data model of the biodiversity archives. However, at the time (and still) that GBIF (and later OBIS) started to accept DNA-based occurrences, ASVs/OTUs and their metadata were not widely published, which may explain why so many MlxS terms were added to new fields in DwC to include in the DNA extension created by GBIF.

In this section we have looked at the categories of metadata that are accommodated in the biodiversity stakeholders investigated here, and which are relevant to eDNA-derived occurrences. We selected the 9 stakeholders that did provide data templates and did publish DNA-based data: OBIS (which covers also EurOBIS and/or EMODnet), GBIF, PANGAEA, PlutoF, SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal, DASSH-MEDIN, Atlas of Living Australia (ALA), Freshwater Biodiversity Data Portal, SDBI.

We categorised metadata into the following:

- Any information on sampling methods
- Any information on sample to sequence methods
- Any information on sequence to ASV/OTU methods
- Taxonomy information
- Raw sequence information
- ASV/OTU data
- Various/any MlxS and FAIRe-type fields
- Location information (latitude, longitude)
- Dates
- Depth
- Original sample IDs
- Specimen information
- Environmental information

We looked for: is this included in their (meta)data; how is it included (example field names); is this mandatory, recommended, or optional; are there any requirements regarding formatting of the data? The collected data are provided as a downloadable that is available from the [Zenodo record](https://zenodo.org/records/18890220)⁴¹ of this deliverable.

We found that:

- All stakeholders included sampling date (ISO format), decimal latitude and longitude, depth (or negative elevation) and (where relevant to the template) taxonomic metadata (e.g. names, IDs). For most these fields are mandatory or strongly recommended.
- A big proportion use the DNA extension of DwC – GBIF, OBIS and three others because they all exported their data to GBIF (SDBI, ALA, and SCAR).
- Other than those using the DwC vocabulary, there is a diversity in the naming of the terms meaning the same thing: this is not surprising, given that each stakeholder

⁴¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/18890220>

creates their own databases and templates, but is apparently a source of confusion for users (see the [Task 5.1 Blueprint workshop](#)⁴²).

- Where metadata on the genomics part of the work are specifically included, they are strongly recommended – following GBIF’s and OBIS’s use of the DwC DNA extension.
- Few specifically cater for fields that can be used to convey information about stored replicated or source samples within their templates.

A few notes on what we did/did not include in this analysis:

- PANGAEA reports that they are working on creating templates for DNA-based data, so we looked at their biology templates and added what information they provided on their wiki about molecular data.
- DASSH-MEDIN also does not have (e)DNA-focussed templates, so we used the biodiversity one.
- GFBio referred to PANGAEA and ENA for templates, so we did not include this stakeholder in our analysis.
- To obtain templates for some stakeholders, we would have had to register and/or download an app: iNaturalist, Dandjoo, FINBIF. Therefore we did not include them in our analysis. PlutoF also requires registration, but we happened to already have that and so could analyse their templates.
- Freshwater Biodiversity Data Portal kept timing out when we tried to access the necessary information.

In summary, given the proportion of investigated stakeholders that share data with GBIF and so use their standard (DwC) and their requirements (mandatory etc), we suggest that any work on improving eDNA metadata in biodiversity archives should probably concentrate on this.

2.2 Web services

Web services are an important part of the digital ecosystem, providing programmatic access to machines, developers, and humans, to the (meta)data held by the stakeholders. These can be in the form of user interfaces offering map-based data searches and data exploration and sub-selection, or machine-focussed interfaces offering access to defined components of the data, search and download, or providing automated feeds of the data for machine-consumption. The machine-focussed services are especially important to allow automated, repeatable, efficient sharing of (meta)data between stakeholders, and with providers and users. In an era of big data – sequence data can produce 100s of pieces of information and large and numerous datasets – the more hands-off the data findability and accessibility is, the smoother and faster the ecosystem can operate.

These days, increasing use is made of machine2machine (m2m) services to allow information to be shared. Full m2m services require no human interaction; machine2developer (m2d) services are where a machine runs the service but a developer has to understand how to run the service. We looked at the m2m and m2d, and a few human-only, web services of a subset of the stakeholders, focussing on those who were the most representative of their domains according to our analysis in the previous sections. See Appendix [A4](#) for the list of stakeholders, their endpoints investigated, and the information

⁴² <https://zenodo.org/records/18833437>

gathered. Note that this list also includes genomics and taxonomic stakeholders, for which the analysis is in Sec. [3.3](#).

We investigated the following questions:

- What type of service was provided
- What range of information was provided through those services
- Format of returned data
- Interoperability level for the machine-focused (m2m or m2d) services (i.e. excluding those solely for humans)

The “interoperability level” was assessed via a schema we created. Full details are in Appendix [A4](#), and a summary given in Table 4. Some examples of the range of levels different types of services can reach is given in Table 5, to provide a general guideline for subsequent interpretation.

Table 4 Interoperability level criteria

Level	Description
Level 1	Basic Technical Interoperability. The endpoint is technically consumable by multiple clients, but fragile
Level 2	Standardised API Interoperability. Independent clients can interoperate reliably
Level 3	Documented & Discoverable. New consumers can onboard without direct support
Level 4	Cross-client Interoperability. Browsers, scripts, services, and workflows interoperate equally
Level 5	Ecosystem Integration. Interoperability extends into real-world workflows
Level 6	Semantic Interoperability. Different systems understand the same data the same way
Level 7	Operational Interoperability. Interoperability is sustained over time, not accidental

Table 5 Typical interoperability levels reached by different types of services

Technology / Service	Typical Level	Why
OpenAPI REST API	3-5	Excellent documentation & developer experience; semantics vary
ElasticSearch	4-5	Strong technical + operational maturity
OAI-PMH	2-6	Simple protocol; semantics depend on metadata

Technology / Service	Typical Level	Why
WSDL SOAP	2-3	Strong contracts; weaker discoverability
OGS Services	4-7	Built-in semantics + standards alignment

The biodiversity stakeholders investigated were: OBIS, GBIF, PANGAEA, DASSH-MEDIN, and HELCOM Biodiversity Database.

A summary of our findings for the biodiversity stakeholders:

- OBIS
 - Service architecture⁴³; and contract⁴⁴/standards: RESTful ;Open API, and human-only
 - Type of (meta)data provided: occurrence, taxon, specified checklists, dataset, node and institute, area, country, facet (filtering categories), statistics
 - Format of returned results: JSON
 - Average interoperability level: 3
- EurOBIS
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: OGC, RESTful, SOAP;OGC, ISO 19115
 - Type of (meta)data provided: occurrence records, metadata, maps/layers
 - Format of returned results: XML, JSON, GML, GeoTIFF, image
 - Average interoperability level: 4
- GBIF
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful, OpenAPI
 - Type of (meta)data provided: anything in the GBIF Registry, including all registered datasets, installations, organisations, nodes, and networks discoverable, taxon name with related information, occurrences and related information, images associated with a single occurrence, pre-calculated and ad-hoc occurrence map tiles, vocabularies, literature (indexed by GBIF), validation report/results + errors/issues
 - Format of returned results: JSON
 - Average interoperability level: 3
- PANGAEA
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; ElasticSearch, OAH-PMH, WSDL, OGC, plain download, and human-only
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Dataset metadata records, search result collections, detailed individual dataset records, indexed PANGAEA metadata and data descriptors, parameters and related metadata, georeferenced datasets and publications, submission and curation services, data entities such as user, organization, samplegroup, sample, sample analysis result, layers, map requests, features / raster cells, metadata describing layer coverage, resolution and coordinate system
 - Format of returned results: PNG, JPEG, GIF, JSON, XML, tabular text

⁴³ Web service architecture describes how to instantiate the elements of the service and implement the operations in an interoperable manner

⁴⁴ Contract: a formal, machine-readable agreement defining how a service consumer and provider interact

- Average interoperability level: 2, some 1 and 3
- DASSH-MEDIN
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: – ; OGC, ISO 19115/19138, GEMINI, INSPIRE
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Metadata records (catalogue entries; descriptive metadata about marine datasets, not the data itself), search result collections, detailed metadata objects, auxiliary catalogue information
 - Format of returned results: XML, JSON, HTML
 - Average interoperability level: 3
- HELCOM
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI, GeoNetwork
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Resources on the browser interface are geospatial datasets and services, metadata records, search result list/record summaries, record details, supporting objects/system information (metadata about spatial and environmental resources catalogued in the HELCOM Metadata Catalogue
 - Format of returned results: HTML, JSON
 - Average interoperability level: 3

In summary, the investigated stakeholders have quite comprehensive web services, offering access to much of their (meta)data. However, the interoperability of these services is fairly low – most are 3 or lower, meaning that the services are “Documented & Discoverable”, i.e. new consumers can onboard without direct support. In other words, the services are aimed at developers, rather than machines, and are not interoperable with services, or the outputs of services, from other stakeholders (even those of the same type). This means that the web-services part of the digital ecosystem still needs a lot of work (ideally this requires Level 6, Semantic interoperability)

3. Biodiversity, genomics, and taxonomic stakeholders

We expanded our analysis of the biodiversity stakeholders in Sec. 2 to include other stakeholders in the wider eDNA digital ecosystem: DNA (genomics) infrastructures, reference libraries, providers of bioinformatics services, genomics biodiversity data infrastructures, and taxonomic systems. The organisations included here are: NCBI GenBank, EMBL-EBI ENA, BOLD, UNITE, NCBI BioProject, NCBI BioSample, EBI BioSample, SDBI (which is also included in the biodiversity category analysed in Sec. 2), MGnify, Earth Biogenome Project, GGBN, ERGA, Darwin Tree of Life, Genome Taxonomy Database, CoL, GOAT, iBOL. In this section we repeat the analyses of Sec. 2 to cover these other stakeholders and to identify commonalities and differences.

3.1 Schemas, standards, and taxonomy in (meta)data

3.1.1 Vocabularies, schemas, standards for (meta)data formats

First we looked at the (meta)data standards used, and the formats data were exported (provided to users) in. (The N/A entries are excluded from this analysis.)

The most common data standards used are FASTA and FASTQ, being the standard employed for raw and processed sequences, the most common standards for metadata are GSC MIxS and TDWG DwC, both being vocabularies (Fig. 9). There is a long tail of less used formats, many of which are specific to different types of genomics results. CSV and XLSX are common: a move away from XLSX and to CSV should be encouraged, for reasons of interoperability and open data formats.

The most common metadata export formats are CSV/TSV, JSON, TXT (text), and XML (Fig. 10). A move to JSON-LD from all of these would be appropriate for metadata and it should be encouraged for reasons of interoperability. The most common data export format is FASTA (weighted by the number of stakeholders in this group who work with bioinformatics outputs such as these), with a long tail to other specialised formats. FASTA is a text-based format, while CRAM and BAM (two other popular formats) are binary: much genomics data is large and binary formats are necessary. The use of DwC outside of the biodiversity domain is less than the use of MIxS in the biodiversity domain; however this is understandable as the parts of DwC that apply to genomics are generally limited to sample information, which is largely covered by BioSamples. BioSamples lists the preferred vocabularies within their defined fields (typically as defined by MIxS); but we note that the INSDC are not particularly strict about in practice actually controlling the vocabulary beyond a core of fields (e.g. URIs over strings), and this affects interoperability of the metadata submitted to them. BioProjects is a multi-hierarchical organisational object layer on top of BioSamples, with however little control of metadata in it. We have classified BioSample and BioProject as providers of only metadata, that is all the information *is* the metadata. These metadata are then linked to sequences that are uploaded to INSDC (NCBI, ENA, DDBJ), hence becoming the metadata for those data. BioSamples are heavily integrated into the sequence databases of ENA and NCBI, being effectively part of their metadata, and, hence, are linked with the various checklists (such as the MIxS ones) they use. A mapping of BioSamples/MIxS terms to other vocabularies should be a relatively easy task, and would improve the interoperability of the (meta)data between the biodiversity and genomics domains. Note that MIxS is included in DwC via the DNA extension (see eDNAqua-Plan's D3.2 for more information on their mapping to each other).

Figure 9 Data (bottom) and metadata (top) standards used

Figure 10 Data (bottom) and metadata (top) export formats used

In summary, many vocabularies are in use among these stakeholders. We suggest that a cross-walk analysis of these vocabularies would help to identify their function in the eDNA digital ecosystem, with respect to each other and to the data they are used to describe. There are also many different data standards in use: that such standards exist is good news, and a check on their interoperability should be made (i.e. not just that they are the same format, but that the data within them are formatted in the same way).

3.1.2 The MixS vocabulary

The main metadata vocabulary that incorporates terms that are relevant to (e)DNA data are the MixS checklists. MixS is maintained by the Genomics Standards Consortium (GSC⁴⁵). It is used by INSDC among many others, and as mentioned in Sec. 2.1.1, it is mapped into the DNA extension of DwC. An eDNA-specific checklist called [MIEM](#)⁴⁶ was proposed in 2024, and the [FAIR eDNA project](#)⁴⁷ is also working towards integrating the FAIRe checklist into the GSC suite⁴⁸.

MixS reaches a high degree of interoperability: MixS terms are defined with URIs, which are maintained on <https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/>. The terms follow a well-defined structure (<https://genomicsstandardsconsortium.github.io/mixs/{term-code}/>). The vocabulary is described using the linkML⁴⁹ specification, the schema/model is formally/explicitly defined (in YAML), and the documentation mentions “generators for compiling LinkML schemas to other frameworks (converting to JSON-LD would be our recommendation).

Its strengths:

- Persistent, resolvable URIs
- LinkML as master model
- Machine-readable serialisation “out of the box”
- Many MixS terms link to other external ontologies (e.g. ENVO⁵⁰), and there is an explicit effort⁵¹ to align with other biodiversity standards

Potential improvements:

- More explicit RDF/Linked Data interfaces: make the linked data (e.g. JSON-LD, OWL-RDF, ...) output more visible.
- Publish as SKOS⁵² concept schemes: as a lightweight W3C⁵³ standard explicitly intended for controlled vocabularies. Publishing MixS using the SKOS specification would make it easier for tools such as semantic search engines and federated catalogues to discover and interoperate.
- Clearly document cross-standard mapping (using e.g. SSSOM⁵⁴): this will help in understanding terms equivalence.
- Strengthen the metadata about the vocabulary itself (contributors, versioning, domain usage, provenance) using standards such as DCterms⁵⁵, SKOS, VoID⁵⁶.
- More human friendly access / lookup tooling: a browsable vocabulary portal (such as LOV⁵⁷ (Linked Open Vocabularies), BioPortal⁵⁸, prefix.cc⁵⁹ style lookup) with term metadata, hierarchies, and usage examples would increase discoverability and reuse.

⁴⁵ <https://www.gensc.org/>

⁴⁶ <https://mbmq.pensoft.net/article/128689/>

⁴⁷ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

⁴⁸ See <https://fair-edna.github.io/next.html> and <https://mnhn.hal.science/mnhn-05219221v1>

⁴⁹ <https://linkml.io/>: is a language for modeling linked data

⁵⁰ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/envo>

⁵¹ <https://www.tdwg.org/community/gbwg/mixs/>

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simple_Knowledge_Organization_System

⁵³ <https://www.w3.org/>

⁵⁴ <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.w3.org/TR/void/>

⁵⁷ <https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

⁵⁸ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/>

⁵⁹ <http://prefix.cc/>

3.1.3 Taxonomies

We next looked at which taxonomic systems that are used by these stakeholders, and their formats (Figs 11 and 12). Clearly, genomics-based taxonomic systems are more heavily used in the genomics domain, and so it is no surprise that the NCBI taxonomy is the most popular one used in data and metadata for these stakeholders. A brief explanation of the NCBI taxonomy, as well as some of the others shown in Fig. 11, can be found in Sec. [2.1.1](#).

For those stakeholders with “in-house” systems, this term refers to those that incorporate multiple other systems.

Figure 11 Taxonomic systems used in data (blue) and metadata (red). Zero-point for the red bars is where they rise from the blue bars.

Figure 12 Formats for the taxonomic names in data (blue) and metadata (red). Zero-point for the red bars is where they rise from the blue bars.

In Table 6 we show the statistics on the conditions set on using taxonomic IDs and names in (meta)data, excluding the N/A values. The great majority require both, which is encouraging and an improvement on the same statistics for biodiversity stakeholders. The formats in which the IDs are given are shown in Table 7. PIDs are the most popular format (they are semi-interoperable and user-friendly) in metadata, but strings or integers (i.e. just the unique part of the ID) are also common and this is unfortunate, being extremely non-interoperable.

Table 6 Statistics on conditions set for taxonomic information

Condition on taxonomic ID	No. used in data	No. used in metadata	Condition on taxonomic name	No. used in data	No. used in metadata
Mandatory	7	12	Mandatory	11	20
None	3	6	None	0	0
Unknown	2	3	Unknown	1	1

Table 7 Statistics on the formats that taxon IDs are provided in

Taxonomic ID format	Data	Metadata
URI	5	6
PID	4	10
integer/string	5	10

Taxonomic ID format	Data	Metadata
none	0	1

In summary, there are many taxonomic naming systems in use, with NCBI dominating among the investigated stakeholders. NCBI does have a mapping to other systems (e.g. its taxmapper⁶⁰ function), but we could find little information about how this is done. Mapping systems to each other is important for human understandability and machine interoperability, and should be sustained (hence probably automated), documented, and exposed in machine-interoperable ways. Greater use of URIs over PIDs or strings to refer to taxon IDs should be made.

3.1.4 Linking to external data

Finally, we looked at the types of external data (excluding taxonomic, which was covered previously) to which links could be made in the (meta)data of these investigated stakeholders, excluding the N/A values. This is shown in Fig. 13. There are many different types of genomics data to which links are made within the data; for metadata the most common links are made to sequence data (e.g. accession numbers in ENA), sequence metadata (e.g. BioSamples), and whatever the data submitter provided. This is the same picture as found for the biodiversity stakeholders. The most common format of these links are PIDs (12 and 10 for data and metadata), with URIs being a distant second in data (2) but encouragingly common in metadata (7).

In summary, greater use should be made of using URIs to link to external data.

⁶⁰ <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC8320524/>

Figure 13 Type of external data that can be linked to within the data (blue) and metadata (red) of the stakeholders. Zero-point for the red bars is where they rise from the blue bars.

3.2 Connections between all stakeholders

To investigate the degree of linking in the eDNA digital ecosystem, we looked at all the investigated stakeholders to see: organisations that receive (meta)data from our stakeholders, and organisations that our stakeholders receive (meta)data from, and we also looked at which organisations were specifically linked to from within the (meta)data of our stakeholders following the stakeholders' own recommendations to their data submitters. We grouped all the organisations found from this analysis into the following:

- Biodiversity data infrastructures, from omics and non-omics sources
- Biodiversity data infrastructures, from omics sources only
- Genomics data infrastructures, providers of bioinformatics services (including BioSample, for which we have combined that from NCBI and EBI)
- Reference libraries
- Taxonomic systems
- Other, that are linked to government, EU, monitoring, or international organisations
- Other (journals, generalist repositories, etc)
- Collection, biobanks

The list of organisations against their classification can be found in Appendix [A3](#). Some organisations can be classified into more than one type: for example, BOLD is used both as

a reference library and to do bioinformatics, or Darwin Tree of Life provides sequences that can be used as references and also aims to classify life from sequences. In these cases we grouped the stakeholders according to what we believed was their primary purpose. As before, we add the proviso that this information is based on what we could find on the various websites and within their data, and is probably not complete.

The figures showing the relationship graphs between all stakeholders and the organisations that provide (meta)data to and get (meta)data from the stakeholders can be found in Appendix [A3](#). Regarding the receivers of (meta)data from our stakeholders – that means where (meta)data held by stakeholders are used by others in their data/analysis workflows, to add to their own metadata or to serve as references in their own (meta)data – we find that a lot of sharing happens. ENA, Eur(OBIS), and GBIF are the main, centrally-placed nodes but many others also have many connections (PANGAEA, GFBio, PlutoF and HELCOM, to name a few). This is encouraging. Most stakeholders share with others of their own type, which is natural; and we also find that there are numerous connections between the omics-only and other biodiversity organisations, genomics organisations and reference libraries. There are some, but not many, connections from stakeholders to governmental/European organisations, although whether this is because those connections do not exist, or are not reported on their websites, is unclear. There appears to be more metadata sharing than data sharing, which is acceptable: where metadata include references to data, there is not necessarily a need to copy over the data. In addition, BioSample, which is a significant node, is a metadata-only stakeholder.

Regarding the data providers, the conclusions are much the same as for the data receivers. One difference is that Zenodo is a node, but not one that is connected to the eDNA specialised data. Zenodo is particularly good for publishing software, e.g. because of its connection to GitHub⁶¹ and automatically granting DOIs, although adoption of more software-focussed metadata standards would be recommended. It is possible that non-academic institutions could be more likely to publish their data on Zenodo (where you can upload anything) rather than the specialised genomics or biodiversity archives (which have stricter requirements): if Zenodo could take on-board more focussed metadata for these domains, that would help make those data more findable (for example, as they currently do for data released from [biodiversity literature](#)⁶²). The specialist archives still ought to be the go to repositories for appropriate (meta)data.

Regarding the organisations that are mentioned in the (meta)data of our stakeholders: here we can see that those stakeholders that are significant nodes in the other plots stand out here as well. Clearly, these are the most popular data infrastructures to use and to link to. (We add the proviso that in our investigation we were biased to picking out mention of the stakeholders that figured in our list.)

In summary, these graphs (Appendix [A3](#)) of connections could be extremely useful for understanding the ecosystem, however a more focussed and deeper analysis (requiring interviews with all stakeholders) would be necessary to complete the graphs and interpret them fully, since it is very possible that not all the information is provided on the websites of the stakeholders: additionally, *how* a connection is made is as interesting as who are connected. A specific investigation of the connection between academic and monitoring/mandated stakeholders would be interesting. We suggest that it would be useful for Zenodo to add more specific metadata fields for specific types of digital objects

⁶¹ <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/github/>

⁶² <https://zenodo.org/communities/biosyslit/>

(software/workflows, biodiversity, genomics), possibly in collaboration with CodeMeta⁶³[2] (software) and/or ODIS (software and data).

3.3 Web services

The investigation into the web services of the biodiversity stakeholders in Sec. 2.2 was extended to include genomics data stakeholders (ENA, NCBI GenBank, BOLD, BioSamples, MGnify) and stakeholders providing taxonomic data (ENA, NCBI GenBank, WoRMS, Catalogue of Life, Open Tree of Life, PR2 and UNITE). Please see that section for guidance on the information collected. See Appendix A4 for the list of stakeholders, their endpoints investigated, and the information gathered.

We investigated the following questions:

- What type of service was provided
- What range of information was provided through those services
- Format of returned data
- Interoperability level for the machine-focused (m2m or m2d) services (i.e. excluding those solely for humans)

A summary of our findings for the genomics stakeholders:

- ENA
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI, web standards (HTTPS, HTML, Javascript)
 - Type of (meta)data provided: sequences, records/accessions, files/datasets, studies/projects, samples, run/experiments, taxonomy/organisms, sequence records/accessions, job dispatch information
 - Format of returned results: FASTA/Q, XML, EMBLflatfile, JSON, TSV, CSV
 - Interoperability level: 3
- NCBI GenBank including BioSamples (NCBI)
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI
 - Type of (meta)data provided: all NCBI data, including services PubMed, PMC, Taxonomy, SNP, Structure, SRA, Gene, Nucleotide, Protein, PubChem, etc. Various kinds of information (metadata, annotation reports, stats, ...) relating to genomes, genes, virus, taxonomy, BioSamples and Organelle Genome Resources
 - Format of returned results: XML, TXT, JSON
 - Interoperability level: 2 and 5
- BOLD
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI
 - Type of (meta)data provided: various data such as query records, terms, documents and ancillary documents, maps, stats, counts, images, taxonomies, QR code
 - Format of returned results: DwC, TSV, JSON
 - Interoperability level: 3
- BioSamples (ENA)
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI, HAL⁶⁴, JSON-LD

⁶³ <https://codemeta.github.io/>

⁶⁴ Hypertext Application Language

- Type of (meta)data provided: Sample metadata, cross-refs, project data
- Format of returned results: JSON, JSON-LD, XML
- Interoperability level: 4
- MGNify
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI
 - Type of (meta)data provided: microbiome studies, analyses, genomes, metadata
 - Format of returned results: JSON
 - Interoperability level: 3

A summary of our findings for the taxonomy stakeholders:

- GBIF
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Taxonomy, names, occurrence data, cross-refs
 - Format of returned results: JSON, DwC, CSV
 - Interoperability level: 4
- NCBI GenBank
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: REST-like; E-utilities
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Taxonomy records; lineage; sequence links; metadata; cross-references
 - Format of returned results: XML, JSON, ASN.1, TXT
 - Interoperability level: 2
- WoRMS
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI, WSDL, LDES
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Taxon-names, IDs, cross-references, synonyms, and checklist, geographical, presence etc information
 - Format of returned results: JSON, XML, RDF/Turtle
 - Interoperability level: 2, 4, 6
- Catalogue of Life
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; OpenAPI, ChecklistBank-specific
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Taxonomy, checklists, names, synonyms, datasets, cross-references, Checklist datasets, metadata, references
 - Format of returned results: CoLDP, JSON, CSV, TSV
 - Interoperability level: 2,3
- Open Tree of Life
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; documented JSON API
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Synthetic tree, taxonomy, studies, mappings, metadata
 - Format of returned results: JSON, phyloXML
 - Interoperability level: 2,4
- PR2
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: R-code
 - Type of (meta)data provided: 18S rRNA sequences, taxonomy, primers, metadata
 - Format of returned results: FASTA. CSV R dataframe
 - Interoperability level: 1

- UNITE
 - Service architecture; and contract/standards: RESTful; INSDC standards
 - Type of (meta)data provided: Fungal ITS sequences, species hypotheses, PIDs, metadata
 - Format of returned results: JSON, CSV, HTML
 - Interoperability level: 3

In summary, the level of interoperability for the genomics stakeholders hovers around the 3 (Documented & Discoverable) - 4 (Cross-client Interoperability) level and for the taxonomic stakeholders at the 2 (Standardised API Interoperability) - 4 level (See Table 3 for the interoperability level definitions); this is very slightly better than for the biodiversity stakeholders and hence the same conclusions hold here: most of the services are not interoperable with services and their outputs from other stakeholders. This means that the web-services part of the digital ecosystem still needs a lot of work (ideally this requires Level 6, Semantic interoperability).

NCBI's recent addition of a modern, OpenAPI-described REST API offers standardised, machine-actionable access to NCBI genome-centric datasets. This is a significant improvement in interoperability to its previous (still-existing) Entrez server-side programming, moving its interoperability level from 2 to 5. Only one service has reached level 6, and that is the LDES feed from WoRMS, being a machine-readable and -understandable update feed for tracking new or modified WoRMS records. This standard is what the Blueprint of D5.1 should be aiming for.

3.5 Use-case investigation

Two uses-cases specifically focussing on data published in biodiversity archives, and tracing those back along the data chain to the source data, were carried out. We started with data published in GBIF and OBIS, and the focus was on how a human (rather than a machine) could find

- the originating DNA data
- information on the samples processed into DNA
- the bioinformatics codes used
- the reference libraries used
- provenance metadata on the sampling, processing, and all analysis steps

The GBIF data are metabarcoding of macrobenthos and fish from ILVO. The OBIS data are a metabarcoding dataset of the hard-bottom communities published by the ARMS-MBON project. In both cases, the sequence data were published in INSDC repositories (ENA and NCBI)

The full results are given in Appendix [A5](#). **In summary** we found that

- Tracing the data from stage to stage was possible for both, using the links and information provided in the respective metadata, however it did require patience and persistence since a lot of clicking and reading was necessary, and some general internet searches were also required. *If all metadata from repositories were exposed as standardised LOD, it would be possible to create a knowledge graph that would find these links, avoiding the need to do that manually.*

- Links to related data and publications are extremely useful for the scientist navigating the data space they are interested in. Such links are given patchily. While it is difficult to get data providers to include such information (especially a-posteriori). Automated processes could be employed here, i.e. harvesting the information over the web, however that will only be possible if all data infrastructures make that type of information available to be found and understood, and if standards for that type of information are agreed on. *This breaks provenance and is user-unfriendly.*
- The ARMS-MBON data were harvested into GBIF, but no link to the originating OBIS record could be found from its metadata page (one had to navigate to the IPT). *This creates a break in the provenance.*
- The IPT used by GBIF and OBIS does not include links to related publications and data, even though that is provided on the originating metadata record for the ARMS-MBON dataset. *This is user-unfriendly and breaks reusability.*
- OBIS metadata did not include a licence (although it was provided on its IPT link). *Even if by default all data in a repository are open access, a licence must be given in all metadata records.*
- Both datasets were complicated enough that data was also provided on GitHub repositories. *In these cases, we recommend a data paper should always be written to allow others (especially those less familiar with GitHub) to understand how to navigate the dataset. A template for such a data paper could be a useful asset to be provided by the eDNA community.*

3.6 Summary of the digital ecosystem, from field to genomics to biodiversity observational linkable data

Here we summarise the results of our analysis of the digital ecosystem covering biodiversity (omics-only and omics-also) and genomics data infrastructures (including those providing bioinformatics services), reference libraries, and taxonomic systems.

In biodiversity data, we find that:

- Links to the raw sequence data are usually provided in the form of PID (an accession number from an INSDC repository). BioSample links, as a PID, are also often used. For both, use of URIs should be preferred, for greater interoperability.
- The ASV/OTU sequence are often included within the data, usually with a limited amount of descriptive and provenance metadata: however, the amount of provenance provided is not sufficient to really provide trustability, traceability and reusability. While it would be preferable that ASVs and OTUs were published in specific repositories together with their specialist metadata, rather than being included within the biodiversity data, the *de facto* model is the other way around. Improvements are being made to the metadata necessary to describe genomics data, such as improving the DwC DNA extension (see timeline on the FAIR eDNA “[next steps](#)⁶⁵”) and also by ENA allowing ASV/OTU tables to be uploaded and associated with samples and sequences.
- GBIF, INSDC (e.g. ENA), and to a slightly lesser degree OBIS, are significant influencers in the publishing of biodiversity data, and especially that based on genomics. The DNA extension is a blessing, and the GBIF/OBIS “publish once, share

⁶⁵ <https://fair-edna.github.io/next.html>

many times” approach is of great benefit to the biodiversity data ecosystem. Unfortunately, as long as their data models are relaxed on the requirements for mandatory fields, and on the requirements for using URIs over PIDs and PIDs over strings, improvements to the interoperability and reusability of these data will be limited.

Over the entire digital ecosystem, we find that:

- Greater use of URIs when referring to taxonomic names should also be encouraged, to provide better traceability for this information.
- Backward links (linking current data to its immediately preceding data) are often provided, although greater use of URIs should be encouraged. Links to other related data or publications, for example “forward” links from a sequence to the published biodiversity results, are extremely rare, and often not specifically requested in the metadata of the data infrastructures. While this does not break the provenance chain, it does contribute to a less smooth digital ecosystem, as it makes it harder for data users to find the full context and scope of any data. As it is difficult enough to get any metadata from data providers, let alone all the forward and sideways links (often arising *a posteriori*), we suggest that automation would help, although this requires that the necessary information are exposed by all stakeholders (including journals, data repositories, brokers, etc.) in machine-findable and -interoperable ways.
- MlxS is a common vocabulary, both via its use by the INSDC and its incorporation in the DwC DNA extension, between biodiversity and genomics players. Not all biodiversity stakeholders can adopt the DwC standard, although they can adopt the DwC vocabulary for their biodiversity data, and this should be borne in mind e.g. by the FAIR eDNA project and their FAIRe checklist, as well as T5.1 and its Roadmap.
- Sharing of metadata and data is quite common within stakeholder types. and to a slightly lesser degree, between stakeholder types. This is encouraging. However, what is shared, with whom, how, why, and how often is poorly documented. We believe that better informing the data providers and users on these activities would encourage them in their publishing journey, and allow them to better understand and appreciate how the digital ecosystem works.
- Much of the dataset discovery and description metadata is shared via XML/JSON, which is encouraging as it is machine-readable. Greater use of LOD, e.g. using JSON-LD over JSON, would allow for greater semantic interoperability, and wider use of e.g. LDES feeds would allow for greater machine-findability/harvestability.
- Some specific recommendations on the MlxS and DwC vocabularies were made, see Sec. [2.1.1](#) and Sec. [3.1.2](#).
- Recommendations on how to improve web services were made, see Secs [2.2](#) and [3.3](#). For a fully smooth digital ecosystem, it is necessary that more web services focussed on machines, rather than developers, should be provided.
- There are many genomics data formats which are semi-standardised. Greater standardisation of the formatting of the data within those formats is to be encouraged.
- As many taxonomic systems are in use, more information about how they relate to each other, and if and how they are mapped to one another, should be provided. This will improve the traceability of taxonomic results.
- Templates for data submission are often, but by no means always, provided; and almost always require patience to find. This is user unfriendly, both for data users as for data providers. While creating templates does require resources on behalf of the

data repository, it can smooth the passage to receiving quality data. Data submitters may need encouragement to use the templates – especially those that require more interoperability and reusability than is common among scientists – and they do need to be as easy to fill in as possible. (This was a topic of discussion in the [Task 5.1 Blueprint workshop](#)⁶⁶).

- From our two tested use cases, we found that (1) BioSample metadata are too often not semantically-interoperable or accessible (e.g. protocols not given as a URL), (2) there is actually room to include quite a lot of metadata to provide plentiful provenance information in all the data repositories (GBIF, OBIS, ENA, NCBI, BioSample), however whether these fields are filled in, and whether those information are made accessible (being URIs over strings), is almost entirely up to the data submitter’s conscience.
- A deeper study of the connections between the various stakeholders in the eDNA digital ecosystem would be of benefit. It is clear that there are many connections made between the stakeholders we have looked at, at the data and metadata level, but the information to properly and completely map those connections is not easy to find and likely not fully provided. A more in-depth analysis was beyond the scope of this project, but would have allowed the Blueprint and Roadmap that will be produced by WP5 to be “personalised” to individual stakeholders and linkage pathways. This deeper analysis (with dedicated resources) is something that we would strongly recommend to produce more robust and meaningful graphs.

4. Biobanks and Culture collections; Taxonomies

In this second part of Task 3.3 we looked at biobanks and culture collections, and taxonomic backbones, and their role in eDNA research and the eDNA digital ecosystem.

4.1. The Role of Physical Repositories in the eDNA Ecosystem

In the context of the eDNAqua-Plan project and the development of the next generation of aquatic biodiversity monitoring, Biobanks and Culture Collections represent far more than mere repositories of biological material; they constitute the fundamental physical anchor of the digital data ecosystem. While other tasks within WP3 have focused on the standardisation of digital data resulting from sequencing (Task 3.2) and the curation of taxonomic reference libraries (Task 3.1), this section addresses the material origin of that information.

The central premise of this analysis is that the traceability, reproducibility, and reliability of eDNA data intrinsically depend on the ability to link sequencing data—raw and processed—back to its physical source and to its original metadata. Often, specific environmental or historical metadata attributes are not transmitted downstream into sequence repositories or publications because they are not deemed relevant for the initial study. Therefore, biobanks and culture collections serve a critical dual role: they are not merely custodians of the physical material but also the permanent archives of the comprehensive metadata, ensuring that these details remain preserved and accessible for subsequent research.

⁶⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/18833437>

In an ideal digital biodiversity ecosystem, an unbroken thread must exist connecting a species occurrence record in a global database (such as GBIF or OBIS) to the supporting DNA sequence (in ENA or NCBI) and ultimately to the physical sample preserved in an accessible collection. The connection should also comprise recordings of the sample and data processing. This connectivity ensures that molecular identifications can be validated and revisited as taxonomic frameworks evolve.

Therefore, the scope of this section focuses specifically on the interoperability and data linking capacities of these infrastructures of physical material. It does not aim to assess the physical quality of the samples or the legal frameworks of the collections per se (e.g., Nagoya Protocol compliance), except where these factors directly influence the metadata and the digital discoverability of the resources. The objective is to identify how these "offline" archives can be effectively integrated into the online eDNA data pipeline, ensuring that the physical biodiversity of Europe's waters is not just preserved but made Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) for the future of genomic research.

4.2. Landscape of Stakeholders (Biobanks & Culture Collections)

To assess the current status of the aquatic biobanking infrastructure in Europe and its readiness to integrate into the eDNAqua-Plan digital ecosystem, a technical questionnaire was distributed to curators and data managers within the project consortium and associated networks. This survey aimed to identify the technological maturity of these nodes and their specific workflows regarding metadata handling and connection to molecular data.

4.2.1. Survey Methodology and Participation Profile

The analysis presented in this chapter is supported by detailed technical responses from key institutions that represent a cross-section of the European biodiversity infrastructure. The participating nodes cover the spectrum from large national natural history museums to highly specialised culture collections, providing a comprehensive view of the current landscape.

Based on the questionnaire responses, the stakeholders (Table 8) can be categorised into three distinct functional profiles:

1. **Museum Biobanks:** Represented by institutions such as the Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change (LIB) in Germany and the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS) in Belgium.
 - These nodes prioritise long-term preservation of physical specimens (vouchers) and tissue samples for molecular validation. They typically manage vast historical collections alongside modern biobanking facilities.
2. **Culture Collections:** Represented by the Culture Collection of Algae & Protozoa (CCAP) in the UK and the Norwegian Culture Collection of Algae (NORCCA) managed by NIVA.
 - These act as Biological Resource Centres, maintaining living reference strains of marine and freshwater algae and protozoa. They are critical for providing the biological ground truth for taxonomic reference libraries of unicellular eukaryotes.
3. **Research Institutes & Marine Stations:** Such as the Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research (CIIMAR) in Portugal and the Marine Biological Association (MBA) in the UK.

- These institutions bridge the gap between active field sampling campaigns and long-term banking, often holding unique collections derived from specific research projects or long-term monitoring series (e.g., the Continuous Plankton Recorder)

A comprehensive analysis of these findings is detailed in the full report on the results of the questionnaire to biobanks and culture collections, which can be found on the eDNAqua-Plan Zenodo [repository](https://zenodo.org/records/18849564)⁶⁷.

Table 8 List of biobanks and culture collections invited to participate in the questionnaire. Institutions that participated in the questionnaire are highlighted in red.

n	Organisation name	Country
1	EMBRC Belgium	Belgium
2	CIM-UVigo	Spain
3	Banco Español de Algas	Spain
4	Biscay Bay Environmental Biospecimen Bank	Spain
5	UVigo/ECIMAT	Spain
6	EMBRC France Biological resources	France
7	EMBRC Greece	Greece
8	EMBRC Norway	Norway
9	DEEP biobank	Portugal
10	IIM-CSIC's Marine Biobank	Spain
11	Marine Biological Association (MBA)	UK
12	Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change (LIB)	Germany
13	Meise Botanic Garden	UK
14	Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa (CCAP)	UK
15	The Irish Marine Biomaterial Repository	Ireland
16	Spanish Culture Type Collection of Microorganisms	Spain
17	The Norwegian Culture Collection of Algae (NORCCA)	Norway
18	CCBA Culture Collection of Baltic Algae	Poland
19	National Marine Biodiscovery Laboratory in Ireland	Ireland
20	Portuguese Blue Biobank Consortium	Portugal
21	Spanish Institute of Oceanography (CRUST-IEOCD)	Spain
22	Hungarian Natural History Museum	hungary
23	Berlin Natural History Museum	Germany
24	National Museum of Natural History, Paris	France
25	Naturalis Biodiversity Center	Nederland
26	Natural History Museum of Denmark	Denmark
27	National Museum of Natural Sciences	Spain

⁶⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/18849564>

28	Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS)	Belgium
29	Meise Botanic Garden	Belgium
30	Instituut voor Landbouw, Visserij, and Voedingsonderzoek	Belgium
31	Collection "Biogeographie et Ecologie des Vertébrés"	France
32	Real Jardín Botánico - CSIC	Spain
33	Botanical Garden of the University of Valencia (UVEG)	Spain
34	ETH Zurich	Switzerland
35	BONN MUSEUM	Germany
36	EAZA Biobank	Netherlands
37	Interdisciplinary Centre of Marine and Environmental Research (CIIMAR)	Portugal
38	Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture (ILVO) - Marine DNA Collection	Belgium

4.2.2. Operational Heterogeneity and the Digital Divide

The survey results reveal a landscape characterised by a significant technological and operational divide. While all surveyed institutions share the goal of preserving biodiversity, their capacity to participate in a digital eDNA ecosystem varies drastically. This heterogeneity can be structured along three main axes:

A. Digital Maturity and Data Systems (Laboratory Information Management Systems, LIMS)
The "Digital Divide" is most visible in the management systems employed.

- Industrialised Biobanks: Large national nodes (e.g., RBINS, LIB) utilise advanced, often custom-built or enterprise-level LIMS such as DaRWIN⁶⁸ or Specify⁶⁹. These systems support persistent unique identifiers (PIDs), automated label printing, and hierarchical storage management, allowing for the systematic tracking of thousands of samples.
- Research & Culture Collections: Smaller, highly specialised nodes (e.g., NORCCA, research collections at CIIMAR) often rely on ad-hoc solutions, ranging from local SQL databases to simple spreadsheet registries. While scientifically rigorous, these systems frequently lack API connectivity, making the data "machine-inaccessible" to external users without human intervention.

B. "Living" vs. "Preserved" Metadata Complexity A crucial distinction identified is the complexity of metadata required by Culture Collections compared to standard Biobanks.

- Static Repositories (Biobanks): Focus on the static preservation of dead tissue or DNA. Key metadata relates to the *event* (sampling date, location) and the *storage condition* (e.g., -80°C, ethanol).
- Dynamic Repositories (Culture Collections): Institutions such as CCAP and NORCCA manage living strains. Their metadata requirements are significantly more complex, necessitating the tracking of "strain history" (lineage), culture media recipes, and physiological status. This dynamic nature often makes standard biodiversity schemas

⁶⁸ DaRWIN (Data Research Warehouse Information Network): <https://darwin.naturalsciences.be/>

⁶⁹ Specify Collections Consortium: <https://www.specifysoftware.org/>

(like simple Darwin Core) insufficient without specific extensions (e.g., microbial extensions), further complicating data exchange.

C. Connectivity to Global Aggregators Finally, the "Findability" of the collections is uneven.

- The large museum biobanks typically act as established GBIF or OBIS publishers, with automated pipelines (e.g., IPT servers) that refresh data periodically.
- Conversely, many smaller collections hold what can be termed "Dark Data": high-quality biological resources that are catalogued internally but remain invisible to global search indices. For these nodes, the barrier to entry is often the technical debt required to set up and maintain a publishing server (IPT), rather than a lack of willingness to share.

This heterogeneity implies that a "one-size-fits-all" standard is not a viable eDNAqua-Plan recommendation. The infrastructure must support a two-tiered approach: sophisticated API-based harvesting for digitally mature nodes, and low-tech, template-based submission mechanisms (or "Publishing Proxies") to ensure the valuable resources held by smaller collections are not excluded from the European reference library.

4.3. Metadata Handling and Standardisation Practices

The capacity of biobanks and culture collections to integrate into the eDNA digital ecosystems is determined not by the physical quality of their samples, but by the structure and standardisation of their associated metadata. The survey results indicate a clear distinction between internal management practices and external data-sharing protocols.

4.3.1. Internal Data Management: From LIMS to Ad-hoc Solutions

Internal data management varies significantly based on the institutional scale, directly impacting the potential for automated interoperability.

- **Integrated LIMS:** The large museum-based biobanks (e.g., RBINS, LIB) operate within established Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) such as DaRWIn or Specify. These platforms are characterised by:
 - **Relational Architecture:** Capable of handling complex one-to-many relationships (e.g., one field campaign – many specimens – many tissue samples – many DNA extracts).
 - **Persistent Identification:** Automatic generation of stable internal identifiers (catalogue numbers) that remain constant over time.
 - **Traceability:** Logging of sample history, including location changes within freezers and loan history.
- **Ad-hoc Registries:** In contrast, smaller culture collections and research-based repositories often rely on ad-hoc solutions (e.g., Microsoft Excel, Access, or FileMaker). While these systems offer flexibility for recording highly-specific physiological data (crucial for living culture strains), they typically lack:
 - Versioning control.
 - Standardised API access for machine-to-machine communication.
 - Strict validation rules, leading to "dirty data" (e.g., inconsistent date formats or non-standard taxonomic names).

4.3.2. Adoption of Interoperability Standards

To bridge the gap between these internal systems and the global digital ecosystem, data must be mapped to community-accepted standards. The landscape of adoption is currently mixed:

1. Darwin Core (DwC): This is the ubiquitous standard for biodiversity data. All surveyed institutions that share data externally use DwC. However, standard DwC terms are often insufficient for the specific needs of biobanking (e.g., documenting DNA quality or extraction methods).
2. GGBN Extensions: The Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) Data Standard is the critical extension required for eDNA repositories. It adds fields for molecular data (e.g., `materialSampleType`, `preservationType`, `concentration`, `ratio260_280`).
 - *Current Status*: Only the most digitally mature nodes (e.g., LIB, RBINS) have fully implemented GGBN extensions in their IPT (Integrated Publishing Toolkit) pipelines.
3. MIABIS (Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing): While widely used in human biobanking, its adoption in the aquatic biodiversity domain remains limited, with most nodes prioritising GGBN standards which are better integrated into the GBIF/OBIS workflow.

4.3.3. Standardisation of Vocabularies

A significant finding from the questionnaire is the inconsistency in the use of controlled vocabularies. While fields such as *ScientificName* are generally mapped to taxonomic backbones (WoRMS, GBIF Backbone), other critical metadata fields often suffer from free-text entry.

- Anatomical Parts: Descriptions of tissues (e.g., "fin clip", "muscle", "liver") are frequently entered as text strings rather than using ontologies such as UBERON⁷⁰.
- Preparation Types: Terms describing storage (e.g., "frozen -80", "ethanol 96%") lack standardisation, making it difficult for users to filter available resources by preservation quality across different institutions.

There is a pressing need to move from "human-readable" labels to "machine-actionable" URIs. The eDNA digital ecosystems infrastructure must support and encourage the mapping of these free-text fields to established ontologies to ensure true interoperability.

4.4. Linking Strategies: From Physical Sample to Digital Object

The utility of a biobank in the genomic era is defined by its connectivity. A physical sample—no matter how well preserved—loses a significant portion of its scientific value if it cannot be unambiguously linked to the molecular data derived from it. This section analyses the mechanisms used by stakeholders to maintain the "Golden Thread" of traceability connecting the Physical Specimen – DNA Extract – Sequence Data – Biodiversity Record.

4.4.1. Persistent Identification (PIDs)

The foundation of any linking strategy is the unique identification of the physical object. The survey and landscape analysis reveal a transition phase in the community:

⁷⁰ UBERON (Uber-anatomy ontology): <https://obofoundry.org/ontology/uberon.html>

- Local Identifiers: The majority of smaller collections still rely solely on human-readable local identifiers (e.g., "Sample_A_123"). While these are essential for day-to-day internal curation and can certainly remain in use locally, relying *only* on them is problematic, as they are prone to duplication and ambiguity when aggregated at a European scale.
- Global Unique Identifiers (GUIDs): Therefore, the strong recommendation is that all physical samples must *also* be assigned a Universally Unique Identifier (UUID) or a resolvable HTTP URI (e.g., CETAF Stable Identifiers) for external data sharing. Digitally mature nodes (e.g., RBINS, LIB) already implement this dual approach. These global PIDs are machine-actionable and ensure that a specimen's digital citation remains valid across external databases, even if the physical collection is reorganised. These PIDs are machine-actionable and ensure that a specimen citation remains valid even if the collection is reorganised or the database platform changes.

4.4.2. Linking to Sequence Repositories (INSDC: ENA/NCBI)

The critical link between the biobank and the molecular world occurs during the submission of sequences to the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC).

- Mechanism: The link is established using the `specimen_voucher`, `bio_material` or `culture_collection` source modifiers in the ENA/GenBank metadata submission.
- Current Practice: Ideally, the Biobank's PID (e.g., `institution_code:collection_code:catalog_number`) is entered into this field. However, this is not always a mandatory field, and so may not be filled in.
- Identified Gap: A significant "broken link" was identified in the workflow. Often, the researcher (sequencer) fails to report the Accession Number (e.g., `OX123456`) back to the Biobank after publication. Consequently, the Biobank knows the sample was sequenced but lacks the direct digital link to the data, preventing the automated display of genomic information in the Biobank's catalogue.

4.4.3. Linking to Biodiversity Aggregators (GBIF/OBIS)

When Biobanks publish their catalogues to biodiversity networks, they utilise the DwC standard to maintain traceability.

- Core Link: The field `dwc:materialSampleID` is used to store the persistent identifier of the physical sample.
- Genomic Link: The field `dwc:associatedSequences` allows the Biobank to list the URLs or Accession Numbers of derived sequences.
- Aggregator Role: Platforms like OBIS and GBIF ingest these fields. However, if the `associatedSequences` field is not populated (due to the gap mentioned in Sec. 4.4.2), the user exploring the map on GBIF will not know that genetic data is available for that occurrence.

4.4.4. The Challenge of Derived Samples

A complex linking challenge specific to eDNA is the hierarchy of derivation:

Field Sample (Water Filter) – eDNA Extract – Library – Sequence Reads

Most current Collection Management Systems (CMS) are designed for a 1:1 relationship (One Specimen = One Record). They struggle to represent the "One Parent (Filter) – Many Children (PCR Replicates)" relationship required for metabarcoding. The GGBN Data Standard addresses this by treating DNA extracts as distinct material samples linked to a parent voucher, but implementation of this hierarchical logic is currently limited to the most advanced nodes in the network.

4.5. Taxonomic Interoperability and Mapping Services

A central challenge in the eDNA ecosystem is the "Taxonomic Disconnect" between the systems used to categorise physical specimens (morphological taxonomy) and those used to annotate genetic sequences (molecular taxonomy). While Biobanks and Culture Collections typically adhere to authoritative nomenclatural backbones like the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) or the Catalogue of Life (CoL), the downstream sequencing world predominantly relies on the NCBI Taxonomy (via GenBank/ENA).

This section details the technical mechanisms employed within the project to bridge these conflicting namespaces.

4.5.1. The WoRMS – NCBI Mapping Workflow

To ensure that eDNA data can be interpreted within the context of established biodiversity knowledge, a synchronisation pipeline is required. The project relies on the active collaboration between the WoRMS Data Management Team (VLIZ), the NCBI Taxonomy group, and the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). It is important to note that ENA acts primarily as a broker for taxonomy requests to NCBI—providing robust taxonomy APIs and data dumps—while the extensive NCBI team maintains the core taxonomy database.

The Taxonomic Trade-off: This mapping collaboration is crucial due to the inherent differences between the databases. WoRMS provides highly rigorous, expert-driven curation, but its scope is primarily marine (often lacking comprehensive coverage for freshwater and terrestrial aquatic organisms). Conversely, the NCBI Taxonomy offers the widest global coverage across all environments but is sometimes less scientifically rigorous than specialised expert registries like WoRMS.

The Mechanism: A direct one-to-one mapping is maintained between the WoRMS AphiaID (persistent identifier for the taxon name) and the NCBI TaxID.

Workflow: As determined from discussions with VLIZ and ENA, querying their respective APIs for real-time validation is computationally prohibitive due to the massive volume of data. Instead, there is a regular exchange of taxonomic metadata where a synchronised mapping file is generated and shared periodically between VLIZ and ENA (with ENA facilitating access to this taxonomy as the European node). This established process ensures that rigorously described marine species in WoRMS are flagged for inclusion in the broader NCBI taxonomy, and conversely, sequence-based clusters in NCBI can be reviewed for taxonomic validity.

4.5.2. Mapping Methodologies and Algorithms

The interoperability is not achieved through simple name lookups, which are prone to errors due to homonyms and synonyms. The mapping strategy employs a tiered approach:

1. Exact String Matching: The primary pass matches identical strings (Author + Year included). This resolves the majority of stable taxa.
2. Synonym Resolution: A critical step where the algorithm traverses the synonymy lists. Often, an eDNA sequence is annotated in NCBI with a junior synonym (outdated name), while the Biobank uses the currently accepted name. The mapping service resolves these to a single valid entity.
3. Fuzzy String Matching: Used to handle minor spelling variations (e.g., “*spp.*” vs “*sp.*” or varying anglicization of author names). This requires human curation to avoid false positives.
4. Contextual/Tree-based Validation: To resolve homonyms (identical names in different kingdoms, e.g., a plant genus and an animal genus sharing a name), the mapping validates the entire taxonomic tree (Kingdom – Phylum – Class). A match is only confirmed if the phylogenetic parentage aligns in both databases.

4.5.3. Case Study: European Freshwater Fishes

As part of the gap analysis for Task 3.3, we conducted a specific case study focusing on European freshwater fishes—a group where legislative taxonomic lists (e.g., EU Water Framework Directive) frequently clash with scientific revisions. The findings of this investigation are reported below to highlight key harmonization challenges.

- The Issue: Significant discrepancies were identified between major taxonomic references, specifically FishBase⁷¹, the Catalogue of Fishes⁷², and the European Catalogue of Freshwater Fishes⁷³.
- Relevance to Biobanks: The study highlighted that if a Biobank archives a sample under a locally-accepted name that does not currently exist in the NCBI backbone, the resulting eDNA sequences risk being rejected or “orphaned” (assigned merely to *Unidentified*) during submission to sequence repositories.
- Resolution: To address this specific gap, this task developed and tested a reconciled checklist. This checklist successfully acts as a translation layer, demonstrating how Biobanks can retain their curatorial names internally while exporting metadata that is fully compliant with global genomic standards.

4.5.4. Identified Gaps

Despite these workflows, significant gaps remain:

- Latency: There is a time lag between a taxonomic revision (e.g., a genus split) being published in literature and its reflection in the NCBI backbone, creating a temporary dissociation between the physical voucher and its digital twin.
- “Dark Taxa”: A large proportion of eDNA clusters (OTUs) do not map to any Linnaean binomial. Currently, Biobanks lack a standardised way to catalogue samples that are only defined molecularly (e.g., “MOTU_001”) without a physical morphological ID. To address this critical gap, we recommend the establishment of a dedicated, cross-domain working group comprising representatives from Biobanks, Culture

⁷¹ FishBase: A Global Information System on Fishes. <https://www.fishbase.org/>

⁷² <https://researcharchive.calacademy.org/research/ichthyology/catalog/fishcatmain.asp> Eschmeyer's Catalog of Fishes (California Academy of Sciences)FishBase:

⁷³ European taxonomic reference lists commonly used for the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD), typically based on the standard checklists by Kottelat & Freyhof (2007)

Collections, taxonomic authorities (e.g., WoRMS), and genomic repositories (e.g., NCBI). The primary objective of this group would be to define and agree upon a standardised, machine-interoperable framework for assigning, cataloguing, and safely exchanging stable identifiers for these non-Linnaean, molecularly-defined taxa.

- The Proliferation of "Temporary Names": A significant hurdle for taxonomic interoperability is the widespread use of temporary or provisional names (open nomenclature) in ecological and molecular studies. Researchers frequently assign informal identifiers (e.g., 'sp. A', 'cf.', or alphanumeric MOTU codes) to organisms awaiting formal morphological description or when identification is inconclusive. As discussed in recent literature (Horton et al., 2025)⁷⁴, these temporary names create a profound conflict with traditional taxonomic backbones like WoRMS, which are strictly governed by nomenclatural codes and rely on formally published Linnaean binomials. Because these provisional names cannot be easily integrated or validated within traditional registries, they fail to map accurately to molecular databases (such as NCBI Taxonomy). This disconnect results in fragmented digital records, where a physical voucher in a Biobank and its corresponding eDNA sequence cannot be unambiguously linked, ultimately generating orphaned "dark data" that hinders large-scale biodiversity assessments.

4.6. Harmonisation of Molecular and Non-Molecular Frameworks

While Sec. 4.5 details the technical services available for taxonomic mapping, the operational reality within European biobanks is more complex. A significant "Taxonomic Divide" exists between the biodiversity domain (governed by morphological taxonomy and codes of nomenclature) and the genomics domain (governed by the NCBI Taxonomy).

This section audits the current status of taxonomic harmonisation across the project stakeholders, identifying which local frameworks are compatible with the downstream molecular ecosystem.

4.6.1. Compatibility Matrix: Biobanks vs. Sequence Repositories

The following table summarises the taxonomic backbones currently employed by the surveyed Biobanks and Culture Collections (CC) and assesses their direct interoperability with the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC/ENA).

Table 4.1: Taxonomic Compatibility Landscape of Aquatic Stakeholders

Stakeholder Profile	Representative Examples	Primary Internal Taxonomy	Format	Compatibility Molecular DBs (NCBI)	Key Harmonization Friction	Current Resolution Strategy
National Museum Biobanks	RBINS (BE), LIB (DE), Naturalis (NL), MNHN (FR)	WoRMS / GBIF Backbone / CoL	Persistent IDs (AphiaID / GBIF ID)	High	Latency: Valid morphological names in WoRMS take months to sync with NCBI.	Automated Mapping: Using scripts to link AphiaIDs to TaxIDs (e.g.,

⁷⁴ Horton, T., Rabone, M., Ahyong, S. T., Bieler, R., Boyko, C. B., Brandão, S. N., ... & Vandepitte, L. (2025). Tackling temporary names: interim solutions for the taxonomic impediment. *Marine Biodiversity*, 55(5), 76.

						T3.3.4 pipeline).
Generalist Culture Collections (Algae/Protozoa)	CCAP (UK), SAG (DE), NIVA/NORCCA (NO)	Specialised Lists (e.g., AlgaeBase)	Mixed (Strain IDs + Text)	Medium	Synonymy Conflict: Historic strain names often mapped to "unaccepted" synonyms in NCBI.	Manual Curation: Curators manually look up TaxIDs upon user request or sequencing.
Specialised Collections (Diatoms)	BCCM/DCG (BE)	DiatomBase / AlgaeBase	Local IDs	Low	Cryptic Diversity: Strains are often morphologically identical but genetically distinct (Cryptic Species). NCBI lumps them; Collections split them.	Dual Naming: Maintaining a "morphospecies" name and a separate "molecular clade" label.
Specialised Collections (Cyanobacteria)	PCC (FR), BEA (ES), LEGE (PT)	LPSN / CyanoDB	Strain Numbers (e.g., PCC 7120)	Variable	Nomenclatural Code Conflict: Conflict between Botanical (ICN) vs. Bacterial (ICNP) codes. Many "names" are invalid in NCBI.	Strain-Level ID: Ignoring species names and relying solely on Strain Numbers (e.g., "Synechocystis sp. PCC 6803").
Environmental Specimen Banks	PIE-UPV/EHU (ES), ESB (DE)	EUNIS (Habitat) / Local	Sample IDs (No Taxon ID)	N/A	Matrix vs. Taxon: Samples are often "bulk environmental" (sediment, water) without a single taxon ID.	Metadata Tagging: Linking to community sequence data (metabarcoding) rather than single-organism taxonomy.
Genomic - Oriented Biobanks	GGBN Members	NCBI Taxonomy	NCBI TaxID	Native	"Dark Taxa": Use of OTUs or "cf." names that have no equivalence in morphological catalogues.	Open Nomenclature: Heavy use of temporary names ("sp.", "aff.") accepted by GenBank.

As illustrated in Table 4.1, the taxonomic compatibility landscape between physical repositories and molecular databases (such as NCBI) is highly fragmented. There is no "one-size-fits-all" solution, as the points of friction are deeply tied to the specific biological domain and the institutional workflows of each collection. Several key patterns emerge from this analysis:

- **Varying Degrees of Automation:** Large national museum biobanks exhibit high compatibility driven by automated workflows and established Persistent Identifiers (PIDs). For these institutions, the primary barrier is technological latency (the time it takes for systems to sync) rather than a lack of standardization.
- **Biological and Nomenclatural Roadblocks:** Specialised culture collections struggle with profound structural challenges. Issues such as cryptic diversity (e.g., in diatoms) or conflicting nomenclatural codes (e.g., ICN vs. ICNP in cyanobacteria) cannot be solved by simple IT mapping. These collections are currently forced to rely on heavy manual curation, dual-naming systems, or strain-level identifiers to bypass rigid database rules.
- **The Paradigm Shift of Environmental Samples:** Environmental Specimen Banks and genomic-oriented collections often operate outside traditional Linnaean taxonomy altogether. Dealing with bulk matrices or "dark taxa" requires entirely different, metadata-driven approaches rather than traditional single-taxon matching.

4.6.2. The Harmonisation Challenge

The matrix highlights that "compatibility" is not merely technical but semantic.

- **The "Accepted Name" Conflict:** A Biobank may curate a sample under a valid name according to the *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature* (e.g., *Genus species A*). However, if the molecular database (NCBI) follows a different phylogenetic opinion where *Genus A* is split into *Genus B*, the automated submission of the sample metadata will fail or result in misclassification.
- **Lack of Resolution Services:** Currently, smaller collections (Research Stations) lack access to real-time reconciliation services. They manually type names into spreadsheets, creating a bottleneck when these datasets need to be harmonised for EU-level reporting.

4.6.3. Proposed Harmonisation Layer

To resolve these conflicts without forcing Biobanks to abandon their preferred taxonomy, eDNAqua-Plan proposes a "Translation Layer" approach:

1. **Marine Nodes:** Must implement the WoRMS-to-NCBI mapping (described in 4.5) to validate names prior to sequencing.
2. **Freshwater Nodes:** Are encouraged to map local lists to the GBIF Backbone, which acts as a "Rosetta Stone," maintaining links to both NCBI and morphological catalogues.

4.7. Gap Analysis and Infrastructure Connectivity

While the individual components of the eDNA ecosystem (Biobanks, Sequencing Facilities, Data Repositories) function adequately in isolation, the analysis reveals critical structural gaps in how they connect. The current landscape is defined by fragmentation and unidirectional data flows, which severely limit the "Findability" and "Reusability" of physical resources.

4.7.1. Findability: The Absence of a Unified Aquatic Catalogue

To answer the fundamental question—“*Where can I find a physical reference sample of Species X for sequencing?*”—a user currently faces a fragmented discovery process.

- The Gap: There is no single, centralised "European Aquatic Biobank Catalogue."
- The Reality: Users must query multiple disjointed portals:
 1. GGBN Portal: Excellent for genomic samples but limited to members of that specific network (mostly large museums).
 2. GBIF/OBIS: Contain occurrence records, but filtering specifically for "available physical material" is complex and often unreliable due to unfilled `preparations` or `materialSampleID` fields.
 3. Institutional Websites: Many smaller culture collections (as identified in the survey) only list their holdings on local, non-standardised web pages or PDFs.
- Consequence: High-value samples existing in smaller nodes remain "invisible" to the global research community.

4.7.2. Connectivity to DNA Infrastructures: The "Broken Feedback Loop"

A critical infrastructural failure occurs between Biobanks and DNA Repositories (ENA/NCBI).

- Unidirectional Flow: The flow of information is currently one-way. A sample leaves the Biobank, is sequenced, and the data is uploaded to ENA.
- The Missing Link: There is no automated mechanism for the Biobank to "know" that its sample has been sequenced. The accession number generated by ENA is rarely pushed back to the Biobank's Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) or database.
- Metadata Disconnect: In ENA, the `specimen_voucher` field is often populated with free text (e.g., "Fish_Sample_01") rather than a resolvable PID. This prevents automated harvesters from linking the sequence back to the rich metadata held by the Biobank (e.g., environmental conditions at the time of sampling), rendering the sequence less useful for ecological modeling.

4.7.3. Connectivity to Biodiversity Infrastructures: The "Leaky Bucket"

When Biobanks publish data to biodiversity aggregators (OBIS/GBIF) using Darwin Core, data richness is often lost due to mapping rigidities.

- Loss of Environmental Context: Biobanks holding environmental samples (e.g., eDNA water filters) often have rich associated physicochemical data (temperature, salinity, pH). Standard DwC mappings often strip this information or place it in the `ExtendedMeasurementOrFact` (eMOF) extension. While eMOF is highly standardised—utilizing strict controlled vocabularies such as those from the BODC (British Oceanographic Data Centre)—the *existing* vocabularies are often insufficient to adequately capture the highly specific physiological and operational metadata required by Biobanks and Culture Collections. Furthermore, due to the nested structure of eMOF, this critical environmental context remains difficult for end-users to query and extract.
- Dynamic Data: Culture collections hold dynamic data (e.g., current strain viability, culture media history). This "living" metadata fits poorly into the static "occurrence"

model of biodiversity portals, leading to a loss of critical operational information for potential users of the strain.

4.7.4. The "Dark Data" of Non-Digitised Nodes

Finally, a significant gap exists regarding the "Digital Maturity" of the stakeholders identified in Section 4.2.

- The Issue: A substantial portion of specialised collections (approx. 40% of surveyed nodes) lack the technical infrastructure (IPT servers, APIs) to expose their catalogues to *any* aggregator.
- Impact: These collections represent "Dark Data" — physically existent but digitally non-existent. Without a "Publishing Proxy" mechanism (where a larger node publishes on behalf of a smaller one), these resources will remain disconnected from the eDNAqua-Plan ecosystem.

4.8. Recommendations for Enhanced Compatibility

Based on the survey results (Sec. 4.2) and the gap analysis (Sec. 4.7), the following technical recommendations are proposed to integrate European aquatic Biobanks and Culture Collections into the eDNAqua-Plan digital ecosystem. These recommendations aim to transition these infrastructures from passive "physical archives" to active, interoperable nodes in the genomic value chain.

4.8.1. Adoption of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

To resolve the "broken link" issue between physical samples and digital sequences, the use of local, unstable identifiers must be abandoned.

- Requirement: All physical units (specimens, tissue samples, DNA extracts) must be assigned a globally unique Persistent Identifier (PID).
- Technical Implementation: Ideally, this should be a resolvable HTTP URI (e.g., CETAF Stable Identifiers) or a UUID. If this is not locally feasible, the triplet format `InstitutionCode:CollectionCode:CatalogNumber` must be strictly enforced and maintained unchanged across database migrations.

4.8.2. Implementation of GGBN Data Standards

Standard Darwin Core (DwC) is insufficient for the specific needs of eDNA banking.

- Requirement: Data pipelines must adopt the Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN) Extensions alongside Darwin Core.
- Key Fields: It is mandatory to capture molecular-specific metadata such as `ggbn:materialSampleType` (e.g., "DNA extract"), `ggbn:concentration`, `ggbn:quality` (e.g., "260/280 ratio"), and `ggbn:preparationMethod`. This allows researchers to filter samples based on their suitability for specific sequencing technologies (e.g., Long-Read vs. Short-Read).

4.8.3. Controlled Vocabularies over Free Text

To improve machine readability and aggregation:

- Requirement: Free-text fields for anatomical parts and life stages must be mapped to established ontologies.
- Ontologies:
 - UBERON for anatomical structures. Instead of free-text like "fin clip", data pipelines should use standardised CURIEs (Compact URIs) such as `UBERON:0000000`. Recording terms as CURIEs ensures that these Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are machine-findable and can be automatically resolved into full URIs by data aggregators using standard namespace registries.
 - ENVO (Environment Ontology) for describing the habitat of environmental samples (e.g., water filters).

4.8.4. Closing the "Feedback Loop" with Sequence Repositories

Connectivity must become bidirectional.

- Action for Data Submitters (Biobanks and External Users): Whether the sequencing is performed internally by the Biobank or externally by researchers utilizing Biobank materials, the data submitter must actively push the Biobank's originating PID into the `specimen_voucher` or `bio_material` fields when submitting data to INSDC repositories (ENA/NCBI).
- Action for Sequencers: A workflow must be established where the generated Accession Numbers (e.g., `OX123456`) are reported back to the Biobank. This should be automated via scripts that query the ENA API using the Biobank's PID to retrieve linked sequences, thereby enriching the Biobank's local catalogue.

4.8.5. The "Publishing Proxy" Model for Smaller Nodes

To address the "Dark Data" problem of smaller, non-digitised collections:

- The ecosystem should support a "Publishing Proxy" model. Smaller culture collections or research stations without IT infrastructure should not struggle to set up their own IPT servers. Instead, they should format their data (via standardised spreadsheet templates) and submit it to an established "publishing proxy". Depending on their domain and geographic location, this could be a National GBIF Node, a thematic node (e.g., EurOBIS for marine data), or a well-equipped partner institution. This flexible routing ensures that even in regions lacking dedicated national data infrastructures, smaller nodes can achieve visibility in global registries without imposing technical debt on the data provider.

4.8.6. Automated Taxonomic Reconciliation

To mitigate the disconnect between morphological and molecular taxonomy:

- Biobanks should integrate the WoRMS-to-NCBI mapping service (developed in Task 3.3.4) into their validation pipelines. This ensures that when a physical specimen is digitised, its taxonomic name is automatically checked against the molecular

backbone, flagging potential mismatches (e.g., synonyms or homonyms) before the data leaves the institution.

5. Relevant summary of findings from other tasks

Landscaping and gap analyses of the eDNA digital ecosystem have been carried out by tasks in WP2, 3, and 4. In this section we summarise their results that are particularly relevant “linking” (connections, (meta)data links, sharing; Findability and Accessibility) and “compatibility” (Interoperability and Reusability) of all the stakeholders in the digital ecosystem.

LLM ([Claude](https://claude.ai/login)⁷⁵) was used to do the heavy lifting of generating initial tables of gaps in the WP3 conceptual landscape and the WP4 use cases; this was manually checked and modified, with gaps added or removed.

5.1 Barcode / reference libraries

For deliverable [D2.1](#)⁷⁶, an analysis of the gaps for reference libraries was produced. Table D2.1 summarises these gaps. The summary of this report is

*... a reasonable progress has been made in Europe to build reference libraries for aquatic organisms, there is a considerable dispersion of initiatives and uncoordinated efforts. This resulted in reference libraries with varied levels of comprehensiveness, metadata content, taxonomic curation, auditability, accessibility and interoperability. Hence, there is a **strong need for standardised metadata practices, rigorous and harmonised full-curation procedures, and improved data-sharing mechanisms...***

Table D2.1 DNA barcode libraries gaps

Category	Gap	Description
Specimen source, taxonomic identification and processing	Unequal coverage of aquatic ecosystems.	Most of the data available for freshwater and marine water, i.e. limited information from transitional waters and scarce from groundwaters.
	Diverse sources of taxonomy in different libraries.	Sources of cross-reference source for taxonomy were diverse and dependent on the environment or taxa used. For example, WoRMS was the main choice for marine and transition waters, whereas for freshwaters it was WoRMS along with NCBI and GBIF that dominated.
	Different methods and ranks of identification for Metazoa versus microbial libraries.	Morphology-based, species-level taxonomic identification of specimens was the most used approach for metazoan-dominated repositories, while the molecular identification and genus- or family-level identification were associated with microbial repositories.

⁷⁵ <https://claude.ai/login>

⁷⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/15167446>

Category	Gap	Description
	Little information on the library's quantitative data.	There were few replies with quantitative data on the number of the specimens and species included in the reference barcode libraries. The available replies indicate that most repositories have fewer than 200 species and below 500 specimens.
	Considerable variation among taxonomic groups in terms of the degree of coverage.	Overall, libraries for freshwater organisms appear to be more complete than for those inhabiting marine and transitional waters, which have low representation of some dominant and diverse groups (e.g. gastropods). Globally, fish species are much better represented than invertebrates. There are still many gaps in non-indigenous marine invertebrate species, which due to their potential environmental impact deserve particular attention in marine biomonitoring programs. Finally, the gap evaluation for microbial organisms is far more complex than for macro-organisms.
	Limited information on voucher storage conditions.	Specimens are primarily stored in academic or museum collections. Ethanol was the most frequently used storage preservative, especially for freshwater and marine specimens, followed by sub-zero temperatures. However most replies did not mention the ethanol concentration, which may have a strong impact in the ability to recover DNA in the future.
DNA sequence data, metadata and data management	Broad diversity of molecular markers used as barcodes.	Although COX1 (formal animal barcode region at the 5' end of the gene) was the most represented marker for each environment, 19 other markers are also used and deposited in databases, depending on the taxonomic group and environment. For example, 16SrRNA is prevalent in transitional and fresh waters, while 12SrRNA is used predominantly for fish and other vertebrates. For such markers, lacking a standard barcode region, publicly-available sequences are composed of a mosaic of segments from different regions within the gene, often restricted to the few base pairs delimited by the most commonly used metabarcoding primers. This makes it hard to appreciate the taxonomic coverage and effectiveness of the reference library for general DNA-based monitoring.
	Lack of established metadata standards.	Metadata standards were followed only in about half of the reviewed libraries, the majority of which referred to BOLD and Darwin Core. The most frequently deposited metadata included: project identification, GPS coordinates, voucher ID and location, person collecting and identifying specimens, depth/altitude.
	Relevant metadata missing in most cases	Collection date, which is highly relevant for specimens collected from the wild, was rarely mentioned. Extremely relevant metadata, such as images of specimens, PCR and sequencing primers, trace files and sequencing platforms were provided in fewer than half of the cases.

Category	Gap	Description
	Lack of generally recognised minimal criteria for sequence acceptance in reference libraries.	The sequence-acceptance procedure in the libraries was primarily based on sequence quality, then sequence length, and also metadata traceability, but the latter in less than one third of the cases.
	Lack of uniform taxonomic curation procedures.	Taxonomic curation procedures were applied in just under 65% of the libraries. The curation procedures varied considerably and were not equivalent. Phylogenetic congruence checks were only reported for about one third of the libraries with curation procedures. General appraisal and recommendations for reference libraries auditing annotation and curation systems are needed.
DNA sequence data repositories	Non-generalised storage of multiple molecular markers	Only half of the repositories store data on multiple molecular markers.
	Lack of regular yearly updates.	Most of the repositories were updated periodically, but only a few annually.
	Variable or inexistent metadata standards	Only two databases have mandatory metadata. Merely a third of the repositories provide GPS coordinates for specimen records.
	Lack of workflow information.	Most repositories lack detailed workflow information such as sample collection and sequencing protocols.
	Scarcity of confidence levels for taxonomic identifications	Some taxonomic curation is used by nearly all repositories but, at the same time, most lack confidence levels for taxonomic identifications.
	Lack of API standards.	Most repositories do not offer API, desktop or console support. Some lack any web interfaces.

Grouping these gaps into themes that are (as much as possible) common over the entire digital ecosystem that eDNAqua-Plan has investigated,

1. **Suboptimal metadata provision.** Lack of rich metadata associated with published sequences and specimens: dates, images, primers, voucher storage conditions, confidence levels for taxonomic identifications etc. Metadata terms and/or vocabularies/ontologies to accommodate the more complex information are necessary, and it should be created by and in common use over the entire community. A solution is to make more fields mandatory (see Appendix [A6](#)), alternatively to find some other way to encourage, and make it easier to provide, these metadata (e.g. LIMS to enable metadata collection throughout the data life-cycle, coupled with their exporting in the formats and with the standards required by the data publishing infrastructures). Affects Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability.
2. **Lack of established metadata standards.** Lack of use of established metadata standards by many reference libraries. Better sharing of, communication about, and providing assistance in the adoption of those standards could help. *Affects Findability and Interoperability.*

3. **Lack of workflow provenance information.** Provenance templates for recording and exposing workflow metadata should be developed by a combination of scientific and data-technical experts. Publication of these workflows and their metadata should be required by journals (where the scientific results are reported) and encouraged via acknowledgement (software and data are as valuable as scientific results). *Affects Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability.*
4. **Limited data publishing** for the fresh, transitional, and groundwater domains. Increased use of online-accessible, and generally open access, data repositories is clearly the solution here, but how to encourage and reward this is the question. Where such repositories do not exist/can be adopted, then new ones need to be created: they should adopt existing genomics and marine (meta)data templates, formats, and standards. Local/national databases are good, but there could also be an equivalent of OBIS for these domains, alternatively greater use of GBIF; use of INSDC databases for genomics data. *Affects Findability and Accessibility.*
5. **Lack of (standard) APIs.** At a technical level this is an easy gap to plug, as many standard APIs, free to investigate and implement, are available. However, not every stakeholder has the resources to add these to their existing systems, and these entities should be supported in doing this work (sharing is caring). *Improves Findability and Accessibility.*
6. **Heterogeneity of taxonomic systems and taxonomic identification approaches in use.** There is nothing wrong with a diversity of approaches, but that should be based on the science rather than historical reasons. Mappings between different systems is a must to the provision of interoperability. Standardised metadata to capture the key information about identification approaches should be more widely used. *Affects Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability.*
7. **Lack of minimal criteria for sequence acceptance in reference libraries.** Metadata describing sequence acceptance should be included by default; vocabularies to describe the processes may be necessary. *Affects Findability and Reusability.*
8. **Lack of uniform taxonomic curation procedures.** Curation procedures should be documented (they fall under provenance information) in a standardised way/ Working groups could be created to create uniformity curation criteria (which could be in addition to those each infrastructure themselves have) and to recommend metadata, or create a vocabulary, to convey the key information about those criteria. *Affects Findability and Reusability*
9. **Lack of regular yearly updates.** Formal accreditation (along the lines of CoreTrustSeal or IODE accreditation) for infrastructures, whereby regular updates and information about the updating are (interoperably) provided, could encourage and reward this. *Affects sustainability, correctness, and relevance.*
10. **Diversity of molecular markers used as barcodes.** A diversity of molecular markers makes obtaining full information across taxonomic groups and ecosystems a challenge, in particular in biomonitoring. More mandatory requirements on standardised metadata to convey the information about what was used to create a published sequence can allow for a better assessment of coverage. A forum via which the stakeholders producing and using the barcodes can communicate their coverage could help. *Affects Findability and Reusability.*

Resources and rewards for making any improvements are as necessary as the work itself.

5.2 eDNA data infrastructures

For deliverable [D2.2⁷⁷](#), an analysis of the gaps for eDNA data infrastructures (repositories) was produced. Table D2.2 summarises these gaps.

Table D2.2 eDNA repositories gaps

Gap	Description
eDNA raw sequence data is scattered through many repositories	Much eDNA raw sequence data is external to INSDC archives, which makes it difficult to find or reuse data. We were not able to determine exactly how much, but reviews have estimated up to 50% and this is supported by our LLM investigation.
eDNA sequence storage DBs reference only found in 50-77% of scientific papers	Related to the previous gap, in the LLM investigation at best 77% of scientific papers contain the eDNA sequence storage location.
Each repository has its own API and little consistency of each API	eDNA raw sequence accession IDs are hard to query for or to retrieve from many portals or even their APIs, making federated queries challenging
Missing important general sample or sequence related metadata	One third of repositories in the survey are missing any general sample or sequence related metadata e.g. GPS coordinate or library_strategy
Many repositories have no stated processed metadata standards	41/61 repositories of the survey had no stated processed metadata standards, so it is difficult to know the provenance.
Some repositories are using global metadata standards, but many are not	DwC (e.g. OBIS and GBIF) and GSC MlxS (e.g. INSDC) are the most commonly used where there are global standards. Indeed there is a MlxS TDWG-DwC mapping task force. Where eDNA data is buried in papers or in generalist repositories such as Dryad etc., it is less likely to be using global, topic-relevant standards.
Difficult to query for aquatic environmental samples/raw sequence records from the INSDC archives	There are multiple parameters needed to get aquatic environmental samples from the INSDC archives in terms of coverage and accuracy.
Inconsistency of data formats besides FASTA (albeit variable) and FASTQ	Other than for sequence data formats, there is far less standardisation which reduces interoperability and reusability e.g. a variety of OTU/ASV table formats are used.
Barcode gene identification is inconsistent in INSDC	In the INSDC, barcode gene nomenclature for eDNA aquatic samples are rarely captured in the “target_gene” field and we determined that only 20% recorded in the study description or title.
INSDC users sometimes using generic and not aquatic specific checklists	Generic sample checklists with less mandatory information are available at INSDC databases. Users sometimes tend to use these checklists instead of the more specific and metadata rich checklists, which limits data searchability and reusability.
Sampling and archives have been disproportionately lacking from Eastern Europe.	In terms of ecological environments across Europe, there is much diversity of aquatic environments in Europe, in terms of marine, freshwater, ground and brackish. There are eDNA samples in the major seas surrounding Europe and in many countries.

⁷⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/15168646>

Gap	Description
The INSDC raw sequence only gets the taxonomy id initially provided on submission.	The INSDC only gets the taxId at the time the sequences have been uploaded, the taxId is not updated after any improved taxonomic identification, unless the data submitter actively updates the record or the change is due to an update in the taxonomic backbone.
Generally difficult to specifically find eDNA records.	It is hard in most resources to even get a count of eDNA records. It is sometimes not clear what is a raw eDNA sequence record, what is processed and how to query for such.

Grouping these gaps into themes that are (as much as possible) common over the entire digital ecosystem that eDNAqua-Plan has investigated,

1. **Insufficient data publishing.** *Affects FAIRness in general.*
 - a. **Much eDNA data is not published in INSDC repositories.** Data creators (scientists *and* their employing institutions) have to be strongly encouraged to and rewarded for publishing data in the first place: it should be mandatory that publicly-funded data are made publicly available, and it should be mandatory that employers provide tools that help scientists to publish their data. A separate issue is that much eDNA data are published in generalist repositories (e.g. as associated with journals). Unfortunately, such repositories lack the necessary specialised metadata, and do not generally enforce the necessary data standard and templates, making it harder to find the data and guarantee interoperability. Metadata sharing (i.e. to indicate that such data exist elsewhere) between generalist repositories and the specialist ones could help here (INSDC repositories are not currently designed to handle metadata only, e.g. there being no field to link to the URL to external data, however cross-linking to a large number of other resources is done and can be accessed via their [cross-link search](#)⁷⁸). eDNA data that are published in non-INSDC but still genomics-focussed repositories present a findability problem: if you do not know of the existence of these repositories, how can you find their data? Again, sharing at least the metadata about their data with INSDC could provide a solution. INSDC is to be favoured mainly because they have become the de facto repositories for most genomics data, and as such are in a position to create collaborations, links, and ensure compatibility with the other stakeholders in the digital ecosystem.
 - b. **A gap in data from Eastern Europe.** To ensure a sustainable flow of data from regions that are currently not doing so, one needs to investigate why they are not doing so and what they need to start doing so: mind-set, resources, encouragement, tools...
2. **Insufficient metadata on eDNA data availability.** Regular reporting of eDNA data endpoints (i.e. from where they can be found online) is too low. Journals need to enforce a data statement in which the location of the data related to the paper is given. *Affects Findability.*
3. **Suboptimal metadata provision.** *Affects Findability.*
 - a. As raised in Sec. [5.1](#), the solution here is to make more fields mandatory or to find some other way to encourage and make the provision of these metadata easier. With some standout exceptions (GBIF and OBIS), some repositories

⁷⁸ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/xref>

are not using global metadata standards (rather they are using in-house, or none). INSDC repositories typically use GSC MixS, but are hampered by allowing users to provide a minimal amount of metadata.

- b. There is also a lack of search terms for both aquatic data in repositories, and search terms to flag and find eDNA data. These should systematically be added to the metadata checklists being used. Insufficient metadata capture of barcode gene nomenclature can also be resolved by creating and using the necessary terms/vocabularies/schemas. *Affects Findability.*
4. **Lack of provenance metadata (on processing steps).** As raised in Sec. 5.1, more mandatory provenance metadata are required, and templates to record such metadata (ideally via LIMS or other tools) should be created and maintained, by the communities concerned. *Affects Findability and Reusability.*
5. **Insufficient uptake of global metadata standards.** *Affects Interoperability and Reusability.*
6. **Inconsistent API landscape.** Similar to a point in Sec. 5.1, developing and documenting APIs are a must for a smooth, interoperable, digital landscape. *Affects Findability and Accessibility.*
7. **Inconsistency in data formats.** Standardisation of the OTU/ASV (and any other) formats is a key solution here, followed by adoption of those standards by the related data repositories. To be clear, this is not just about using CSV vs XLSX, but about the details of the formatting of the data *in* the files so that they are also standardised, so they are machine-understandable. See Fig. 14 for some examples. For the specific case of taking the data in OTU/ASV tables to publish in biodiversity archives, where reformatting is required (in particular for the DwC-A of GBIF and OBIS), tools to do that reformatting can work far better, on more data, more efficiently, where the input data are standardised in terms of data format and data formatting. Providing tools that work on a fully standardised format could encourage the production of those so-standardised data by the workflow developers. Biological Observation Matrix (BIOM⁷⁹) is a standardised machine-readable example of a non-TSV table format for OTU with [extra metadata](https://biom-format.org/)⁸⁰. *Affects Interoperability.*
8. **Wider use of specific over general checklists required.** This is a matter of enforcement, and perhaps a change to the user interface so that it is easier to naturally choose a specialised checklist. *Affects Findability and Reusability.*
9. **No updating of taxonomic IDs in metadata at INSDC repositories.** It is always difficult to get data submitters to update their metadata once the data are published. Taxonomic information should be added as IDs, preferably URIs but at a minimum CURIEs, rather than as strings. This could ensure that the user of the data can find the taxonomic identification information in the taxonomic backbone it comes from. These backbones need to have ID management systems in place that ensure that the information related to their IDs are always current, and that the change report for each ID is readily available from that IDs endpoint. Where new taxonomic information arises because of subsequent analysis, if those new data are published and linked to the source data (in INSDC) then there is the possibility to automatically add updates on taxonomic information: this requires those respective repositories to share their (meta)data (we recommend using LOD) and incorporate any such updates in their databases.

Resources and rewards for making any improvements are as necessary as the work itself.

⁷⁹ <https://biom-format.org/>

⁸⁰ https://biom-format.org/documentation/format_versions/biom-2.1.html

Figure 14 Illustrating some of the variety of ways an OTU “table” is formatted. Four are TSV/CSV. Even if all your files were in QIIME Classic Style, they would not actually be interoperable unless the OTU_ID was known. The Biom offers formats that are readily machine readable, but would need tools to generate the format; a snippet is shown.

i) QIIME Classic Style (TSV/CSV)

OTU ID	Sample_1	Sample_2	Sample_3
OTU_1	1000	50	1200
OTU_2	200	800	150
OTU_3	0	10	500

ii) QIIME with Taxonomy (TSV/CSV)

OTU ID	Taxonomy	Sample_1	Sample_2	Sample_3
OTU_1	k__Bacteria;p__Firmicutes;g__Alloiooccus	5704	4984	5362
OTU_2	k__Bacteria;p__Proteobacteria;g__Moraxella	3080	20	100
OTU_3	k__Fungi;p__Ascomycota;g__Massarina	0	28	289

iii) Mothur (TSV/CSV)

Sample	OTU_1	OTU_2	OTU_3
Sample_1	1000	200	0
Sample_2	50	800	10
Sample_3	1200	150	500

iv) Long form (TSV/CSV)

Sample	OTU	Frequency
Sample_1	OTU_1	1000
Sample_2	OTU_1	50
Sample_3	OTU_1	1200
Sample_1	OTU_2	200
Sample_2	OTU_2	800
Sample_3	OTU_2	150
Sample_1	OTU_3	0
Sample_2	OTU_3	10
Sample_3	OTU_3	500

v) Biome 2.1 (HDF5)

```

...
GROUP "metadata" {
  DATASET "taxonomy" {
    DATATYPE H5T_STRING {
      STRSIZE H5T_VARIABLE;
      STRPAD H5T_STR_NULLTERM;
      CSET H5T_CSET_ASCII;
      CTYPE H5T_C_S1;
    }
    DATASPACE SIMPLE { ( 5, 7 ) / ( 5, 7 ) }
    DATA {
      (0,0): "k__Bacteria", "p__Proteobacteria",
      (0,2): "c__Gammaproteobacteria", "o__Enterobacteriales",
      (1,0): "k__Bacteria", "p__Cyanobacteria", "c__Nostocophycideae",
      (1,3): "o__Nostocales", "f__Nostocaceae", "g__Dolichospermum",
      (2,0): "k__Archaea", "p__Euryarchaeota", "c__Methanomicrobia",
      (2,3): "o__Methanosarcinales", "f__Methanosarcinaceae",
      (3,0): "k__Bacteria", "p__Firmicutes", "c__Clostridia",
      (3,3): "o__Halanaerobiales", "f__Halanaerobiaceae",
    }
  }
}
}
GROUP "sample" {
  GROUP "group-metadata" {
  }
  DATASET "ids" {
    DATATYPE H5T_STRING {
      STRSIZE H5T_VARIABLE;
      STRPAD H5T_STR_NULLTERM;
      CSET H5T_CSET_ASCII;
      CTYPE H5T_C_S1;
    }
    DATASPACE SIMPLE { ( 3 ) / ( 3 ) }
    DATA {
      (0): "Sample1", "Sample2", "Sample3"
    }
  }
}
...

```

5.3 eDNA workflows

For deliverable [D2.3](#)⁸¹, an analysis of the gaps for eDNA workflows was produced. Table D2.3 summarises these gaps. The report concludes that

*...highlight the **need for standardised workflows and metadata requirements** to support the scalability of eDNA monitoring in Europe and to ensure data adheres to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable)....The document stresses the importance of **promoting open access to national monitoring protocols and international cooperation on standard development**. It suggests **exploring whether submission of eDNA data to repositories can be mandated**, and **highlights a need for incentives for proper documentation and metadata compliance**.*

Table D2.3 eDNA workflows gaps

Category	Gap	Description
Scientific and practitioner community	Internal protocols and guidelines not published or not findable	Many are published in national languages only. A comprehensive review of workflows and guidelines is difficult.

⁸¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15168822>

Category	Gap	Description
	Lack of method standards	Plurality of methods, risk of incomparable data and problems in harmonising European-level data sets.
Data submission	Data from commissioned biomonitoring (including eDNA) is seldom accessible to the wider scientific community	Reports from commissioned biomonitoring (including eDNA) are often published as "grey literature" (without bibliographic indexing), and/or in native languages. The data are often not submitted to repositories or biodiversity portals. Limits findability and reusability.
	Occurrences based on eDNA seldom registered in biodiversity repositories	Manual search of GBIF and OBIS revealed that so far a limited number of data sets based on aquatic eDNA from Europe have been submitted (altogether c. 10 data sets).
	Metadata describing the eDNA workflow of sequencing data in the INSDC is usually scarce	BioSample metadata supplied by the submitter seldom contains information on sampling protocol, size fraction or DNA isolation protocol. Geographic coordinates are not in a standardised format. This limits the reusability of the data.
Data standards	The definitions of types of data records in the INSDC databases is unclear (e.g., a BioSample vs. a Sequencing run or Nucleotide record).	It is (at least apparently) not always clear from the documentation which type of metadata should be associated with each type of data record.
	Low granularity in the Darwin core DNA-derived data metadata related to bioinformatic processing	For instance, there is not a designated field for the sequence denoising method.

Grouping these gaps into themes that are (as much as possible) common over the entire digital ecosystem that eDNAqua-Plan has investigated,

1. **Limited publishing of provenance: in particular protocols**, these not findable or not accessible (language, publication). Overcoming the problem of publication language is not unique to the eDNA digital ecosystem. The state of automated language translation is currently very good, and could be employed more widely to perform translations; training them on the specific vocabulary used in science should not be too much of a (technical) problem. Additionally/Alternatively the most critical information could be given also in English. Encouraging (enforcing) and rewarding the publications of open access protocols and guidelines is required. A lack of provenance metadata in general is also highlighted, this also being a point raised in Sec. [5.1](#) and [5.2](#). *Affects Reusability.*
2. **Limited publication of biomonitoring data**. Incentives should be developed to encourage the open access publication of data from biomonitoring, rather than their only being written into reports. Data submission processes should consider non-academic data providers in their user interfaces and documentation. Collaborations between data infrastructures and the agencies receiving the reports

can help release data from the “grey literature” (in whatever language they are in): see [this news item](#)⁸² from GBIF on such an activity. *Affects FAIRness in general.*

3. **Limitations in metadata.** Lack of accommodation in DwC’s DNA extension for higher granularity in metadata on collection and processing (e.g. protocols, size fractions, geographical coordinates). Fuller use of the MIxS ID fields (e.g. `sampl_collect_device`, `size_frac`) should be encouraged. For any missing terms, it will be necessary to work with MIxS (GSC), TDWG and, GBIF and OBIS. Adopting the [FAIRe checklists](#)⁸³ would also solve the issues raised in this point (work is underway here). *Affects Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability.*
4. **Limited metadata documentation.** Documentation that does not explain how to add metadata correctly to the different levels of accessions in INSDC repositories, and what the different levels are supposed to (consistently) represent. As witnessed during the [Task 5.1 Blueprint workshop](#)⁸⁴, users find that the documentation provided (over the entire digital landscape) is generally insufficient to explain how to correctly describe their data via added metadata. Whether this is due to the documentation really being insufficient, whether it is too detailed, or whether users do not (feel they can) take sufficient time to read the documentation, is unclear. Nonetheless, this is a community problem that results in messy, unclear, insufficient metadata. *Affects FAIRness in general.*
5. **Plurality of methods**, a danger for scientifically-interoperable data. Harmonising data is not only a question of its technical interoperability, but also its scientific interoperability. Data that have been collected or processed in incompatible ways cannot be combined. While it should be that provenance metadata adequately describe the methods used, so that one can know *if* data can be used and combined, international standards on the (documentation of and the) methods for collecting and processing eDNA data could be developed. *Affects Interoperability and Reusability.*
6. **Slow uptake of the publication of eDNA-based results in biodiversity repositories.** With respect to GBIF and OBIS, the DNA extension to DwC has been available as a concept since early 2020 but accommodating those data in databases has taken several years more (this type of timeframe is normal). TDWG have a [community](#)⁸⁵ working on recommendations for TDWG standards for eDNA data, and work is ongoing in including aligning MIxS and DwC terms (eDNAqua-Plan have raised an [issue](#)⁸⁶ on the TDWG GitHub on this topic) and on incorporating the [FAIRe](#)⁸⁷ recommendations in various checklists. D2.3 reported on some gaps identified in the DNA extension, and on ongoing projects that may be able to help plug these gaps. While this work is ongoing, however, it is possible to now submit (e)DNA-based occurrences in OBIS and GBIF: a wide advertising initiative would help in uptake, as well as provision of user-friendly tools (e.g. GBIF’s [DwC validator](#)⁸⁸). A current deterrent for scientists to submit to OBIS is the need to report occurrences using the WoRMS taxonomy (to better guarantee quality in taxonomic information in OBIS), for which a (only semi-automated) mapping from omics taxonomies is currently possible. *Affects FAIRness in general.*

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<https://www.gbif.org/news/3VZX9IIIGcyXI2kVOrOH5qF/taskforce-on-nature-based-financial-disclosures-calls-for-more-biodiversity-data-from-businesses-via-gbif>

⁸³ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

⁸⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/18833437>

⁸⁵ <https://www.tdwg.org/community/gbwg/enviro/>

⁸⁶ <https://github.com/tdwg/gbwg/issues>

⁸⁷ <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

⁸⁸ <https://www.gbif.org/tool/81281/gbif-data-validator>

Resources and rewards for making any improvements are as necessary as the work itself.

5.4 WP3–M7 Current and future landscape

For milestone [M7](#)⁸⁹, an analysis of the current eDNA digital ecosystem was carried out, and a proposal for a better future ecosystem created. M7 reports on the current landscape, and identifies gaps, in summary:

*The current aquatic eDNA landscape has many unconnected or suboptimal links. Generally, the various data entities are **stored in a plethora of repositories: regional, national, global and thematic, but also institutional and sometimes only within scientific papers. Different, and sometimes not acknowledged, standards are used in these repositories. As a result, the FAIR principles are not being fully applied, resulting often in data that is not easily found, is inaccessible or unusable....***

*...an increased adoption of interoperable standards, and an expansion of the minimal metadata being collected. A common theme is that of **federation rather than centralisation**, as this is a pragmatic response to the desire to have institutional, national, or thematic repositories, and to the cost of building new centralised repositories. Using agreed **interoperable (meta)data standards and adopting widely-used web technologies (e.g. W3C) for data exposure and sharing**, will increase the resilience of the overall data infrastructure A proper **data management plan** ...would make collection, collation and deposition of (meta)data to appropriate repositories more straightforward and efficient. Furthermore, **engagement with standards organisations** means that the standards will be more sustainable, have a wider community acceptance, and result in wider (meta)data interoperability.*

Table M7 Landscaping gaps and Future proposal

Topic	Gap	Future Landscape
Fragmented and suboptimal metadata submission	Sample and sequence metadata are often incomplete, inconsistent, or missing entirely (e.g., GPS coordinates, library strategy). Many researchers treat metadata deposition as an afterthought.	Implementation of mandatory Data Management Plans (DMPs) using eDNA-specific templates. Metadata collection should become a seamless byproduct of adhering to international methodological standards (e.g., ISO/CEN).
Lack of standardisation in sampling and laboratory protocols	Protocols for sampling and DNA extraction are rarely published in open, machine-readable repositories (e.g. protocols.io or OBPS), making data provenance difficult to track.	Encouraging the use of Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS) to automate metadata generation and ensuring all protocols are deposited in specialist repositories with associated DOIs.
Siloed and inaccessible "in-house" repositories	Significant amounts of eDNA data (especially biomonitoring data) are kept in private or agency-specific repositories or buried in scientific papers, making it invisible to the	Moving away from "on demand" data sharing toward a federated network of open-access repositories. Promoting a "publish once, harvest often" model via global aggregators like GBIF and OBIS.

⁸⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/16367374>

Topic	Gap	Future Landscape
	wider community.	
Incomplete bioinformatics provenance and reproducibility	Custom bioinformatics scripts and intermediate files (QC results, etc.) are often not shared. Information on the specific computational environment used is frequently missing, hindering replication.	Adoption of workflow management systems (Nextflow, Snakemake) and containerization. Bioinformatics metadata should be linked directly to processed data using standardised formats like RO-Crate or JSON-LD.
Disconnect between raw sequences and processed biodiversity data	Only a fraction of studies share processed data (ASV/OTU tables) in FAIR repositories; they are often relegated to paper supplements or generalist repositories (Zenodo/Dryad) without enforced standards.	Development of "one-stop-shop" tools to stream data from raw sequences to biodiversity occurrences. ENA, GBIF, and OBIS are actively developing services to link ASV/OTU tables directly to sequence archives.
Taxonomic curation feedback loop deficiencies	Taxonomic curation in specialised libraries is rarely reported back to primary databases (INSDC). Genomic taxonomic systems often lack permanent, unique identifiers for novel or unnamed taxa.	Establishing a "network of servers" for reference libraries that exchange data. Implementing feedback systems (such as the Contextual Data Clearing House) to update primary archival records with expert curated annotations.
Heterogeneity and digital isolation of biobanks	Biobanks suffer from inconsistent data formats (Excel/Word), inadequate sample traceability to research outputs, and underrepresentation of certain species or environmental matrices.	Digital transformation of all biobanks, moving from Excel to LIMS-integrated databases. Integration of biobank metadata with INSDC and biodiversity repositories to ensure clear links between physical specimens and digital genetic data.
Lack of incentives and credit for data sharing	Researchers lack strong incentives to perform the time-consuming work of high-quality data deposition, as it is often not credited as effectively as a primary publication.	Implementing a certification/quality label for datasets and repositories that adhere to FAIR standards. Enhancing data citation tracking and enabling researchers to claim ownership of data records via ORCID.

In summary, M7 reports the following:

1. **Suboptimal metadata submission.** Metadata should not be an afterthought. DMPs can be used to improve the current behaviour because the FAIR management of metadata should be described in a DMP. Where DMPs are checked and enforced, even better. *Improves Findability and Interoperability.*
2. **Lack of sample and laboratory provenance.** The collection and publication of metadata and documentation (e.g. protocols), that provide the provenance trail should be encouraged. Adoption of LIMS could help make it easier for these metadata to be published. Publication of protocols should be a default. Provision of provenance templates to make it easier to understand what is necessary. *Improves Reusability.*
3. **eDNA data not published in open access, findable, and accessible repositories.** A federated network of open access repositories, with a "publish once, harvest multiple times" model via data aggregators. Mandate the publication of data created with public funding. *Improves Findability and Accessibility.*

4. **Incomplete bioinformatics provenance.** Publishing bioinformatics workflows, together with standardised descriptive metadata templates, should be encouraged. Sufficient information (as metadata and files) should be provided so the workflows can be reproduced. Heavier use of workflow management systems would help. *Improves Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability.*
5. **Insufficient publication of analysis results,** e.g. OTU/ASV tables. "One-stop-shop" approaches to stream data publication. *Improves Findability and Reusability.*
6. **Taxonomic curation feedback loops.** More information regarding taxonomic curation should be made available in INSDC repositories, and a wider use of GUIDs for novel and unnamed taxa required. Implement a network of servers to allow reference libraries to exchange and allow updates of data and to share curation methodologies. *Improves Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability.*
7. **Heterogeneity and digital isolation of biobanks.** More harmonisation of data standards, schemas, and templates required, and uptake of modern data management systems encouraged. Integration of biobanks metadata with eDNA and biodiversity infrastructures should be encouraged and supported. *Improves Findability, Interoperability, and Reusability.*
8. **Lack of incentives and credit for sharing.** Key to engaging all data creators is to credit them for their work and for sharing their (meta)data. Create a recognition system of databases/libraries that follow (really) best practices. Establish connections between recognised/curated databases so they can communicate through an integrated network. *Improves overall FAIRness and harmonisation.*
9. **Adopting web standards.** To enable machine2machine (meta)data and information sharing, web standards (LOD, W3C protocols, etc) should be adopted. As little of this is currently used by any of the stakeholders in the digital ecosystem (although uptake is increasing), and as many organisations lack the expertise and resources to move in this direction, we suggest European / international groups work together to produce guidelines, tools, techniques, training, resources. *Improves overall FAIRness.*

Resources and rewards for making any improvements are as necessary as the work itself. The environment needs to encourage, champion and reward efforts to deposit data and meet FAIR principles.

5.5 WP4 Use cases

WP4, deliverable [D12](#)⁹⁰, "Report on workflow pitfalls" (Deliverable 12), reports on the problems identified across the different eDNA workflow stages via their use case study. These are summarised in Table D12.

Table: D12 Use Cases from D12 Report on workflow pitfalls

Category	Gap	Description
Data Management Plans (DMPs)	Lack of DMP tailored templates	Existing DMP platforms use generic templates that are not specific to "omics" or eDNA data, causing uncertainty about which datasets and metadata should be included.
	Absence of standards guidance	Templates lack integrated guidance on applicable eDNA metadata standards (e.g., FAIRe, MixS, DwC), making the process time-consuming and inconsistent.

⁹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/17227009>

Category	Gap	Description
Sequence data submission	Non-intuitive processes	Submission to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) is considered impractical and overly complex for non-experts without condensed, user-friendly guidelines. But easy-to-use once understood.
	Low automation	There is a lack of automated tools and scripts to streamline the transition from field/lab metadata to ENA-compliant formats.
	Technical hurdles	Users frequently encounter errors with file checksums, interrupted uploads, and issues with Taxonomic IDs (tax_ID).
Interoperability and metadata standards	Template misalignment	Field names in the FAIR checklist do not currently align with ENA/SRA templates, preventing direct submission without manual adjustments.
	Usability issues	In standard templates (like FAIR), important field descriptions are often hidden in Excel comments, hindering simultaneous editing and viewing.
	Metagenomics gap	Current metadata checklists are heavily oriented toward PCR-based methods (metabarcoding/qPCR) and lack fields for shotgun sequencing and mitogenomics.
	Scaling constraints	The use of Excel-based templates for large metabarcoding datasets is limited by the software's row and column capacities.
Laboratory protocols	Lack of standardisation	Many protocols in publications lack a clear step-by-step procedure and a standardised vocabulary (controlled vocabularies).
	Difficulty in metadata tagging	Finding correct terms for MIOP and FAIR sections is difficult due to scattered or "dead" links to external ontologies (OBI, ENVO, GAZ).
	Platform barriers	Version control via GitHub can be challenging for staff without programming experience; meanwhile, platforms like protocols.io raise concerns about long-term open access.
	Conceptual confusion	There is often confusion between making a protocol "FAIR" (findable/accessible) and making it "machine-readable" (executable by machines).
Bioinformatic workflows	Optional metadata	Many FAIR bioinformatics fields are non-mandatory, leading users to skip critical information about their pipelines.
	Tool-specific bias	Existing fields for taxonomic annotation are focused on BLAST, failing to accommodate sequence composition-based classifiers (e.g., RDP probability thresholds).
	Incomplete metagenomics coverage	Crucial metagenomic steps—such as assembly, binning (MAGs), and functional annotation (KEGG, Pfam)—are currently missing from the FAIR checklist.
Global biodiversity portals (GBIF/OBIS)	Metadata retrieval	Obtaining the necessary URLs for raw sequence data and biosamples from SRA/ENA to link within GBIF is not straightforward for users.

Category	Gap	Description
	Layered data complexity	GBIF is currently centered on species occurrence (metabarcoding) and is not yet fully adapted to the layered complexity of metagenomic data (taxonomic, functional, and MAG layers).
	Access barriers	Data publication requires institutional access and coordination with national contact points, which can be an administrative hurdle.
Taxonomic assignment	Database quality	High-quality metadata in a reference sequence does not guarantee correct taxonomic identification, often due to original misidentification of the voucher specimen.
	Inapplicability of metagenomics to	Many obligatory metadata criteria for DNA markers are not applicable to metagenomic reference sequences.
	Scalability of curation	Curation is time-consuming and requires rare taxonomic expertise.
	Scalability of voucher imaging	Producing high-resolution diagnostic images is time-consuming and requires rare taxonomic expertise.

Recommendations to plug the gaps are:

1. **DMPs.** Example DMPs for eDNA data can be created (this will be one outcome of the eDNAqua-Plan project) including recommendations on standards, schemas, vocabularies, etc to use in a project's (meta)data. Specifically, they should integrate with MIxS, DwC, and FAIRe checklists/terms.
2. **Sequence data submission.** The process for data formatting for and submission to many of the repositories is found to be difficult. This was also brought up during the [Task 5.1 Blueprint workshop](#) and in the analysis reported in Secs [5.1](#)–[5.4](#). More HowTo-style documentation (short, focussed, visual), rather than manuals, is suggested, along with expanded FAQs. More tools and scripts, which could be created by the community but should also be provided by all employers, will help; tools for submitting large amounts of data, and which ensure quality metadata are provided (and quality controlled) is suggested. The level of data literacy is generally quite low among the scientists in the eDNA ecosystem, and more education and training is a must: a good understanding of what interoperable data are, what metadata are, why vocabularies are useful and how to use them, is a necessary for FAIR data to be created in the first place. Technical hurdles occurred, and these should be regularly guarded against. More use of brokerage services (e.g. [GFBio](#)⁹¹ in Germany) could also ease the burden on individual scientists when publishing their data. *Affects general FAIRness.*
3. **Interoperability and metadata standards.** Metadata to describe the different digital objects in the eDNA landscape suffer from a number of issues. *Affects Interoperability and Reusability*
 - a. The [FAIRe](#)⁹² checklists are to be highly recommended, however the field names adopted do not currently align with INSDC templates and so cannot (yet) be followed. Will adoption of the FAIRe checklists require changes to

⁹¹ <https://www.gfbio.org/>

⁹² <https://fair-edna.github.io/index.html>

- data infrastructures (and their current and historical data) or will the checklists have to change?
- b. The use of Excel as templates is bad practice: excel is not an open format, it will not open the same way in different applications (the definition of “not interoperable”), which is particularly annoying if comments or fonts are used to convey useful information. Text-only formats should be used for all templates, with comments added to the “template data package”, and fully worked-out examples provided.
 - c. Current metadata checklists are heavily oriented to PCR-based methods. Fields for shotgun sequencing and metagenomics should be added.
 - d. Mapping between different vocabularies and checklists should be provided, sustained, and easily findable.
4. **Laboratory protocols: standardisation, publishing, platforms**
- a. Protocols are vital, and that they describe the steps undertaken in a clear manner is important. More standardisation would make them more understandable (interoperable) and (re)usable. Training in writing protocols help, as well as clear, easy to find templates.
 - b. A report on dead links to at least some vocabulary terms (ENVO, GAZ, OBI are the examples mentioned). Without more detail it is unclear what the cause could be, but a solution could be for an automatic check to be made on the terms once they are entered in the metadata forms or as they are listed (in a machine-findable way, e.g. via keywords) in the documents. This would ensure that the terms are entered as value URIs.
 - c. Machine-readable and -understandable protocols is a worthy goal, but this is something that data technicians should be responsible for, not the average scientist.
 - d. Protocol publication via protocols.io has a long history, but it was recently sold to Springer Nature: while publishing open access public protocols is still free, this does raise worries about its (free) future.
 - e. GitHub is used by many to make protocols available. However, using and navigating Github version control is not an intuitive process.
 - f. The structured [BeBOP](https://github.com/BeBOP-OBON)⁹³ protocols are a great resource; that for metagenomics should be improved to better accommodate these workflows.
5. **Bioinformatics workflows: insufficient metadata.** A number of points, *affecting Interoperability and Reusability*
- a. Too many metadata fields are not mandatory. This is a point brought up over and again in the [Task 5.1 Blueprint workshop](#)⁹⁴: in short, some data infrastructures do not want to make more metadata mandatory as that results in a drop in data submissions, a greater curation burden for them, and/or is not compatible with their remit. However, without more mandatory metadata the quality of the data as provided by the repositories is always going to be limited to what we have today (i.e. an imperfect data ecosystem).
 - b. Expansion of metadata to include sequence composition-based classifiers is required.
 - c. Crucial metagenomics steps are missing from the FAIRe checklists, and should be added.
6. **Global biodiversity data portals: metadata, (meta)data models, and data submission.** A number of issues *affecting Findability, Interoperability and Reusability.*

⁹³ <https://github.com/BeBOP-OBON>

⁹⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/18833437>

- a. Obtaining the URLs for raw sequence data in the metadata of biodiversity datasets (e.g. on GBIF) is considered to be difficult. A solution would be to ensure that information is published directly as URIs rather than PIDs (i.e. as only the accession numbers).
 - b. The checkbox to indicate data submitted to GBIF can be shared with OBIS should be more obvious.
 - c. Complexity in data layers: it is observed that GBIF (and we presume also OBIS) is not yet fully adapted to the layered complexity of metagenomic data. An ontology (/data model) that could be agreed by all involved stakeholders would be a solution, and a “metagenomic toolkit” is suggested.
 - d. Not all countries have national nodes in OBIS and GBIF, and not all data can fit into the thematic nodes. How to deal with this should be clearly documented. In addition, the coordination with national contact points that is necessary to publish data is considered to be an administrative burden. A consistent data submission interface (albeit that would require the agreement of all nodes!) may be a solution.
7. **Taxonomic assignment: metadata, curation, voucher imaging data.** A number of issues *affecting Findability, Reusability, and correctness*
- a. The quality of curation of databases, e.g. to correct original misidentifications. Curation is time-consuming, heavy on (rare) human resources, and needs to be better rewarded.
 - b. Metadata to better accommodate metagenomic reference sequences are required.
 - c. Metadata to indicate the sequencing technology and bioinformatic procedures used should be mandatory for reference sequences.
 - d. High-resolution images are vital evidence for and of an identification. Producing such images is time-consuming and requires rare taxonomic expertise. Resources and rewards are required.

5.6 Combining these WP3+WP4 conclusions with recommendations collated during the course of T3.3

Looking at the conclusions from Secs 5.1–5.5, we find some commonalities:

- Reference libraries:
 - More standardised metadata and in particular metadata for provenance
 - Improved data sharing mechanisms
 - Between taxonomic systems: more mapping, and information on how the mapping is done,
 - More standardised APIs
- eDNA data infrastructures:
 - More standardised metadata and in particular metadata for provenance
 - Better standardisation of data within their formats
- eDNA workflows
 - More standardised metadata, and in particular metadata for provenance
 - More publishing of the results of monitoring as data, a better connection of monitoring bodies to data repositories
- The overall Landscape
 - Interoperability between the domains in the eDNA digital ecosystem should be improved: standards and requirements on the data

- Federation over centralisation. There is already significant data sharing between “local” data infrastructures and global ones, and this should be further encouraged (and better documented). The Ocean Data Information System (ODIS) could be of use in automating this process and in providing the resulting metadata in a machine-findable and -interoperable way. ODIS provides templates for publishing metadata about data that are published elsewhere. Their templates, being based on schema.org and exposed in JSON-LD, are highly web-friendly, machine-understandable, and when published in a suitable portal, are also both human- and machine-findable (e.g. the ODIS “[Catalogue of Sources](#)⁹⁵”). This could be a way to connect the ecosystem at the dataset discovery and description metadata level, making those metadata more findable and interoperable. The templates also allow for much provenance metadata to be added, which is important for reusability (that does, however, require that the data creators and data infrastructures that publish those data do provide this provenance information in the first place). For stakeholders that cannot afford to invest in modern web-friendly data technology, this could be a way for them to do that (requiring them to provide the content, but not design the templates or provide the web tech). This is something that will be looked at for the T5.1 Roadmap.

Most gaps share a common root: a lack of enforced, usable, well-aligned standards and incentives for publishing complete, linkable provenance and metadata across the full eDNA workflow. This is leading to fragmented, hard-to-reuse output, by any audience: humans or machines.

Acknowledgements

We thank the wider eDNAqua-Plan project and scientific board scientists for the insightful discussions and contributions in workshops and other events.

We also thank Joana Pauperio (ENA) for their review of (sections of) this report.

⁹⁵ <https://catalogue.odis.org/>

Appendix

A1 Table of T3.3 stakeholders

These are the stakeholders – largely, but not exclusively European – that were investigated for their (meta)data, standards, and links by T3.3. Note that not all were investigated to the same level of detail, as this depended on the stakeholder type we classified them as, and the services and data they provided. The fullest investigation was for the biodiversity and genomics data infrastructures, for the reference libraries and taxonomic systems we were primarily interested in their taxonomic references and other stakeholders they connected to, and for the rest we were interested in the other stakeholders they connected to.

We categorised the stakeholders into groups which are defined in a way that is useful to our landscaping analysis, and not one that reflects what those stakeholders define for themselves or fully captures what they do. For the range of allowed values for each of these categories, see Table A2.

- Scientific domain reflecting the type of science that their data cover, informed mainly by what the stakeholders themselves state on their websites
- Taxonomic scope (N/A where taxonomy is not a factor)
- Geographic scope: reflecting the most common geographic range of their data
- Stakeholder group reflecting how WP3 groups the stakeholder in our analyses, based on the main services they offer
- Technical domain “data” refer to research data outputs, while “metadata” refers to descriptive data that describe associated data. While all data infrastructures will manage metadata as well as data, here our focus is on what they provide to users via their web pages.

Name and Acronym	Scientific Domain	Taxonomic Scope	Geographic scope	Stakeholder group	Technical Domain
Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)	Biodiversity	Marine organisms	Global	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
European Ocean Biodiversity Information System (EurOBIS) / European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet)	Biodiversity	Marine organisms	Regional Europe	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	Biodiversity	All organisms	Global	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
PANGAEA	Earth, Environment	All organisms	Global	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
German Federation for Biological data (GFBIO)	Biodiversity, Environment	All organisms	National Germany	Data broker	Data, Metadata
Water Information System for Europe (WISE , Marine and Freshwater)	Environment	Marine and Freshwater organisms	Regional Europe	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
PlutoE	Biodiversity	All organisms	Global	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data management, Data

Name and Acronym	Scientific Domain	Taxonomic Scope	Geographic scope	Stakeholder group	Technical Domain
Finish node of GBIF (FINBIF)	Biodiversity	All organisms	National Finland	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal	Biodiversity	Marine organisms	Regional Antarctic, Southern Ocean	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
PNDB Data Repository	Biodiversity	All organisms	National France	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
EnviDat	Biodiversity, Environment	All organisms	National Switzerland, Global	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
DASSH	Biodiversity	All organisms	National - UK	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
MarineInfo	Marine	All organisms	Global	Marine data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
OpenBioDiv	Taxonomy	All organisms	Regional Europe	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
NBN Atlas	Biodiversity	All organisms	National - UK	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
GigaDB	General research	N/A	Global	General data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
Dryad	General research	N/A	Global	General data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
Zenodo	General	N/A	Regional Europe	- General data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
BCO-DMO	Biology, Chemistry	All organisms	Global	Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data
VertNet	Biodiversity	All organisms	Regional USA, Global	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
Dandjoo	Biodiversity	All organisms	National Australia	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data
Atlas of Living Australia (ALA)	Biodiversity	All organisms	National Australia	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
Observation	Biodiversity	All organisms	Global	Citizen science	Data
HELCOM Biodiversity Database	Biodiversity	All organisms	Regional Baltic Sea	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
iNaturalist	Biodiversity	All organisms	Global	Citizen science	Data
Freshwater Biodiversity Data Portal	Biodiversity	Freshwater organisms	Regional Europe	- Biodiversity data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI GenBank)	Genomics	All organisms	Global	Genomics data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
NCBI BioProject	Genomics	All organisms	Global	Genomics data infrastructure	Metadata
NCBI BioSample	Genomics, Samples	All organisms	Global	Genomics data	Metadata

Name and Acronym	Scientific Domain	Taxonomic Scope	Geographic scope	Stakeholder group	Technical Domain
				infrastructure	
FBI BioSample	Genomics, Sample	All organisms	Global	Genomics data infrastructure	Metadata
European Nucleotide Archive (EMBL-EBI ENA)	Genomics	All organisms	Global	Genomics data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA)	Genomics, Reference library	All organisms	Regional Europe	Genomics data network	Information sharing
Darwin Tree of Life	Genomics, Reference library, Bioinformatics		National - UK	Genomics data infrastructure, Genomics data network, Bioinformatics	Data, Metadata, Workflow
Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB)	Genomics, Biodiversity genomics	Microbes	National Australia	Genomics data infrastructure, Genomics analysis infrastructure	Data, Metadata, Workflows
Barcode Of Life Data Systems (BOLD)	Biodiversity genomics, Taxonomy, Reference library, Bioinformatics	All organisms	Global	Genomics data infrastructure, Reference library	Data, Metadata, Workflow
UNITE	Reference library, Bioinformatics	Protists	Global	Reference library	Data, Workflow
Swedish Biodiversity Data Infrastructure (SBDI)	Biodiversity, Genomics, Bioinformatics	All organisms	Global	Genomics data infrastructure	Data, Metadata, Workflow
Mgnify	Bioinformatics, Genomics	All organisms	Global	Genomics data infrastructure, Bioinformatics	Data, Metadata, Workflow
Global Genome Biodiversity Network (GGBN)	Biodiversity genomics, reference library, Bioinformatics	All organisms	Global	Genomics data network, Genomics data infrastructure	Data, metadata
Earth Biogenome Project	Biodiversity genomics	Eukaryotic	Global	Genomics data network	Information sharing
International Barcode of Life (iBOL)	Biodiversity genomics, Reference library	All organisms	Global	Taxonomy, Reference library	Data, Metadata
Freshwater Ecology	Biodiversity	Freshwater organisms	Regional Europe	Biodiversity	Metadata
Genomes on a Tree (GoaT)	Genomics, Reference library	Eukaryotic	Global	Genomics data infrastructure	Data, Metadata
Catalogue of Life	Taxonomy, Biodiversity genomics	All organisms	Global	Taxonomy	Metadata
European Alien Invasive Species Network (EASIN)	Taxonomy	Invasive organisms	Regional Europe	Taxonomy	Metadata
World Register of Marine	Taxonomy	Marine	Global	Taxonomy	Data,

Name and Acronym	Scientific Domain	Taxonomic Scope	Geographic scope	Stakeholder group	Technical Domain
Species (WoRMS)		organisms			Metadata
NBCI Taxonomy	Taxonomy	All organisms	Global	Taxonomy	Metadata
Ocean Data Information System (ODIS)	Marine data	N/A	Global	Data information system	Metadata
NIOZ Dataverse	Marine data	N/A	Global	Marine data infrastructure	Data, Metadata

A2 Stakeholder landscaping data

For collecting information on the (meta)data, links and information sharing, and the various standards used by the investigated stakeholders, we standardised the values so that our ChatGPT analysis produced reliable results. Values “none”, “unknown”, and “N/A” (not applicable) were also allowed, with “none” being treated as a real value in the analysis.

The spreadsheets with all the actual collected data are provided as attachments to the [Zenodo record](#)⁹⁶ for this deliverable: D3.3_AppA2a_StakeholderLandscaping.csv for the main data collection (the fields of which are tabulated below), and D3.3_AppA2b_StakeholderLandscaping.csv for the omics-metadata specific data collection (which is described in Sec. [.2.1.3](#)).

Questions	Explanation	Allowed values in the answers
Geographic scope	Whether global or restricted to certain regions	global, regional - region name, national - country name
Scientific domain	Scientific domain of their (meta)data	earth, environment, biodiversity, general, genomics, taxonomy, marine, freshwater, bioinformatics (any grade of working on sequences), general research, general, chemistry, biology, samples, reference library, biodiversity genomics (biodiversity limited to genetic and taxonomic information)
Taxonomic scope	Taxonomic scope of their (meta)data	marine organisms, freshwater organisms, all organisms, invasive organisms, protists, eukaryotic, microbes
Include DNA-based data	Are DNA data or DNA-based data accepted and specifically handled by the stakeholder	Yes, No
Stakeholder group	According to our Task 3.3 classification	biodiversity data infrastructure, genomics data infrastructure, genomics data network, general data infrastructure, marine data infrastructure, biodiversity genomics, bioinformatics, citizen science, reference library, data information system, taxonomy
Technical domain	Technical domain covered by the stakeholder	data, metadata, information sharing, workflow, data management
Metadata standard	Standard / schema used for metadata	All metadata standards found, with standardised formatting and spelling
Metadata export format	Format / standard in which metadata are provided to the	All metadata formats found, with standardised formatting and spelling

⁹⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/18890220>

Questions	Explanation	Allowed values in the answers
	public	
Data standard	Format / standard / schema of data coming in	All data standards found, with standardised formatting and spelling
Data export standard	Format / standard / schema of data provided to the public	All standards found, with standardised formatting and spelling
Data export methods	Wata export methods:webpage = download via a click on a webpage after a search; webtools = any GUI-based download/search/aggregate method, e.g. map searchers	All methods found, with standardised formatting and spelling
Data templates	Does the stakeholder provide templates for submitting data (spreadsheet, webform, etc), or explain how to use a standard format (e.g. DwC)?	yes, no
Data providers	Who provide data to the organisation	Acronyms of the organisations. Other allowed values are: OBIS nodes, GBIF nodes, individuals (i.e. anyone), projects, research institutes (this includes universities), citizen science, research programs (this includes projects), national authorities, own team (i.e. internally-provided), taxonomic backbones
Data receivers	Who harvest data from the organisation	Acronyms of the organisations. Other allowed values are: OBIS nodes, GBIF nodes, individuals (i.e. anyone), projects, research institutes (this includes universities), citizen science, research programs (this includes projects), national authorities, own team (i.e. internally-provided), taxonomic backbones, collections
Metadata providers	Who provide metadata to the organisation	Acronyms of the organisations. Other allowed values are: OBIS nodes, GBIF nodes, individuals (i.e. anyone), projects, research institutes (this includes universities), citizen science, research programs (this includes projects), national authorities, own team (i.e. internally-provided), taxonomic backbones, reference libraries
Metadata receivers	Who harvest metadata from the organisation	Acronyms of the organisations. Other allowed values are: OBIS nodes, GBIF nodes, individuals (i.e. anyone), projects, research institutes (this includes universities), citizen science, research programs (this includes projects), national authorities, own team (i.e. internally-provided), taxonomic backbones, reference libraries, collections
Data taxonomic reference	Which taxonomic backbones/systems are used in the data	The names of taxonomic systems used, including the standardised names of the stakeholders represented here. Also in-house
Metadata taxonomic reference	Which taxonomic backbones/systems are used in the metadata	The names of taxonomic systems used, including the standardised names of the stakeholders represented here. Also in-house
Data taxonomic ID format	In which format are taxonomic identifiers given in the data (not the names, just the identifiers)	LSID, TSN, PID, URI, NCBI GenBank PID, integer, PURL, PID (i.e. a formatted string)

Questions	Explanation	Allowed values in the answers
Metadata taxonomic ID format	In which format are taxonomic identifiers given in the metadata (not the names, just the identifiers)	LSID, TSN, PID, URI, NCBI GenBank PID, integer, PURL, PID (i.e. a formatted string)
Condition on taxonomic ID in data	Condition on taxonomic ID in the data	recommended, mandatory
Condition on taxonomic ID in metadata	Condition on taxonomic ID in the metadata	recommended, mandatory
Condition on taxonomic names in data	Condition on taxonomic names in the data	recommended, mandatory,
Condition on taxonomic names in metadata	Condition on taxonomic names in the metadata	recommended, mandatory
Data vocabulary	Which vocabularies are used in the data (excluding taxonomic)	Standardised names of vocabularies used. Also dataprovider provided (i.e. as provided by the data submitter), in-house
Metadata vocabulary	Which vocabularies are used in the metadata (excluding taxonomic)	Standardised names of vocabularies used. Also dataprovider provided (i.e. as provided by the data submitter), in-house, DCAT, in-house, schema.org
Data vocabulary format	What formats are the terms given in the data (excluding taxonomic)	URI, string, PID (i.e, formatted string), dataprovider provided (i.e. as provided by the data submitter)
Metadata vocabulary format	What formats are the terms given in the metadata (excluding taxonomic)	URI, string, PID (i.e, formatted string), dataprovider provided (i.e. as provided by the data submitter)
Data links	Which type of information in the data can link to data or metadata held elsewhere. This does not include links to software or publications - that is covered in the next tab	All types of links found, with standardised formatting and spelling
Metadata links	Which type of information in the metadata can link to data or metadata held elsewhere. This does not include links to software or publications - that is covered in the next tab	All types of links found, with standardised formatting and spelling
Data links format	How are these links given in the data	URI, string, PID (i.e, formatted string), dataprovider provided (i.e. as provided by the data submitter), webpage (i.e. on the page)
Metadata links format	How are these links given in the metadata	URI, DOI, string, PID (i.e, formatted string), dataprovider provided (i.e. as provided by the data submitter), webpage (i.e. on the page), CSV (download)
Organisations linked in data	Which organisations are linked to in the data via these fields	The standardised names of organisations that are mentioned in the data
Organisations linked in metadata	Which organisations are linked to in the metadata via these	The standardised names of organisations that are mentioned in the data

Questions	Explanation	Allowed values in the answers
metadata	fields	
Information about replicate samples in the data	What information, if any, is included in the data about the presence of replicate material	A mixed bag of values, some with explanation. Common values are: dataprovider provided, collection code, technical replicates
Information about voucher specimens in the data	What information, if any, is included in the data about the related voucher specimens	A mixed bag of values, some with explanation. Common values are: dataprovider provided, collection code, , specimen_voucher

A3 Graphs showing stakeholder (meta)data sharing

Biodiversity stakeholders

We created graphs showing the connections between the biodiversity stakeholders and their (meta)data providers and receivers, based on information available on the stakeholders websites. We have excluded individuals, research organisations, research programs, and universities in these diagrams. as almost all of the stakeholders work with these agents. “Partners” and “nodes” means official partners of the respective organisations. Note that we have slightly modified the input from the spreadsheet for these diagrams in order to make them easier to read and to complete some connections (e.g. adding specifically GBIF France and Sweden rather than including them as “nodes”, as they are specifically connected to by other stakeholders). We show first the agents that provide data and metadata to our biodiversity stakeholders, and then those that receive data and metadata from our biodiversity stakeholders. These 9 graphs are attached to the [Zenodo record](#)⁹⁷ for this deliverable: to see them in detail, we recommend viewing those. The filenames are: D3.3_AppA3_(meta)data_(receivers)(providers)_(from)(to)_(Biod)(All)Stakeholders.png, and D3.3_AppA3_org_linkedin_metadata+data_AllStakeholders.png.

⁹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/18890220>

Agents that provide data to our stakeholders

The agents that provide data to our biodiversity stakeholders, according to information collected from the websites of the stakeholders. The arrows point from the provider to the receiver.

Agents that receive data from our stakeholders

The agents that receive data from our biodiversity stakeholders, according to information collected from the websites of the stakeholders. The arrows point from the stakeholder receiver to those they receive from.

Agents that provide metadata to our stakeholders

The agents that provide metadata to our biodiversity stakeholders, according to information collected from the websites of the stakeholders. The arrows point from the provider to the receiver.

other organisations found in this investigations as follows (classification type+colour coding for the figures, followed by the organisation names):

Biodiversity organisations (blue)

OBIS, GBIF, GBIF nodes, OBIS nodes, EurOBIS, PANGAEA, EMODnet, GFBio, WISE Marine, WISE Freshwater, PlutoF, (all and any “official”) partners, FINBIF, SCAR Antarctic Biodiversity Portal, PNDP Data Repository, EnviDat, DASSH - MEDIN, NBN Atlas, BCO-DMO, VertNet, ALA, Observation, Dandjoo, HELCOM, iNaturalist, CoL, Freshwater Biodiversity Data Portal, NIOZ Dataverse, Freshwater Information Platform, SDBI, Freshwater Ecology, MarineInfo, GBIF Sweden, GBIF France, ICES, NIOZ researchers, MARBEF, KNB⁹⁹, NCEI, NOAA, MBLWHOI, EDITO, LW ERIC, Baltic Data Flows, CEFAS, Blue-Cloud, ELIXIR, own team

Other (with governmental / EU / international links) (brown)

EEA, CBD, EU Flood Directive, government, MSFD Database, European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum, EU Open Repository, national authorities, GOOS, data.europa.eu, UNEP, GEO, EDMED, opendata.swiss, DG ENV, EASIN, Eionet Central Data Repository, WISE WFD (Water Framework Directive Database), GEOSS, INSPIRE Geoportal, CSRD, The Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive, Freshwater Information Platform

Other (black)

Zenodo (data), Dryad, GigaDB, dataprovider provided, ODIS, BODC, partners, industry, AURA, AAS Journals, The Generic Mapping Tools, Biodiversity Literature repository, Machine Learning for Particle Physics, Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative, citizen science Pensoft, Plazi, Earthdata, Scopus, Google Dataset Search, Thomson-Reuters Data Citation Index, OpenAIRE, GCMD, SDN, DataOne

Genomics data infrastructures / bioinformatics (orange)

ENA, NCBI GenBank, INSDC, NCBI partners, BioSample (both NCBI and ENA), BioProject, MGnify, SRA, BOLD, dbGaP, GEO

Reference libraries (yellow)

UNITE, ERGA, reference libraries, GOAT, EUKARYOME¹⁰⁰

Taxonomies (green)

WoRMS, ITIS, AlgaeBase, FishBase, numerous taxonomies, EoL, taxonomic backbones, GBIF backbone

Culture Collections and Biobanks (purple)

BGBM, DSMZ, IPK¹⁰¹, culture collections, biobanks, MfN

Genomics biodiversity infrastructures (red)

⁹⁹ <https://knb.ecoinformatics.org/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://eukaryome.org>

¹⁰¹ <https://www.ipk-gatersleben.de/en/>

OpenBioDiv, SDBI, Earth Biogenome Project, GGBN, Genome Taxonomy Database, iBOL, Darwin Tree of Life

Providers of data to the stakeholders

The network of organisations that our stakeholders provide data to. Arrows point from the data provider to the receiver. Colour coding: blue=biodiversity, red=genomics biodiversity, orange=genomics, yellow=reference libraries, green=taxonomies, purple=biobank, culture collections, brown=other (gov't, int'l, EU), black=other

Receivers of data from the stakeholders

The network of organisations that our stakeholders receive data from. The arrows show the connection from the stakeholder to those that receive from them. Colour coding: blue=biodiversity, red=genomics biodiversity, orange=genomics, yellow=reference libraries, green=taxonomies, purple=biobank, brown=other (gov't, int'l, EU), black=other

Organisations mentioned in (meta)data

The organisations that are mentioned in the metadata and data of our stakeholders. Arrows point from the stakeholder to the mentioned organisation. Colour coding: blue=biodiversity, red=genomics biodiversity, orange=genomics, yellow=reference libraries, green=taxonomies, purple=biobank, culture collections, brown=other (gov't, int'l, EU), black=other

A4 Web services

The spreadsheet with all the collected data is provided as a download from the [Zenodo record](#)¹⁰² for this deliverable with the file name D3.3_AppA4_APIanalysis.csv. Here we tabulate the stakeholders investigated and their endpoints. Note that Open Tree of Life and PR2 are not among the stakeholders investigated in this deliverable but they have been investigated by T3.1. They have been included to increase the representation of reference libraries and taxonomies in our investigation.

¹⁰² <https://zenodo.org/records/18890220>

Stakeholder	Type	Home page	Endpoints to start investigation on
OBIS	Biodiversity	https://www.obis.org	https://api.obis.org/ , https://github.com/iobis/robis , see also https://manual.obis.org/dna_data.html#how-to-find-genetic-data-in-obis
GBIF	Biodiversity	https://www.gbif.org	https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/openapi/ and https://api.gbif.org/
PANGAEA	Biodiversity	https://www.pangaea.de	"Web services" on https://www.pangaea.de/about/services.php , https://pangeabio.io/docs/api , and the R and Py scripts mentioned on https://www.pangaea.de/tools/
DASSH - Medin	Biodiversity	https://www.dassh.ac.uk/	https://portal.medin.org.uk/portal/start.php , from there to https://portal.medin.org.uk/portal/api_docs.php
HELCOM Biodiversity database	Biodiversity	https://helcom.fi/baltic-sea-trends/biodiversity/ , https://unite.ut.ee/ , https://metadata.helcom.fi/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search	https://metadata.helcom.fi/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/search?facet.q=type%2Fservice , https://metadata.helcom.fi/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/search?facet.q=type%2Fservice-OGC:WMS , https://metadata.helcom.fi/geonetwork/srv/eng/catalog.search#/search?facet.q=type%2Fservice-ArcGIS
ENA	Genomics	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/api/swagger-ui/index.html , and https://swagger.io/specification/ . https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/retrieval/programmatic-access.html# may be useful
NCBI GenBank	Genomics	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/home/develop/api/ only the Entrez one; https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/docs/v2/api/rest-api/ , https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/datasets/docs/v2/api/
BOLD	Genomics, Reference library, Bioinformatics	https://boldsystems.org/	https://boldsystems.org/data/api/
BioSamples / NCBI	Genomics	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample	See the NCBI entry
BioSamples / ENA	Genomics	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/docs/references/api/overview
MGNify	Genomics,	https://www.ebi.ac.uk	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/api/v1/

Stakeholder	Type	Home page	Endpoints to start investigation on
	Bioninformatics	k/metagenomics	
GBIF - Taxonomy	Taxonomy	https://www.gbif.org/dataset/d7dddbf4-2cf0-4f39-9b2a-bb099caae36c	https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/openapi/v1/species
WoRMS	Taxonomy	https://www.marinespecies.org/	https://www.marinespecies.org/aphia.php?p=webservice
NCBI - Taxonomy	Taxonomy	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy	
Catalogue of Life	Taxonomy	https://www.catalogueoflife.org/	https://api.checklistbank.org/# , https://github.com/CatalogueOfLife/coldp (?), https://github.com/CatalogueOfLife/backend (?)
UNITE	Taxonomy, Reference library	https://unite.ut.ee/	https://portal.unite.eu/en_GB/developers/
PR2	Taxonomy, Reference library	https://pr2-database.org/	https://pr2database.github.io/pr2database/articles/pr2database.html , https://github.com/pr2database/pr2database (?)
Open Tree of Life	Taxonomy	https://opentreeoflife.github.io/	https://opentree.readthedocs.io/en/latest/api-docs.html , https://opentreeoflife.github.io/use for the R, python, jupyter

Our schema for assessing interoperability

We created a set of criteria for assessing interoperability of web services. This maturity model/checklist draws inspiration from several established lines of thinking about interoperability and system maturity. It reflects the layered interoperability approach of the [European Commission's European Interoperability Framework](#)¹⁰³, which distinguishes technical, semantic, and organisational levels. It also aligns with the FAIR data movement promoted by the [GO FAIR](#)¹⁰⁴ Initiative, especially the shift from simple data access to reusable, well-described, and governed data. At the technical level, it builds on API maturity thinking such as the [Richardson Maturity Model](#)¹⁰⁵ and common web/API best practices (REST, OpenAPI, cloud service evolution), extending them beyond interface design toward ecosystem integration and long-term operational reliability.

Level 0 - Ad Hoc / Isolated

Interoperability is effectively absent

- Access requires manual steps or human mediation

¹⁰³

<https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/iopeu-monitoring/european-interoperability-framework>

¹⁰⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

¹⁰⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richardson_Maturity_Model

- No stable endpoint URL
- Custom or undocumented request/response formats
- Tight coupling to a single application or UI

Why this matters

Anything that depends on people clicking buttons or copying files cannot scale or automate. Reuse is costly and fragile.

Example

A web portal where users download a CSV by hand after logging in, with column meanings known only to the original team.

Level 1 - Basic Technical Interoperability

The endpoint is technically consumable by multiple clients, but fragile

- Available over the web (HTTP/HTTPS-based endpoint)
- Uses common data formats (JSON, XML, CSV)
- Each request stands on its own (Stateless request–response model)
- Can be used without clicking through a UI (Machine-accessible without UI interaction)

Why this matters

This is the first step toward automation, but small changes can easily break consumers. Integration is possible, not dependable.

Typical Examples

A simple web endpoint that returns JSON when called, but whose structure occasionally changes without notice. A simple HTTP endpoint returning JSON Early-stage internal microservices. “Just hit this URL and see what comes back” APIs

Level 2 - Standardised API Interoperability

Independent clients can interoperate reliably

- Follows a consistent structure (REST or comparable architectural style)
- Addresses and responses behave predictably (Clear resource model and predictable URLs)
- Inputs and outputs are clearly defined (Explicit request/response schemas)
- Errors and versions are handled in a standard way (a.o. Standard HTTP methods and status codes)

Why this matters

This is where system-to-system use becomes realistic. Independent teams can build against it without constant coordination.

Typical Examples

A versioned data service where the same request always returns the same shaped response, and errors follow clear rules. Basic REST APIs (without OpenAPI). WSDL SOAP services (well-defined but opaque). OAI-PMH endpoints

Level 3 - Documented & Discoverable

New consumers can onboard without direct support

- A formal description of how it works (Machine-readable API specification (OpenAPI/Swagger))
- Clear written documentation (Human-readable documentation)
- Concrete examples of typical use (Example requests and responses)
- Errors are explained clearly (Clear error semantics)
- Easy to discover where and how to use it (Endpoint discoverable via registry or landing page, looking at “How findable are endpoints from their home page?”)

Why this matters

Interoperability now includes people you’ve never met. Adoption no longer depends on insider knowledge.

Typical Examples

A public service with a landing page, examples, and a downloadable specification that lets a new team get started in an afternoon. OpenAPI-described REST APIs. Public APIs with Swagger UI. Well-documented SOAP services (~ good readable documentation)

Level 4 - Cross-client Interoperability

Browsers, scripts, services, and workflows interoperate equally

- Does not assume a web browser (No browser-only assumptions (e.g. cookies, session state))
- Not dependent on a specific programming language (No language-specific dependencies)
- Works with general-purpose tools (Works with generic HTTP clients (curl, wget))
- Access rules are explicit and intentional (CORS policy explicitly defined (open or justified restrictions))

Why this matters

The endpoint stops favoring one ecosystem. Scripts, services, and workflows all work the same way.

Example

A data endpoint usable from a browser, a command-line script, or a backend service without special handling. Well-designed OpenAPI REST services. Elasticsearch HTTP API. Generic OGC services used outside GIS tooling

Level 5 - Ecosystem Integration

Interoperability extends into real-world workflows

- Supported helper tools or libraries (Official or community-supported clients (Python, R, etc.))

- Authentication works cleanly for automated use (Authentication abstracted cleanly for programmatic use)
- Clear rules for large result sets and limits (Pagination, rate limits, retries clearly defined)
- Designed for automation and repeated use (Supports automation and batch processing)

Why this matters

This is the difference between “nice in theory” and actually used in production.

Example

A service that supports scheduled data pulls, handles large datasets gracefully, and documents rate limits clearly. Elasticsearch clusters in production. Cloud APIs with SDKs (AWS, GCP, Azure). Mature OGC service deployments

Level 6 - Semantic Interoperability

Different systems understand the same data the same way

- Uses agreed-upon terms and concepts (Uses shared vocabularies or ontologies)
- Data fields mean the same thing everywhere (Field meanings are explicit and consistent)
- Identifiers can be understood outside the system (Identifiers are globally resolvable (URIs, DOIs, etc.))
- Aligns with recognised domain standards (e.g. GA4GH, OBO, DCAT)

Why this matters

Data can now move between organizations without being reinterpreted or re-mapped each time. This is true interoperability, not just data exchange.

Example

Two independent platforms exchanging biological or catalog data and agreeing on what each field means, not just how it's formatted. OGC services with domain profiles. OAI-PMH with well-defined metadata standards (e.g. Dublin Core). APIs aligned with strong community schemas (e.g. GA4GH)

Level 7 - Operational Interoperability

Interoperability is sustained over time, not accidental

- Changes don't break existing users unexpectedly (Backward compatibility guarantees)
- Retirements are announced in advance (Deprecation policy communicated in advance)
- Behavior is tested against expectations (Contract testing or validation in place)
- Reliability and availability are actively monitored (Monitoring and uptime guarantees)

Why this matters

Interoperability becomes a long-term commitment, not an accident. Trust builds, and downstream systems can rely on it.

Example

A long-running public data service that evolves over years without breaking existing integrations and communicates changes clearly. Long-running public infrastructure APIs. National or international data services. Standards-backed services with governance

A5 Two use-cases following data trails

We carried out two practical tests of the connectivity in the eDNA digital ecosystem by looking at two datasets published in biodiversity archives, and tracing those data back to the source data and material. Diagrams to accompany these cases are provided along with the [Zenodo record](#)¹⁰⁶ of this deliverable, called D3.3_AppA5_UseCase(1)(2).pdf.

Case 1: ARMS-MBON dataset

These data are published on OBIS

ARMS-MBON data on long-term monitoring of hard-bottom communities: COI results from 2018-2020 <https://obis.org/dataset/066f002f-58d5-4687-bdb8-b39cdaef0c2b>

The ARMS-MBON collaboration arose from the Horizon 2020 ASSEMBLE Plus project. Some 20 stations distributed around the coastline of Europe perform sampling for eDNA of benthic organisms using Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures (settlement plates). The dataset we looked at contained the results of the analysis of the COI sequences from all stations over the period 2018 to 2020. This dataset was submitted for publication by VLIZ, including the authors of this deliverable.

The starting point of this journey was this dataset. We looked to see how far along the provenance trail it was possible for someone to travel, and how easy or difficult this would be.

First, a report on the FAIRness of this metadata record and its related data.

Findability

- That same data is published on GBIF, but there is no link to that on the OBIS page. There is a link to the dataset in the IPT → *Recommendation to include links to all the related assets (data, publications, web-sites)*. We happen to know that the source metadata record (<https://www.eurobis.org/imis?module=dataset&dasid=8357>) does include links to related data, publications, and a web-site, and we wonder why the OBIS record does not display that information as well. Inspecting the metadata provided on the IPT (which is the medium via which data are submitted to EurOBIS and OBIS), we can see that the external data links *are* included, but related data and publications *are not*: *is this a failure in the metadata schema of the IPT or due to a lack of attention from the data provider?* (We happen to know that using the IPT to create a DwC package to submit is not easy and is a discouragingly manual process).
- When searching for other “ARMS-MBON” data from the OBIS search page on <https://obis.org/search>, we can see that there are two datasets with exactly the same title, published about 9 months apart: there is no information given about what the difference between the two is, and whether the first one ought to have been deprecated. We believe that the reason is that the 2024 publication was submitted

¹⁰⁶ <https://zenodo.org/records/18890220>

directly to OBIS while the 2025 version was ingested via EurOBIS → *Recommendation to include such information in the metadata record itself, and if not provided then to require it.*

Accessibility

- The dataset itself is very accessible and can be directly downloaded via the IPT, which is provided as a link in the OBIS metadata record.
- The OBIS page gives categorised information about the content of the DwC, which is very useful. One can see what fields and information are included in the DNA extension, for example. *As a nice-to-have, we would like to see more of this: for DNA-derived data included in DwC, various omics information is included the occurrence file, rather than the DNA file (for example, the identificationRemarks and References), and these are useful for people to also be able to see from this page, before having to inspect the DwC file itself.*

Interoperability

- As these data are provided in DwC, they are in the standard use by the larger biodiversity data infrastructures

Reusability

- There are many columns included in the DwC dataset that allow for reusability of the data:
 - sampling protocols is given as a URL
 - datasetID gives a link to the GitHub space for the project (although this is not the expected field for such information)
 - associated ENA run accession numbers are given
 - various bioinformatics information are given
 - NCBI taxonomy IDs are given for all occurrences, filling in the gap where AphiaIDs are not given
- A more detailed explanation about the content of the DwC is not given, making it difficult to learn about what information is available and where, for these data. This is relevant for DNA-derived occurrences because it is quite a nice area of biodiversity data publishing, and many non-omics scientists may want to use these data: they will not know what it is that they ought to know to use those data. *As a nice-to-have it would have been nice to have a more detailed explanation of the content of the data.*
- A licence is clearly stated on the IPT but it is not given in the metadata in OBIS → *Recommend that licence is added to OBIS, in other words that all the metadata available are displayed in all metadata records, not only those that have the data directly accessible.*

Next, a step-by-step provenance analysis of the dataset. We used a bottom-up method that simulates how a researcher might initially explore the dataset, starting with the taxonomic backbone and a specific occurrence record. We then followed by investigating the processed sequence data that underlies the occurrence record, followed by the bioinformatics pipeline and reference library used. Then we looked for the original raw sequencing data, the sample processing protocols, and lastly the original material sample:.

1. **Taxonomic backbone:** YES Links to WoRMS and NCBI IDs for each taxon in the OBIS metadata record, and the IDs themselves are in the DwC data file
2. **Provenance and biodiversity data:** YES The following are provided in the OBIS data

1. Country
 2. Coordinates and depth
 3. Event date
 4. Habitat keywords
 5. Protocols used (just sampling)
 6. Taxon classification from Kingdom to Species, and identification confidence level
3. **Provenance and biodiversity metadata:** SOME The following are provided in the metadata record on OBIS
1. On OBIS: Taxon classification from Kingdom to Species
 2. On the IPT: Taxon classification from Kingdom to Species; Event date; Coordinate bounding box
3. **Processed sequence data:** YES Processed DNA sequence information was provided in the OBIS data, including
1. The DNA sequence
 2. PCR forward and reverse primers; *however, the primer citation is not to an open access article*
 3. Material sample ID *however it is not linked to any other asset and so useful only as an internal string (albeit this is normal behaviour)*
 4. Dataset ID, which points to the GitHub repository where more on this data can be found
 5. Event ID *however it is not linked to any other asset and so useful only as an internal string (albeit this is normal behaviour)*
 6. Coordinates
 7. Date range *however no information about (lack of) precision is given*
 8. Sample size unit
 9. Sample size value
 10. *Identifying person is not given for sequences. There is no traditional "identifying person" for DNA-based occurrences, however one could be the name of the person who ran the bioinformatics code and did the QC on the results.*
 11. Institution Code
- **Bioinformatics pipeline and reference library:** NOT DIRECTLY FINDABLE OR ACCESSIBLE. The information about the bioinformatics code and its reference libraries are included in the OBIS data, in the columns identificationRemarks and identificationReferences. These columns are unstructured text, and how easily they can be understood will depend on the conscientiousness of the data submitted. Here, "PEMA v.2.1.4" is given and its GitHub link given in the first and "RDP classifier; confidence cutoff 0.8; ref db Midori v2" in the second.
 - PEMA is an open-source standardised pipeline for metabarcoding, combining reference libraries with a bioinformatics pipeline. The GitHub repository includes the code and link to the open access article given.
 - The parameter settings when running the code are given in identificationRemarks as "https://github.com/arms-mbon/analysis_release_001/tree/main/parameter_files": while this is appreciated, there could be a better explanation of this text. A longer explanation *is* provided on the GitHub repository.

- Similarly, the phrasing of the text in Identification References leaves something to be desired. Midori v2 is not directly accessible (no link is given); its link is given in the PEMA GitHub repository, however it was very unclear from that web-site how one can access “version 2” of that database.
- No information is available in ENA, however this is not expected as bioinformatics work is done to a later stage of the data.
- **Raw sequence data:** NOT DIRECTLY ACCESSIBLE The ENA run accession numbers are given (associatedSequences, in the occurrence file) but just as a ID, not as a link (hence it you have to know what this refers to in order to find them). Sample accession number is also given (in the EMOF file), although again only as an ID. That provides the following metadata
 - Year of sampling
 - Country and region
 - Coordinates
 - Standardised sample name used by ARMS-MBON for tracking
 - *Submitter ID: No specific person mentioned*
 - Description
- **Protocols:** PARTLY In the OBIS data, the link to the sampling protocol is given, but no link to the molecular protocols can be found (a field “sop” is available for this information). Reading the sampling protocol, we learn that photos are taken of the settlement plates as well as DNA, but no information about this fact is provided in the OBIS dataset (although one can eventually find that out from the documentation in GitHub). No protocol information can be found in the BioSample entry in ENA (which is copied to NCBI). No related publications are given either.
- **BioSample metadata:** SOME The material samples are described in the data, and the BioSample IDs are given (although not as a URL) and have the following metadata
 - Year of sampling
 - Country and region
 - Coordinates
 - Standardised sample name used by ARMS-MBON for tracking
 - *Submitter ID: No specific person mentioned*
 - Description
 - No protocols (see point above)

Overall impression and recommendations: This ARMS-MBON has nearly complete and findable, accessible, interoperable metadata with a few gaps. While following the trail from the OBIS data, through the bioinformatics, to the sampling data can be found, it did require persistence because of the need to identify external URLs, some general internet searches, and working our way though the associated GitHub site. *Recommendation that any dataset such as this is accompanied with an open access data paper, where a putative user of the data can be shown how the data were created and constructed. Alternatively, a standardised, separate provenance file to document could be provided (although that would need to be findable from the OBIS metadata).*

- No specific personnel is linked to any of the dataset records.
 - Providing information on the personnel (names or their roles/expertise level) provides transparency, traceability, and add to the trustability of the data.

- BioSample/Project metadata is findable but has poor linkage from the OBIS occurrence record
 - *Recommendation: any external IDs which can also be given as URLs, should be done so*
 - *Space is made here for related publications to be referenced (as URLs)*
- The fields that give reference library and bioinformatics information are only useful if the data submitter is conscientious when filling them in
 - *Recommendation to standardised these data entry for these fields in DwC (and MixS), if necessary to add more to contain specific information*
- The bioinformatics pipeline is well documented and seems highly reusable
- The GitHub repositories seem to be thorough, well documented and annotated.
- The reference library could eventually be found online, but how to access the version used was unclear.
 - *Recommend that all versions of reference libraries are frozen and published as a standalone, URL-linked and findable asset.*

A visual summary of this analysis can be found [here on our google folder](#)¹⁰⁷.

Case 2: ILVO metabarcoding marine macrobenthos and fish in the North Sea

These data are available on GBIF

eDNA from water column to characterise fish and invertebrate communities from 30 sites in the Belgian Part of the North Sea
<https://www.gbif.org/dataset/8fd84a4f-bbed-490b-9ca4-c0a3d0aea079>

These data are from water sampling carried out by ILVO in the Belgian part of the North Sea, taken in order to assess the usefulness of eDNA monitoring of the effects of wind farms on soft-sediment fauna. 12S eDNA was extracted and analysed with their bioinformatics workflow, and taxonomic lists produced and published.

First, a report on the FAIRness of this metadata record and its related data.

Findability

- A search on part of the title on the GBIF site reveals that there is related data (the same work, but for the COI marker). *Recommendation: related data should be linked to each other, especially when they are available from the same data infrastructure.*

Accessibility

- The dataset itself is very accessible and can be directly downloaded via the IPT, which is provided as a link in the metadata record.

Interoperability

- As these data are provided in DwC, they are in the standard use by the larger biodiversity data infrastructures

Reusability

¹⁰⁷ https://drive.google.com/file/d/16W4p_Ri9cC7aCGyFfjpnMRWa7foPZSdi

- We have the same comments as for case 1, except for the licence, as that is displayed on the GBIF metadata record.
- In addition, the sampling and sequencing methodology is written into the Methodology field. However, for the bioinformatics: no direct links to the codes were given, only some version numbers were included, the custom-made reference database is not findable or accessible. This is information that only the data provider should have given.

Next, a step-by-step provenance analysis of the dataset (bottom up method as described in the previous case), including the GBIF data and the linked omics (meta)data:

1. **Taxonomic backbone:** YES Data in GBIF are given IDs from its taxonomic backbone. These IDs can be found (with 3 clicks) from the metadata record, but are not available in the DwC data (neither as a URL or an ID). *Recommendation to include the IDs in the data as well*
2. **Provenance and biodiversity data:** YES The following are available in the GBIF data
 1. Country
 2. Coordinates and depth
 3. Event date
 4. Habitat keywords
 5. Protocols used (just sampling)
 6. Taxon classification from Kingdom to Species, and identification confidence level
3. **Provenance and biodiversity metadata:** LITTLE The following are available in the GBIF metadata record
 1. Event date
 2. Methodology
 3. A related publication is given, but the nature of the relationship is not clear (the metadata do not accommodate that information)
3. **Processed sequence data:** YES Processed DNA sequences are provided in the GBIF occurrence record, including
 1. The DNA sequence
 2. PCR forward and reverse primers, *however with no citation*
 3. Material sample IDs from NCBI as URLs
 4. Associated sequence IDs from NCBI, as URLs
 5. Coordinates
 6. Date/month/year of material sample
 7. Sample size unit
 8. Sample size value
 9. Identifying person
 10. Institution name and ID
4. **Reference libraries:** PARTLY A custom reference library is mentioned as the primary reference in the GBIF dataset description, but it is not described or linked. BLASTing against GenBank was also referenced in text. No information is available in NCBI, however this is not expected as reference library work is done to a later stage of the data.

5. **Bioinformatics pipeline:** PARTLY Pipeline information is given in text in the metadata (methodology), but no specific input parameters are provided. No information is available in NCBI, however this is not expected as reference library work is done to a later stage of the data.
6. **Raw sequence data:** YES The NCBI links to the raw sequences are given as URLs.
7. **Protocols:** PARTLY These are written into the GBIF metadata record (methodology) but are not also given in the data in the DwC files. Protocol names are given in the BioSample entries in NCBI, however the protocols behind the names are not accessible. Some sequencing protocol information can also be found on the SRA entries in NCBI, but again no protocol document is accessible from there. The same detail available in the GBIF methodology section is not given in the omics data. However, publications linked via the BioSample *do* contain a detailed description of the sampling, processing, and bioinformatics methodology, and moreover those publications are open access.
8. **BioSample data:** PARTLY In BioSamples (i.e. NCBI) the following information are available:
 1. Date
 2. Depth information (not a number, just a description)
 3. Habitat information (not from a vocabulary, however)
 4. Location, latitude, longitude
 5. Some sample collection information
 6. Some processing information

Overall impression and recommendations: This dataset has provided findable and accessible data and metadata that can be traced from GBIF to NCBI to its metadata in BioProject and BioSamples. The sampling and sequencing methodology is described in the GBIF metadata; in NCBI only protocol names can be found, although the related open access publications linked in the BioSample entry do give this information. However, that this is done is due to the consciousness of the data owners – this will not always be the case. The biggest break in the trail for these data is the lack of any Reusable information about the reference database, as this is not accessible. It is described (but still not accessible) in a related publication that can be found from the BioSample entry, but not from the GBIF metadata or data. Our recommendations are:

- *All protocols are provided as open access publications or documents, and links to these are included in the metadata in all places where the related data are published.*
- *Have more space in the GBIF metadata and in NCBI to hold related data and publications, where the nature of that relationship is also documented (terms taken from a controlled vocabulary).*
- *Reference databases, bioinformatics codes, and workflow settings should be mandatory to document in the metadata and/or data, and moreover the reference database and any codes should be documented as URLs (i.e. must be accessible).*

A visual summary of this analysis can be found [here on our google folder](#)¹⁰⁸.

¹⁰⁸ https://drive.google.com/file/d/16W4p_Ri9cC7aCGyFfjpnMRWa7foPZSdi

A6 Mandatory Fields in Relevant Resources

FAIRe Checklists Mandatory Fields - (v1.02, January 2026)

a) Link Related Mandatory Fields

project_id, **samp_name** (but **sample_id** would be better!), **geographical** (decimalLongitude decimalLatitude geo_loc_name eventDate env_broad_scale env_local_scale env_medium), **seq_id**

Highly recommended include: **taxonID**, **taxonID_db**,

b) All Mandatory Fields

data_type	section	term_name	description	requirement level code	requirement level
projectMetadata	Project	recordedBy	A list (concatenated and separated) of names of people responsible for the submitted dataset	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Project	project_contact	A contact person and their contact (i.e., email address) for data enquiry	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Project	project_id	A brief, concise project identifier with no spaces or special characters, ensuring machine readability. This ID will be used in data file names as 'project_id'.	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Project	assay_type	The method used in the eDNA study to detect taxon/taxa of interest in environmental sample. A targeted eDNA assay is designed to detect the presence of a specific species or a small subset of taxa (such as a genus or family) using techniques like quantitative PCR (qPCR). This contrasts with a metabarcoding eDNA assay which aims to characterise the composition of broader taxonomic communities, often encompassing multiple phyletic groups, by utilising high-throughput sequencing such as metabarcoding	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Data management	checkls_ver	The version number of the FAIR eDNA (FAIRe) metadata checklist used to format the data	M	Mandatory

data_type	section	term_name	description	requirement level code	requirement level
sampleMetadata ampData stdData experimentRunMetadata	Sample information	samp_name	Sample Name is a name that you choose for the sample. It can have any format, but we suggest that you make it concise, unique and consistent within your lab, and as informative as possible. Every Sample Name from a single Submitter must be unique.	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample information	samp_category	A type/category of a sample. "Sample" includes biological and technical replicates. If negative or positive control was selected, provide further information under the terms fill neg_cont_type and pos_cont_type.	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample information	neg_cont_type	A negative control type used in an investigation. See Table 2 in Klymus et al. 2024 (DOI: 10.3897/mbmg.8.128689) for the description of each control type, how and why it's created. For example, process negative is a sample added during processing that lacks target DNA, such as blank filter papers.	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample information	pos_cont_type	A positive control type used in an investigation. See Table 2 in Klymus et al. 2024 (DOI: 10.3897/mbmg.8.128689) for the description of each control type, how and why it's created. For example, PCR positive is a introduced target material to monitor for PCR success, including moch community samples. Provide further details (e.g., synthetic DNA) where applicable.	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample collection	decimalLongitude	The geographic longitude in decimal degrees using WGS84 datum. Positive values are east of the Greenwich Meridian, negative values are west of it. Legal values lie between -180 and 180, inclusive. The desired minimum number of decimal places is the hundred-thousandth (0.00001) to achieve meter scale resolution.	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample collection	decimalLatitude	The geographic latitude in decimal degrees using WGS84 datum. Positive values are north of the Equator, negative values are south of it. Legal values lie between -90 and 90, inclusive. The desired minimum number of decimal places is the hundred-thousandth (0.00001) to achieve meter scale resolution.	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample collection	geo_loc_name	The geographical origin of the sample as defined by the country or sea name followed by regions and localities. Country or sea names should be chosen from the INSDC Geographic Location Name List INSDC country list (http://insdc.org/country.html). Fixed format following <country or sea names>:<region>,<locality>. E.g., "USA: Maryland,	M	Mandatory

data_type	section	term_name	description	requirement level code	requirement level
			Bethesda" , "Atlantic Ocean:Charlie Gibbs Fracture Zone"		
sampleMetadata	Sample collection	eventDate	The date and time of sampling, either as an instance (single point in time) or interval. Must follow ISO 8601 format (yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ss). Time zone must be specified after the timestamp (e.g., "2008-01-23T19:23-06:00" in the time zone six hours earlier than UTC, "2008-01-23T19:23Z" at UTC time). In case no exact time is available, the date/time can be right truncated i.e. all of these are valid times: 2008-01-23T19:23:10+00:00; 2008-01-23T19:23:10Z; 2008-01-23; 2008-01; 2008; Except: 2008-01; 2008 all are ISO8601 compliant. A date and time range can be specified using a forward slash (/) to separate the start and end values (e.g., 2008-01-23T19:23-06:00/2008-01-23T19:53-06:00). A duration can also be provided using the eventDurationValue term.	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample collection	env_broad_scale	Major environmental system your sample came from. The systems identified should have a coarse spatial grain, to provide the general environmental context of where the sampling was done. Select from ENVO's biome class: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_00000428 . Examples include; estuarine biome [ENVO:01000020], tropical moist broadleaf forest biome [ENVO:01000228],	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample collection	env_local_scale	The entity or entities which are in your sample or specimen's local vicinity and which you believe have significant causal influences on your sample. Select from ENVO's layer class: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_01000281 . Examples include; marine pelagic zone [ENVO:00000208], estuarine coastal surface layer [ENVO:01001302], shrub layer [ENVO:01000336]	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Sample collection	env_medium	Environmental material or materials (pipe separated) immediately surrounded your sample prior to sampling. Select from ENVO's environmental material class (entity/continuant/independent continuant/material entity/environmental material): http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_00010483 . Examples include; soil [ENVO:00001998], marine sediment [ENVO:03000033], air [ENVO:00002005], sea water [ENVO:00002149], fresh water [ENVO:00002011], tap water [ENVO:00003096], fecal material [ENVO:00002003], digestive tract environment [ENVO:2100002], intestine environment	M	Mandatory

data_type	section	term_name	description	requirement level code	requirement level
			[ENVO:2100002], planktonic material [ENVO:01000063]		
projectMetadata	PCR	pcr_0_1	Was PCR performed in the study? Yes = 1, No (pcr-free approaches including shotgun metagenomics, Nanopore) = 0	M	Mandatory
ampData stdData	PCR	technical_rep_id	An integer uniquely identifying a specific PCR technical replicate within a sample.	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata sampleMetadata ampData experimentRunMetadata stdData eLowQuantData	PCR	assay_name	A brief, concise identifier for assay with no spaces or special characters, ensuring machine readability. This ID will be used in file names as 'assay_name'.	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	PCR	targetTaxonomic Assay	Taxa or species name targeted by the primers, probes, and/or other approaches applied in the PCR.	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	PCR	pcr_primer_forward	Forward PCR primer (5' - 3') that were used to amplify the sequence of the targeted gene. The primer sequence should NOT contain MID and adapter sequences, and should be reported in uppercase letters. If multiple forward primers are present in a single PCR reaction, either report them separately in separate submissions (with separate OTU tables for each primer set), or list the primers here separated by pipe () and provide one OTU table resulting from all the primers applied here. The latter is recommended only when the multiple primers target the same gene region and thus a single OTU table was generated from the multiplexed PCR. This term is required except for PCR free methods.	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	PCR	pcr_primer_reverse	Reverse PCR primer (5' - 3') that were used to amplify the sequence of the targeted gene. The primer sequence should NOT contain MID and adapter sequences, and should be reported in uppercase letters. If multiple reverse primers are present in a single PCR reaction, either report them separately in separate submissions (with separate OTU tables for each primer set), or list the primers here separated by pipe () and provide one OTU table resulting from all the primers applied here. The latter is recommended only when the multiple primers target the same gene region and thus a single OTU table was generated from the multiplexed PCR. This term is required except for PCR free methods.	M	Mandatory

data_type	section	term_name	description	requirement level code	requirement level
experimentRunMetadata ampData stdData	PCR	pcr_plate_id	PCR plate ID. This identifier is particularly crucial when location-specific standard curves are employed for targeted assay detections, as it ensures a linkage between the standards and the corresponding eDNA samples. If two-step PCR was applied for a metabarcoding approach, enter the second PCR protocol under the term pcr2_* in the library preparation/sequencing section.	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Targeted assay detection	amp_vis_method	Amplicon visualisation method (i.e., qPCR, dPCR, gel electrophoresis, PCR capillary electrophoresis (PCR-CE), Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP)) to determine the detection of a targeted taxon	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Targeted assay detection	detection_criteria	Criteria to determine positive detection. For example, a certain number of positive amplifications per sample, sanger sequencing of amplicons	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Targeted assay detection	pcr_assay_lod	Assay's limit of detection (LOD) (the lowest amount of target taxon DNA that can be detected with a defined level of confidence).	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Targeted assay detection	pcr_assay_lod_unit	Unit for pcr_assay_lod	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Targeted assay detection	pcr_assay_loq	Assay's limit of quantification (LOQ) (the lowest amount of target taxon DNA that can be quantitatively determined with a stated precision under the stated experimental conditions).	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Targeted assay detection	pcr_assay_loq_unit	unit for pcr_assay_loq	M	Mandatory
projectMetadata	Targeted assay detection	thresholdQuantificationCycle	Threshold for change in fluorescence signal between cycles. No unit.	M	Mandatory
stdData	Targeted assay detection	std_conc	Input quantity of qPCR standard DNA	M	Mandatory
stdData	Targeted assay detection	std_conc_unit	Unit for input quantity of qPCR standard DNA	M	Mandatory

data_type	section	term_name	description	requirement level code	requirement level
ampData stdData	Targeted assay detection	quantificationCycle	The number of cycles required for the fluorescent signal to cross a given value threshold above the baseline for each technical replicate. Quantification cycle (Cq), threshold cycle (Ct), crossing point (Cp), and take-off point (TOP) refer to the same value from the real-time instrument. Use of quantification cycle (Cq), is preferable according to the RDML (Real-Time PCR Data Markup Language) data standard (http://www.rdml.org). Use "NA" (not zero) to indicate no amplification occurred. Unit = Cycle	M	Mandatory
sampleMetadata	Targeted assay detection	detected_notDetected	Detection of the targeted taxon for each biological replicate, based on the specified detection criteria (detailed under the term 'detection_criteria'). Detected = 1, Not detected = 0. For projects employing multiple assays, this term should be specified separately for each assay. The term name should include the assay identifier in the format detected_notDetected_<assay_name> (e.g., detected_notDetected_eSERU5).	M	Mandatory
experimentRunMetadata	Library preparation sequencing	lib_id	An identifier of a library (an amplicon of a sample with unique MIDs)	M	Mandatory
experimentRunMetadata	Library preparation sequencing	seq_run_id	A brief, concise identifier for sequencing run with no spaces or special characters, ensuring machine readability. This ID will be used in file names as 'seq_run_id'.	M	Mandatory

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

